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List of Abbreviation and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AOE	Action Oriented Experimentation
CB	Capacity building
CPD	Continual Professional Development
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GADAP	Gender and Diversity Action Plan
GAP	Gender Action Plan
GILL	Gendered Innovation Living Labs
GRSIE	Gender Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Labs
LMIC	Low to middle income country
QH	Quadruple Helix
RI&E	Research, innovation and entrepreneurship
SDG	United Nation's Sustainable Development Goal
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the final impact analysis of the **Gendered Innovation Living Labs (GILL)** project, synthesising evidence from all work packages and 15 Action-Oriented Experimentations (AOEs) to assess GILL's contribution to advancing gender equality in **research, innovation and entrepreneurship (RI&E)** within the European Research Area (ERA). The analysis is structured around the expected outcomes defined in the Description of Action—**EO1: Advances in knowledge and practice** and **EO2: Strengthening innovation and inclusiveness in the ERA**—and their associated pathways to impact.

GILL demonstrates that persistent gender inequalities in RI&E cannot be effectively addressed through isolated interventions focused solely on representation, institutional procedures, or research content. Instead, the project makes a substantive contribution by identifying and operationalising a **fourth “fix” for gender equality: the Cultural Fix**. This approach targets the everyday norms, practices, meanings, and power relations that shape innovation ecosystems and systematically disadvantage women and other underrepresented groups. By foregrounding culture as a site of intervention, GILL addresses a critical gap in EU gender equality and innovation policy, where cultural dynamics are widely acknowledged but rarely tackled through concrete, transferable methods.

Across its lifetime, GILL generated **validated tools, methods, and practices for Gender Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship (GRSIE)** and tested them in real-world settings through AOEs spanning health, the green transition, the digital transition, and cross-sectoral innovation. These Action-Oriented Experimentations functioned as living laboratories, producing evidence of impact at **micro- and meso- levels** of RI&E ecosystems, including changes in organisational practices, team dynamics, innovation processes, data use, and stakeholder awareness. While systemic and macro-level impacts necessarily extend beyond the project timeframe, GILL has demonstrably laid the foundations for longer-term structural change.

The project's outputs and outcomes contribute to three interrelated Horizon Europe impact areas:

1. **A more open, inclusive and gender-equal R&I system**, through the development and application of GRSIE tools that reshape organisational cultures, innovation practices, and decision-making processes.
2. **Stronger alignment of R&I with societal needs, values and expectations**, by embedding gender and intersectional perspectives into innovation design, data practices, and citizen engagement mechanisms.
3. **Enhanced knowledge sharing and collaboration**, enabled by the GILL Hub, mentoring and capacity-building programmes, and the integration of GILL resources into European Living Lab networks.

A key exploitable result of the project is the **GILL Hub**, an open-access, sustainable platform hosting validated tools, case studies, training materials, mentoring resources, and policy-relevant guidance. Developed through participatory and iterative Living Lab processes, the Hub operationalises the Cultural Fix and supports the implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and gender-responsive innovation practices across diverse contexts. Its planned integration into the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) provides a credible pathway for sustainability, scaling, and long-term exploitation beyond the project's duration.

Impact evidence has been systematically gathered throughout the project lifecycle using mixed methods, including surveys, workshops, reflective diaries, and participatory evaluation activities. This embedded approach to impact assessment goes beyond output counting, capturing qualitative

change, learning processes, and emerging pathways to impact. It also informs a set of **practice-based recommendations** for managing highly diverse, fragmented R&I consortia and for strengthening impact planning and evaluation in future Horizon Europe and FP10 projects.

Overall, GILL contributes to the WIDERA objectives by strengthening inclusiveness, capacity-building, and institutional learning within the ERA. While recognising that gender equality in RI&E is a wicked problem requiring sustained, multi-level intervention, the project delivers a coherent framework, tested methodologies, and a sustainable infrastructure to support continued progress. By addressing culture as a core component of innovation systems, GILL advances both **conceptual understanding and practical capability** for achieving gender-responsive research and innovation in Europe.

1 Introduction

As outlined in the GILL Description of Action (DoA), GILL adopted the spirit of the CIVITAS 2020 Process and Impact Evaluation Framework (PIEF) (Engels, 2020) which has guided the evaluation of many EU funded projects since 2015. In so far as

'From the start of the project, it is important to engage all stakeholders and responsible persons in these organisations to agree on the objectives and targets to be evaluated, on the indicators to be used and on the data to be collected. During the project all partners should contribute to the collection of relevant data and participate in the validation and process evaluation activities to understand the impacts and the reasons why, making the story behind the figures clear to technicians and policymakers' (Engel, p27).

and that

'Evaluation is a powerful tool for learning what works, what does not, and the reasons for this. In other words, we evaluate because we want to measure the impacts, understand the story behind the figures, how measures were implemented and why we have the observed changes. This will allow to exchange experiences, learning from each other's successes and failures.' (Engels, p8).

In GILL, we have sought to embed impact evaluation into the project from the beginning, as a means of

- creating a responsible research culture,
- maintaining sight of the end goal - which was to develop a sustainable approach to reducing inequality in the RI&E ecosystem
- capturing impact, on real people, in real world contexts, through the work of the AOE's and wider project

This was achieved by providing regular opportunities for reflection, templates for data gathering and workshops. In this way, we tried to ensure that impact analysis was not merely a tick box exercise, conducted in the last 3 months of the project to capture surface, quantitative metrics (i.e. counting outputs).

Therefore, the deliverable is able to not only show where the project has, and could have impact, but also provide recommendations for future projects based on key learnings.

1.1 Purpose and organisation of D4.4

The aim of the deliverable is to show where GILL has, or could have, impact, and the steps needed to ensure that the GILL hub and its resources are used by future researchers, innovators and entrepreneurs to reduce gender inequalities in Europe. It is divided into 3 parts.

In this, the opening chapter, the project is set in its wider context by considering the wicked problem of gender equality and the slow progress towards gender equality in Europe (as revealed in the recent SheFigures 2025 report) and the difficulties of impact assessment in this area. Following this, Chapter 2 reviews the aims of the project as set out in the DoA and how different parts of the project (i.e. AOE's and WP outputs) have contributed to their fulfilment or advancement.

In the second part (chapters 3 and 4) more detailed accounts are provided of the work of the AOE's, the impact of the project on gender competence and sensitivity of partners engaged in the project,

and an exploration of past and future pathways to impact which can address gender inequalities in RI&E.

In the final part of the deliverable (chapters 5 to 7) we assess the relevance of the critical risks and barriers as laid down in the DoA, with the ones that we encountered, and which are specific to gender and RI&E. Prior to the conclusion, we set out a detailed set of recommendations related to project management, impact analysis and ways in which **GILL** could be used to deliver sustainable impact.

The Deliverable is accompanied by several annexes: the project summary form from the original DoA; a detailed description of the AOE's and the analysis of the gender competency data; and the template used to gather impact assessment data at the end of the project.

1.1.1 Relationship to other GILL deliverables and milestones

D4.4 has been written as part of T4.6: review and evaluation, led Coventry University. It is a public deliverable, intended to summarise and explain the achievements of the project, and point to key learnings that can be taken forward in ERA, RI&E and FP10 projects.

As one of the final deliverables it draws on:

- D1.1 Roadmap for GRSIE (UCPH)
- D2.1 Needs Analysis report (GAC)
- Ms14 Internal evaluation of AOE's (CU)

Where possible, we have tried to reduce replication with the last set of project deliverables. With this in mind, this deliverable should be read in conjunction with the final report (ENoLL) and:

- D3.2 Insights and recommendations report on Use-Case and Cross-Theme levels for GRSIE (AUTH)
- D4.3 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Final Report (Vi-Labs)
- D4.5 Report on policy development (FGB)
- D4.6 Exploitation and long-term sustainability (Vi-Labs)
- Ms16 Final evaluation report (AUTH)

1.1.2 Intended readership

This deliverable is intended for a wide range of stakeholders engaged in gender-responsive innovation, and the advancement of inclusive research and innovation in ERA. Its primary readership includes:

- **GILL consortium partners**, who require a consolidated overview of the impact of the project
- **Living Lab practitioners** and innovation intermediaries seeking practical insights on how the AOE's in **GILL** worked with stakeholders to achieve impact
- **Researchers and educators** working in gender studies, innovation studies, entrepreneurship, and social science evaluation who may use the findings to advance academic understanding and refine methodological approaches.
- **Policy-makers** interested in discovering how **GILL** has laid the foundations for gender equality in RI&E, and how this work could be extended.
- **European innovation networks and initiatives**, including ENoLL and related ecosystems, who can draw on the results to support capacity-building, training, and the broader institutionalization of GRSIE methods.

The report is designed to be accessible and relevant to both expert and non-expert audiences, providing actionable insights for future replication, scaling, and sustainability of gender equality.

1.2 Gender inequality

Gender inequality in research, innovation and entrepreneurship (RI&E) remains a *wicked* (Rittel and Webber, 1973) and persistent problem. Despite many initiatives (see Galligan, 2024, for a review), progress has been slower than expected: *“The European R&I sector has overall made slower-than-expected progress in improving gender equality and has particular organisational features that can make gender inequalities starker”* (Andriescu et al., 2024, p. 14).

Structural Drivers of Inequality

RI&E reflects broader societal and institutional biases across Europe, including:

- Enduring cultural norms positioning women primarily in domestic roles.
- Organisational structures that fail to recognise or reward women’s contributions.
- Persistent labour market inequalities:
 - part-time employment gap (EU avg. 20.7%; 1.1% in Romania to 44.1% in the Netherlands, 2021)
 - gender pay gap (12.7% in 2021)
 - gender pension gap (28% in 2020)
 - care gap (7.7 million women kept out of the labour market due to unpaid care, compared with 450,000 men)
- Underrepresentation of women in STEM fields, leadership roles and as entrepreneurial role models.
- Entrepreneurial norms that value traits aligned with hegemonic masculinity.
- Post-COVID working arrangements that risk widening exclusion.

Limitations of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

The main instrument for advancing gender equality in R&I is the Gender Equality Plan. Although training and support actions have expanded, GEPs are frequently criticised for:

- limited resources and excessive administrative focus,
- weak leadership commitment (sometimes driven mainly by funding eligibility),
- failure to address structural and intersectional inequalities,
- insufficient monitoring, cohesion and practical tools,
- inadequate data—particularly disaggregated data,
- lack of sustainability and fragmentation across institutions.

Structural Change and the GILL Project

The **GILL** project aims to support transformational change aligned with the EU’s vision of structural reform—changes in rules, regulations, organisational processes and cultures to better include women researchers and decision-makers, with special attention to organisational culture and everyday practices.

According to Andriescu et al. (2024), such transformation requires:

- questioning the gendered assumptions underpinning roles, practices and interventions,
- allowing time for norm reframing and practice change,
- recognising the complexity of gender inequalities,
- challenging unequal power relations,
- embedding new, equality-supportive ways of thinking and working across national, institutional and micro-level settings,
- integrating intersectionality,
- ensuring sustainability through monitoring, promotion and iterative development,
- replacing exclusionary narratives with equality-supporting discourses.

Inclusive Gendered Innovations (IGI)

To situate **GILL**'s work, this review highlights inclusive gendered innovations (IGI), defined by Karaulova et al. (2023) as an approach that:

- mainstreams sex, gender and intersectional analysis into R&D and innovation processes;
- acknowledges how unconscious bias, gender relations and structural inequalities shape innovation trajectories and beneficiaries;
- involves diverse groups directly in innovation processes.

While achieving full intersectionality may be challenging empirically, IGI should at minimum adopt Sex, Gender & Diversity Analysis (SG&DA) as a foundation.

Persistent Data Gaps

A major barrier to advancing IGI and assessing female-led RI&E is the continued lack of detailed, high-quality and intersectional data. Work undertaken during the project highlights:

- limited information on entrepreneurs' intersectional characteristics (e.g., in the UK, ethnicity data are available but patchy),
- minimal data on entrepreneurial ambition,
- systematic under-reporting of micro-businesses.

1.2.1 Female entrepreneurship

Data from She Figures show that women are underrepresented among inventors (9 %) and authors in academic-corporate collaboration teams (26%), and in 2022, the self-employment rate among women was 9 %, compared to 16 % for men. Gender gaps are identified in capital investment of tech start-ups, where all-men founding teams dominate (82 % of all investment, compared to 15 % of mixed gender and 3 % of all-women teams), and in venture capital leadership, with women comprising only 16 % of general partners.

Tzanakou (2025) summarised that

- Women exhibit lower levels of activity than men in initiating and managing new businesses. About 6 % of women in the EU (compared to 8 % of men) and 9 % of women in OECD countries (compared to 11 % of men) were actively working on a start-up or managing a new business (<42 months old)

over the period 2018–2022, with slightly higher figures for the Netherlands and Latvia (where women reported limited employment opportunities,

- The gender gap in self-employment is slowly closing. The self-employment rate among women in the EU is 9 %, compared to 16 % for men (2022 data), although there is an overall downturn in self-employment by 6 % overall in the EU over the last decade and the gender gap has increased substantially over the past decade in Croatia, Estonia, Latvia, Poland and Slovakia.
- Gender gap demographics amongst self-employed people. Self-employed women in the EU are about 30 % less likely than men to be employers (2022 data). Self-employed women in the EU are, on average, younger than self-employed men. 55 % of self-employed women are aged 25–49 years old, compared to 50 % of self-employed men (2022 data).
- Barriers such as self-perceived fear of failure and skills gaps hinder women in business creation. Nearly half of women in the EU report that a fear of failure prevents them from starting a business, compared to slightly more than 40 % of men. Women are about 75 % as likely as men to report that they have the necessary skills for starting business, indicating both skills gaps and self-confidence gaps.

Supporting this data, Christensen et al.’s (forthcoming) analysis of entrepreneurship shows in Denmark and the UK revealed many gender-based differences between men and women who were pitching for investment in their start-ups; for example, overconfidence and overvaluation by men; imposter syndrome and lack of confidence by women; as well as biases amongst investors – with most investment going to young males, or all male teams. Looking longitudinally across many series, there is a significant change in the presentation of the show, away from stereotypical representations of entrepreneurship (toxic masculinity) towards more socially oriented and eco-friendly businesses.

1.2.2 University spin-outs

The EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025 highlights the need to strengthen the participation of women in STEM across education, research and innovation, including through gender-inclusive STEAM pathways and support for incubators within higher education institutions (HEIs) (EC, 2023). It also recognises the persistent challenge of attracting and retaining diverse talent, particularly in STEM fields where women remain underrepresented.

The ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024 identifies academic spin-outs and inclusive gender innovation (IGI) as contributors to several priority actions, including talent circulation and mobility, gender equality and inclusiveness, knowledge valorisation and the development of stronger R&I ecosystems (EC, 2021).

Academic spin-outs play a critical role in R&I valorisation by supporting knowledge commercialisation and fostering entrepreneurial skills within research performing organisations. However, comparative research on academic entrepreneurship remains limited, and existing analyses tend to focus narrowly on economic performance. Broader outcome measures—such as sustainability, wellbeing, and job satisfaction—are needed, alongside systematic data on spin-out activity (e.g. volume, sector, maturity, and actor involvement) from an inclusive, ecosystem-level perspective (Miranda et al., 2017).

Women remain significantly underrepresented among academic spin-out founders, accounting for approximately 13–17 % across studies (Tzanakou, 2025). Contributing factors include micro-level influences such as career stage, skills, confidence, family circumstances, and women’s underrepresentation in senior and STEM roles, as well as meso- and macro-level gendered structures,

cultures, and practices within academic entrepreneurship. Research from the **GILL** project further highlights the compounded barriers faced by ethnic minority women, including familial and societal influences (Hacsek et al., 2024).

At the macro level, cultural norms, policy frameworks, infrastructure, and media representations continue to reinforce a masculine model of entrepreneurship, positioning women as exceptions rather than norms (Christensen et al., forthcoming). Addressing these systemic barriers requires more inclusive research, innovation and entrepreneurship environments. The **GILL** project contributes to this agenda by providing tools, methods, good practice examples, and targeted support through mentoring and networks to advance gender equality in academic spin-outs.

1.2.3 Research and innovation

SheFigures report persistent gender gaps in inventorships, scientific publications and academic-corporate collaboration:

- Women are underrepresented among inventors. In the EU, women make up only 9 % of inventors, compared to a global average of 12 %. Some countries, notably Portugal, Croatia, Spain, and Lithuania, report higher proportions of women inventors, exceeding 15 %.
- There has been little change in the proportion of women holding patents over the past decade.
- Women inventorships have increased but still vary across technology areas. In sectors like chemistry and metallurgy, women account for 21 % of inventorships, while in mechanical engineering and construction, this figure drops to just 3 %.
- Only 5 % of inventorship teams are gender balanced. Most teams were men-only or men-majority (more than 90 %) while only a small fraction of all patent applications (4 %) comprised solely or mostly women.
- Women are less likely to be active authors especially as they advance in seniority across all fields. Only 16 % of authorship teams exhibit gender balance, with the majority comprising 60 % or more men, accounting for 31 % of all teams.
- Fewer women than men are authors in academic-corporate collaboration teams. At EU level, women comprise an average of 26 % of authors on academic-corporate collaboration teams, a slight increase from 22 % compared to She Figures 2021.

Although some member states are introducing strategies for gender equality in R&I, substantial gender gaps remain in relation to women's senior leadership and management of projects and research centres, authorship, patenting, and network strength. This is exacerbated by the motherhood penalty, Mathilda effect, leaky pipelines, discriminatory HR policies, attitudes and stereotypes in STEM. Women are catching up, but are still overrepresented in health, care, education, services, social enterprises. Importantly the sectors in which they are overrepresented receive less attention (GENDERACTION, 2019) and are not seen by Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) and funding bodies as being able to generate commercial value (Amble et al, 2013; GENDERACTION, 2019). The support of university TTOs (or equivalent, such as Intellectual Property or Business Development Officers) is of key importance in developing spin outs as they can be the gatekeepers to internal support and external funds. If they do not see substantial commercial benefit for the university, they will not support spin-outs – effectively strangling an idea before it has taken its first breath and demoralising the research team. Such factors are also present across national and EU funding bodies and policy makers. Whilst understandable from a business perspective, wider opportunities (e.g., to

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effect social and cultural change) are missed (Vohora et al, 2004), and the stereotype of successful entrepreneurs (tech savvy, young male) is perpetuated – as explored in Christensen et al. (forthcoming).

1.2.4 Women’s participation in research teams

Gender balance in research teams of scientific publications is becoming more prevalent yet remains a challenge. Women are still underrepresented among researchers, with SheFigures 2024 reporting that only one-third (33.7 %) of European researchers (all fields of research considered) are women (EC, 2024). This is despite the known benefits of mixed gender teams where women can influence the nature and approach of research, as well as the research questions posed; a higher inclusion of sex-based or gender-based analysis and better usage of team members, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and a higher number of publications. However, Pinheiro et al. (2024) found little research or agreement on the relationship between team composition gender and research impact. Their detailed multivariate analysis of the impact of gender composition in research teams on patent and policy-related documents in science revealed a complicated picture with outcomes influenced by team size, number of authors, seniority, discipline, etc. Results included that in scientific publications, the share of publications cited by policy increases as the participation of women increases in health; in sciences in general and in research related to SDG13 and AI that the uptake in patents decreases with greater numbers of women co-authors of publication.

Given the systemic nature of gender inequality throughout all aspects of E&I, and the failure of other EU initiatives to level the playing field, one 3-year project is unlikely to achieve major impact within its lifetime. **GILL**’s achievement of the many KPIs listed in section 2.1.2 and elsewhere in the DoA are documented in companion deliverables (see section 1.1).

D4.4 considers the steps taken by the project to lay the foundations for and drive forward impact in WIDERA through assessment of the pathways to impact. We expect the project outcomes to have a positive impact on the some of the six key dimensions identified in the SheFigures index, i.e. pipeline segregation, research sectors, career progression, decision-making, research participation, and the incorporation of a gender dimension in research and innovation output

1.2.5 National statistics

Not all countries in the consortium were analysed in detail in the SheFigures report¹. The table below summarises the most pressing challenges for each country. These map onto **GILL**’s macro level objectives in particular, A) organisational and cultural change and B) professional development (as discussed in further detail in Chapter 2. In addition, specific AOE’s tackled issues of national importance with respect to RI&E at a more local level (as described in Chapter 4). This is indicative of the impact the project could have on national RI&Es.

Table 1. Mapping of gender inequality issues per country on to **GILL** aims and objectives

Country	Pressing gender inequality issues as per SheFigures (2024), In all cases there is a need to:	Mapping on to AOE activity
Spain	Increase women’s academic standing, leadership of HEIs and efforts as innovators.	

¹ https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/interactive-reports/she-figures-2024#new__map

Denmark	Increase the proportion of women researchers in the business enterprise sector, as heads of HEIs and better representation among patent applicants.	
Germany	Increase the proportion of women S&Es in the total labour force and in researchers in the business enterprise sector as well as women holding Grade A positions and submitting patent applications.	AOE13
Czech Republic		AOE12
Italy	Provide career advancement opportunities and efforts to increase number of women in leadership and decision-making positions and improving prospects in science and engineering and the number of research outputs, particularly as authors of publications and patent inventors.	AOE8
Romania	Ensure that women have equal access to leadership and decision-making positions in HEIs and improved employment opportunities in science and technology occupations also need to be improved.	AOE11
France	Increase the proportion of women among self-employed S&E and ICT professionals, to increase the share of women holding Grade A positions and as heads of HEIs, and to increase women's research and innovation outputs.	
Greece	Target action on boosting women's presence in senior academic grades, institutional leadership, grant-holding principal investigator roles, and patenting/authorship output.	AOE10
UK²	Target increasing women's share of Grade A leadership roles, senior institutional positions, research funding, leadership and research outputs (authorships and patents).	AOE3

1.3 Factors to consider in impact assessment

In their critique of current approaches to impact, Ma and Agner (2022), started their paper with the following statements:

'Impact assessment is challenging. It is because the notion of impact encompasses a wide range of events and changes: some smaller in scale, some wider in scope; some focus on local communities, some aim at solving global challenges; some can be achieved tomorrow, while others may take decades or generations to be realised. Impact assessment is challenging also because individuals, from researchers to policymakers to the general public, have different conceptions of impact: what constitute positive impacts and meaningful contributions now and in the future?' (Ma and Agner, p289).

Research has to be measured objectively, its learnings distilled, its impact and effectiveness measured. This is possible for outputs and perhaps outcomes, but wider impact ambitions and claims may be hard to substantiate (Watermeyer, 2014; Chubb and Watermeyer, 2017) within the lifetime of a project.

² Uk was not included in SheFigures report, Equivalent information has been sources from HESA, Advance HE, WISE and. UKRI

The logic model of Impact (also referred to as the impact journey) is based on the original Logic Model Development Guide published by the Kellogg Foundation (2004) and is used to guide many funded projects and research excellence assessments. In **GILL**, its influence can clearly be seen in, for example, Section 2 of the DoA and the Summary table (reproduced in Annex 1). While the first 3 stages shown in Figure 1 are ‘research focussed’ leading to recognisable, and accredited/peer reviewed outputs, the outcomes are steps towards impact. They are not ‘impact’ by definition, which requires a change in academic, cultural, economic, educational, environmental, health, political, societal, and /or technological fields. Such impacts are possible (especially in STEM fields) but are unlikely in the social sciences, where changes to policy, culture and practice may take decades to achieve even when a direct influence can be shown, with no confounding variables.

Figure 1. The impact journey (adapted from UCD Research Impact Toolkit.³ As reproduced in Ma and Agnew (2022)

In relation to **GILL** these relationships are shown in Annex 1, and represented graphically in Figure 2, which provides a simplified representation of the linkages of the tables in the DoA, Sections 2.1.2. and 2.1.3. These link the project to the wider ambitions in the EU and ERA to create a fairer, more inclusive and gender equal society.

The pathways to impact outlined in the DoA, mainly concentrated on short and occasional medium-term impacts in relation to the WIDERA work programme. Table 2 is indicative of the type of activities undertaken.

Table 2. Indicative table summarising first 4 stages on **GILL**'s journey to impact

Impact journey stage	Examples from GILL
Inputs	EU and UKRI project funding, additional institutional funds to support outputs (e.g. GILL book; conference attendance; open access publications; background knowledge

³ <https://www.uck.ie/impacttoolkit/whatisimpact>),

	and experience of partners; research facilities, networks and know-how; commitment of partners to gender equality.
Activities	As described and managed in the WPs. These included advancing knowledge of gender inequalities, through interviews, LR and practice)development of the 4 th fix, and tools and methods to change cultural practices; activities supporting the design and development of the GILL platform (including surveys, codesign workshops and IT development); experimentation – in relation to design and testing of methods; primary research; AOE activities managed by WP3; reporting, monitoring and evaluation.
Outputs	Outputs are measured against KPIs as stated in the DoA. As befitting a R&I project these have included conference papers, journal articles, Zenodo ⁴ and you tube ⁵ pages. a forthcoming book (Christensen et al, 2026) and final conference; a set of validated tools and methods to support cultural change, citizen social science courses. Full details are provided in D4.6. Section 2.3.6.
Outcomes	Tangible outcomes include 2 new companies, new LL, plans for consultancy services, development of citizen scientists, organisational change processes at host organizations (e.g. D4D, Experimentarium), use of gender competency workshop by external parties, policy notes. Currently 15 citations have been found for GILL papers.

The research grant enabled completion of all major activities, but was insufficient

- to cover outputs such as the rising cost of publications and conference attendance, which in turn reduced potential impact and reach of the project
- to provide expertise to realise certain activities such as prototyping and technical development in the form of IT support, this in turn reduced the impact, significance and TRL of some of the project outcomes, e.g., mobility game, gender competency workshop, OIP for democratising design and discussion forum.

A brief overview of progress in meeting the Key Performance Indicators is shown in table 3. More in depth analysis is provided in D4.3. These represent key outcome and activities through which **GILL** delivered in its expected outcomes and short-term impact.

Table 3. Illustrative KPIs from Dissemination and Communication Actions

Examples of Dissemination KPIs			Examples of Communication KPIs		
<u>Tool</u>	<u>Type</u>	<u>By M35</u>	<u>Tool</u>	<u>Target</u>	<u>By M35</u>
EU level events	Conferences & thematic webinars	Achieved	GILL website	50K visits	11.5k sessions, 22k views, 72k events counts
Scientific publications and data sets	Books, (non) peer reviewed papers etc, OPEN and FAIR dataset	Achieved	Project output downloads	1000	519 on Zenodo

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/GILL-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/@GILLProject>

Public sector	<i>Targeted recommendations and whitepapers</i>	Achieved	Social media	1k followers	1024
Local community	<i>Average of 15+ interactions and outreach events by partner</i>	Achieved		5 videos with 20K views	11 videos with 2904 views

GILL's Expected Outcomes (EOs) lay in EO1: Advancing knowledge and practice with respect to gender, and in EO2: Strengthening innovation and inclusiveness in ERA (through increasing gender equality). Each of these have their own pathways and ways in which progress can be measured through quantifiable outcomes in both the short and long term. While short (and some long) term measures in all cases in EO1 have been achieved in the project lifetime, EO2 remains more problematic. Certainly, GRSIE tools, methods, and mentorship resources can be used to strengthen and empower individuals (Pathway 2a), but longer-term measures for all pathways, especially those related to EO2 will not only take time to develop, as they require additional support from ERA and the EC at policy, funding and strategy levels.

Figure 2. Summary of Expected Outcomes, Pathways and Impacts in **GILL**

The three areas of impact are at the centre of Figure 2, i.e., Impact 1: an enhanced more open and inclusive R&I system; Impact 2; Stronger alignment of strategic R&I with society needs, expectation and values; Impact 3: knowledge and collaboration, and their associated pathways and the activities/outputs which can contribute to the wider EU impact. These are reviewed in more detail in the following chapters.

In a project, such as **GILL**, activities are extremely fragmented. The 15 Action Oriented Experimentations (AOEs) were, in some ways, the powerhouse behind the project, validating tools and methods and demonstrating changes in local entrepreneurial ecosystems. However, their contribution to impact via the pathways outlined in Figure 2 has been hard to assess. This was partly addressed through the Impact Analysis workshop in which partners were asked to focus on Impact across the project (see chapter 4.1.). The workshop was designed to fill a key gap in knowledge, conceptualised in Figure 3, concerning how a pathway to impact is operationalised and made effective.

The results from the workshop have led to experience-based recommendations related to experiences in the co-ordination of a fragmented project.

Figure 3. Gap in knowledge about pathways to impact

1.4 Summary

GILL commenced in 2022, with the initial proposal developed in 2021. During this time a lot of positive changes have been made in the consideration, wider acceptance and understanding of gender inequality and intersectionality in the EU; yet progress has been slower than hoped. This chapter has provided an updated state of the art with respect to gender inequality in RI&E and started to show where **GILL** has had an impact or would hope to fit into wider movements within the EU and ERA and support further initiatives. This is explored further in the companion deliverable, D4.6 which is more policy oriented.

Gender equality in RI&E is a wicked problem, requiring not only the capturing of hearts and minds, but practical methods to implement, monitor and enforce it, acting in concert with economic, ethical, and scientific arguments about its necessity. Arguments which are needed more than ever in the light of geopolitical movements which are threatening women's rights in RI&E.

The chapter has also opened up questions about impact and how the far reaching societal and cultural changes anticipated in the DoA can be usefully measured. The following chapters address in more detail the projects impact and legacy in relation to the DoA and wider goals of the ERA.

2 Impact as specified in the DoA

2.1 Introduction to the GILL project

The **GILL** project aimed to develop a pan-European collaboration and learning hub based on Living Lab principles which could act as open innovation framework for all European actors and support open gendered innovation. The co-created hub/platform will provide a sustainable mechanism to increase Gender Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship (GRSIE) by fixing practices and culture across the European ecosystems.

Although the original intention was to develop a 'Gender innovation living lab' as part of the suite of ENoLL accredited Living Labs, the plan is now to integrate the platform (and associated activities) into ENoLL itself, where it can be better embedded into the everyday practice of LLs and be serviced by the Working Group in Gender Innovation (as described in D4.6). This will allow a clear sustainable pathway for **GILL** after the lifetime of the project and enable it to influence all LLs in the future (e.g., through gender and diversity competence certification and mentorship).

GILL had 4 macro-objectives:

- OA to enable the organisational and cultural changes,
- OB to enhance professional development,
- OC to increase the integration of gender and diversity into product design, technologies and innovation,
- OD to allow gendered educational practices.

In parallel, its Action Oriented Experimentation (AOEs) sought to contribute to

- horizontal spheres of innovation (*individual & team, tools & methods, innovation & products, societal processes*) and
- three vertical EU priority areas (*Health and resilience, Green & Digital transition*).

Both the **GILL** platform and the AOEs were implemented through an iterative, co-creation approach structured on a four-phases cycle (*understand, co-design, implement, evaluate*) repeated twice to incorporate the feedback and evaluation results. In line with LL methodology, co-creation and open innovation were fostered among the main actors of the Quadruple Helix model - citizens, government, industry, and academia – whose engagement was sought in different participatory activities throughout the project.

The 15 AOEs in 8 European countries developed new approaches to GRSIE within their own fields of reference whilst at the same time, testing and validating the GRSIE tools and methods in real-life open ecosystems.

Through this cycle, **GILL** aimed to deliver a systemic review of barriers to GRSIE leading to the co-design of proven methodologies, services, and tools for GRSIE (as documented in Christensen et al., 2026) to be made widely available on a sustainable and easy to use platform.

2.1.1 Gender Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship

Gender Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship (GRSIE) was not defined in the DoA, but in an earlier deliverable, Woodcock and Christensen (2023) provided the following working definition for GRSIE in the context of **GILL**:

'GRSIE is a reaction against one sided innovations that only take into account the technological side and which only benefit one group. It can be disruptive, reactive and challenging.

It is a means of responding to real world challenges holistically and with new indicators, in ways which prioritise and address gender and other intersectional characteristics together with material innovations.

'Smartness' is implied not only in the use of technology, but also in the mindsets and methods of those engaged in the innovation ecosystem. Products and systems are 'smarter' when they are integrated with, and build on existing solutions, when they are inclusive, i.e. benefitting everyone, not creating worse problems by prioritising the needs of one group, or innovation at the expense of others.

'Gender responsive smartness' requires aspiring innovators and entrepreneurs to work in new ways, with new partners and cutting-edge technologies, - to disrupt old ways of thinking and services, particularly in enabling women and those from previously excluded groups to have a voice, and to encourage innovations and socio material designs and services, which are based on their shared experiences.

It also requires the development of a culture which values and uses these inputs. GILL activities address the need to fix cultures and ways of working which impede GRSIE.'

This is known as the fourth fix.

2.2 The cultural fix

The concept of a "fix" originates from the Gendered Innovations project, a "fix" is not a simple solution. A "fix" in itself could be defined as a 'pathway to impact' i.e., *a structured process through which research findings are translated into real-world applications that generate benefits for society, policy, or practice.*" (Alimohammadzadeh et al., 2016; Yeo, 2010).

The 2010, Gendered Innovations project aligned with Europe's ambition to lead global technology and innovation. It introduced a conceptual and methodological framework for systematically integrating gender perspectives into research and innovation policies at the European level. Through case studies, it demonstrated how sex, gender, and intersectional analysis enhance the robustness, reliability, and societal relevance of research and innovation. The project emphasized that needs, behaviours, and attitudes are gendered and shape scientific inquiry and technological development, concluding that incorporating gender dimensions is the most effective way to address these issues across disciplines and sectors (Schiebinger & Klinge, 2010; Schiebinger & Schraudner, 2011).

The original 3 fixes were:

Fix the Numbers. A strategy seeking to increase the participation of women and other underrepresented groups by integrating them into existing structures. It emphasizes the use of statistics and data to document gender gaps in areas such as recruitment, salaries, research staff, and management. Conceptually linked to feminist empiricism, it prioritizes evidence-based approaches. More recently, this strategy has been associated with *business feminism*, particularly in top management, finance, and entrepreneurship (Fodor, Glass & Nagy, 2019).

Fix the Institutions An approach promoting structural change within research and innovation organizations to create inclusive environments. It addresses barriers such as inadequate parental

leave, childcare facilities, and work-life balance policies. Rooted in standpoint and socialist feminist theory, it values the lived experiences of women and marginalized groups. Common interventions include gender quotas, transparent recruitment policies, and broader reflections on welfare and social policy (European Commission, 2013).

Fix the Knowledge This was the core focus of the Gendered Innovations project, this strategy advances excellence in science and technology by integrating sex, gender, and intersectional analysis into research. It challenges static categories of sex and gender, viewing them as socially constructed and fluid. Gender, alongside other human categories such as age, race, and ability, is analysed in relation to cultural and technological contexts to produce more robust and socially relevant knowledge (European Commission, 2013).

Building on these, **GILL** introduced the **Cultural Fix** as a transformative approach to gender and innovation. While the existing strategies are valuable, they remain insufficient. The Cultural Fix addresses implicit norms, practices, and meanings across micro (teams), meso (organizations), and macro (institutions) levels, highlighting how culture shapes team dynamics, governance structures, and broader ecosystems. It offers new analytical and policy perspectives and tackles a central dilemma in feminist science: should women be integrated into existing structures, or should those structures—and the knowledge they produce—be fundamentally transformed? (Schiebinger, 1987).

This fix emphasizes transformative rather than integrative change, positioning cultural change as a core component of innovation and entrepreneurship. The **GILL** project not only

1. Developed the fourth fix
2. Provided tools and methods to change cultural practices in RI&E
3. Illustrated how this could be used in the AOE
4. Widely communicated and disseminated the cultural fix in publications, online events and role models (i.e the AOE) to increase knowledge and practice, in line with Pathways 1a Advance knowledge and 1b Advancing practice as part of expected Outcome, O1; Advances in knowledge and practice
5. Provided mentorship and guidance to advance women and those from non -traditional entrepreneurial backgrounds through a range of curated material on the **GILL** hub.

The Cultural Fix Elaborated

The Cultural Fix builds on the recent “cultural turn” in entrepreneurship studies, which emphasizes norms, values, imaginaries, and symbolic meaning systems. While culture has often been viewed as a constraining force embedded in broader societal structures, it can also serve as an enabling resource—a strategic “toolkit” for entrepreneurs and innovators (Ang, 2020; Lounsbury et al., 2018). Entrepreneurs increasingly act as cultural operators, mobilizing cultural elements to advance their ventures. However, treating culture as static or homogeneous risks reinforcing stereotypes and binary notions of masculinity and femininity, reducing “cultural problems” to vague explanations for gender gaps. Cultural analysis must therefore move beyond essentialist views to uncover differentiated practices, interests, and power relations (Fischer, 2007).

Modern cultural studies emerged in the UK during the 1980s through the work of Stuart Hall and colleagues at the Centre for Contemporary Cultural Studies, profoundly influencing social sciences and arts in Western and postcolonial contexts (Ang, 2020). Since then, cultural analysis has gained relevance in institutional and strategic settings. This book situates cultural analysis within these broader trends and feminist debates, including research on masculinities, intersectionality, and the integration of gender and diversity into policy strategies.

Culture plays a critical role in shaping entrepreneurial ecosystems, defined as the interplay of social, political, and cultural elements that support innovation (Spigel & Harrison, 2018). Yet, major reports such as those by the World Economic Forum (2013) largely overlook cultural and gendered dimensions, focusing instead on education, finance, and infrastructure. A cultural fix requires integrating soft components (education, mentoring), hard components (finance, facilities), and compliance elements (policy frameworks), while addressing how these systems privilege or disadvantage different groups.

Figure 4. *The 4th fix of culture in innovation and entrepreneurship*

Although culture is recognised as a cornerstone of entrepreneurial ecosystems, it remains understudied (Christensen et al., 2024). A key aim of GRSIE methods is to operationalise the cultural fix by combining these components into new concepts and strategies. Culture is applied as a transversal approach—a nexus that connects and renews feminist strategies and entrepreneurial discourses, as illustrated in Figure 4. In reference to gender being a wicked problem (as discussed in Chapter 1) the green quadrants contain elements which make it so intractable (e.g. toxic masculinities, gender biases in power and agency and the embeddedness of (gender discriminatory ecosystem components such as HR policies).

The **GILL** project provides Gender-Responsive Smart Innovation and Entrepreneurship (GRSIE) tools and methods to implement the Cultural Fix in entrepreneurial and innovation contexts. These methods, developed and refined through 15 AOE in living labs across the EU, operate at the levels of team dynamics, organisational routines, and design practices. Rather than adding a superficial layer of diversity, they reshape the conditions under which innovation occurs. What unites these methods is their commitment to situated reflexivity and iterative reconfiguration of everyday and institutional practices—whether in meetings, planning, hiring, or design (Nielsen, Bloch & Schiebinger, 2018).

In summary, the Cultural Fix extends the trilogy of fixes with a fourth pillar, enriching feminist entrepreneurship studies through cultural, intersectional, and gender-responsive perspectives. This approach functions as a flexible bricolage, connecting multiple levels and topics. The chapters that follow elaborate these concepts and present new tools and strategies for embedding cultural and gender-responsive methods in innovation and entrepreneurship.

By foregrounding culture, **GILL** demonstrates how entrepreneurial ecosystems can be rethought as dynamic, gendered systems where norms and practices matter as much as finance or infrastructure. The cultural fix thus adds a critical lens for analyzing and redesigning ecosystems to foster more inclusive innovation.

2.3 Overview of GILL's pathways to impact

The impact section in the DoA was shaped in part by the aims and objectives of the funding programme in relation to the need to

- (1) address EU policy priorities through Research and Innovation (R&I),
- (2) deliver benefits and impact through R&I missions and
- (3) strengthen the uptake of innovation in society

GILL's proposed contribution to expected outcomes (EO) and impacts (EI) were specified in Section 2.1 of the DoA with an overall alignment to Key Strategic Orientation D: Creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society, as outlined in the Horizon Europe Strategic Plan. The summary overview as it appeared in the DoA been included in Annex 1 for completeness.

The success of the project in achieving the stated KPIs (as outlined in section 1.1.1.1 of the DoA) is addressed in D4.3. This section addresses how these have created or have the potential to create an impact in the fight for gender equality in RI&E in the European Research Arena and in light of the latest SheFigures report on gender equality in the EU.

2.3.1 Key Exploitable Results

GILL proposed the following Key Exploitable Results (KERs) as initial mechanisms through which impact could be achieved.

Table 4. Initial Key Exploitable Results

KER	Result	Further description	Status
1	GILL collaboration and learning hub	https://GILLhub.eu/ - open access platform	Live, populated and fully accessible and updatable. This will be transferred to ENoLL in 2026
2	GILL methodology	Embedding the cultural fix and GRSIE methods in LL iterative cycles and approaches; embedding reflective practice in evaluation and impact analysis	Proven during conduct of project, outputs produced and disseminated
3	Recommendations	Relating to reducing gender inequality in ERA etc	Included in this deliverable, D4.5 and related white papers
4	GILL toolkit	https://GILLhub.eu/explore/toolbox/ - collated & validated resources for researchers and entrepreneurs from GILL and other sources	Live, populated and fully accessible and updatable. This will be transferred to ENoLL in 2026
5	GILL mentoring, training and	The dynamic Capacity Building programme rolled out during GILL to enable the AOE's learn	The GILL CB programme was successfully completed. The GILL mentoring document is available at:

	CB programme	from their results and improve the GRSIE approach. Alongside the trainers and mentors involved in the CB programme, the GILL consortium created a service for online and offline mentoring on GRSIE and related topics available in the “Mentoring” module of the GILL hub and in the document “GILL mentoring guidelines for Gender Responsive Innovation in Organisations”	https://backend.GILLhub.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/GILL_Mentoring-Guidelines.pdf
6	ENoLL WG on GRSIE	Open access ENoLL working group for gender innovation	Established in 2024, work plan for 2026 submitted to ENoLL
7	Gender evaluation scheme for certification		Roll out scheme for gender competency workshops ⁶ and certification submitted as part of the work plan for ENoLL WG on GRSIE

2.3.1.1 1 KERs 1 and 4: The GILL hub and toolkit

The **GILL** Hub has been developed as a sustainable, extensible platform dedicated to promoting GRSIE. It comprises 8 elements as shown in the following figure

Figure 5. Overview of contents of the **GILL** platform

In accordance with the **GILL** methodology, it was developed through a participatory, user-driven process to ensure alignment with the real needs of innovation stakeholders across Europe, as outlined below.

⁶ Woodcock, A. (2025) Workshop outline <https://zenodo.org/records/17552813>

Figure 6. Overview of the development process of the hub

Its unique value is summarised as follows:

Figure 7. Value of the GILL hub

A set of KPIs were associated with the usage of the GILL hub, these are also indicative of the impact and reach of the project. Additional data shows that the GILL hub has approximately 860 active users.

Table 5. Key Performance Indicators for the GILL hub

KPI	Expected value	Value M35	Related KERs
Hub launch	1	1	KER1
Services and tools available	20+	67	KER1 and 4
Content with documents	20+	20	KER1
Mentoring programme launched	1	1	KER5

Experts in mentoring programme	5	6	KER5
Ecosystems connected	15	29	KER1
Software usability score	80/100	77/100	KER1
Users visiting the hub	200	7300	KER1 and 4
Users uploading/ downloading content	20 and 50	18 and n/a	KER1 and 4

2.3.1.2 KER2 GILL methodology

Adherence to the Gill methodology has been at the heart of the project, this has included

- the Living Lab approach which was embodied in for example
 - the iterative development of the GILL platform,
 - the co-ordinate the work of the AOE's
 - the emphasis QH engagement and codesign principles
- feminist social psychological/autoethnographic approaches to understand the lived experience through, for example the use of reflective diaries by both AOE's and project partners e.g. to reflect on organisational practices, but to also understand gender dynamics within the project
- The focus on the cultural fix and the use of GRSIE methods to change practices.

2.3.1.3 KER3 Recommendations and policy notes

The recommendations and policy notes from **GILL** in D4.5 emphasise embedding participatory and reflexive approaches into Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and innovation ecosystems, using Living Lab methodologies, peer-learning networks, and the Cultural Fix model to drive institutional change. They call for stronger governance structures, leadership accountability, and systemic incentives linking funding to demonstrable equality outcomes. Continuous learning, harmonised monitoring frameworks, and the scaling of action-oriented experiments are highlighted as key mechanisms for sustaining progress. In digital innovation, the proposals stress mandatory gender impact assessments, inclusive design standards, and interdisciplinary collaboration to mitigate bias in AI and technology development. Collectively, these measures aim to mainstream gender considerations across policy, practice, and innovation, ensuring more equitable and responsive institutions and technologies.

2.3.1.4 KERs 5,6 and 7 Capacity building, mentorship and certification of gender evaluation scheme for certification

This group of KERs are essential in maintaining and sustaining efforts to address gender equality, by providing practical support for women researchers and entrepreneurs through mentorship, training, capacity building and networking.

KER5 addressing mentoring, training, and the CB Programme, has achieved a high level of impact. The KPIs related to the number of mentors engaged and participation in Continuous Professional Development (CPD) activities have exceeded the targets defined in the DoA.

Specifically, against KPIs of 200 participants in GILL training activities and the involvement of at least 20 mentors, a total of 300 stakeholders from across the quadruple helix were trained, and 30 mentors were engaged through GILL online and offline activities.

All training sessions delivered within the framework of the GILL Capacity Building Programme have been made available via the GILL Hub under the “Training Materials” module.

The sustained, open-access availability of these materials beyond the project lifetime ensures continued capacity building and supports the long-term exploitation of project results. Post-event evaluations indicate that participants considered the sessions to be valuable, relevant, and informative, confirming the quality and effectiveness of the training programme. In GILL, mentorship and capacity building also includes the use of online material and training resources as detailed in the [GILL Mentoring Guidelines for Gender-Responsive Innovation in Organisations](#). Central to the future development and usefulness of this will be the further integration of the discussion forum and network enabling women to work together and discuss ideas in a safe on-line environment.

KER6 - the Working Group for GRSIE - now entitled Working Group for Gender and Innovation was established in 2024, with an inaugural meeting at the OLLD2024 in Timisoara. A detailed calendar of events and action has been put forward and submitted to the ENoLL council. A new WG leader has been appointed, Prof Nicola Marsden from Heilbronn university,

KER7 has not achieved the level of impact anticipated and remains work in progress. A gender evaluation scheme is available from the University of Toronto (as detailed in Sections 3, 4 and Annex 3). This was used to evaluate the impact of working on the project on partners levels of gender competence. It was found to be comprehensive, useful, and applicable. The initial plan was to adapt this so that it could relate specifically to LLs. However, despite the establishment of an ENoLL working group on gender and innovation, gender does not appear to be a high-level priority within this community (as evidenced by the small membership of the WG, and levels of attendance at GILL events at OLLD conferences).

A sustainable evaluation scheme requires both a process, and an accredited monitor e.g., to assess resulting Gender Equality Plans [provide formative feedback and award digital badges. Several draft evaluation and monitoring processes were outlined to certify living labs or its members as being gender competent. To be sustainable after the project this process would need to be administered by ENoLL. At the time, it was not felt appropriate to either integrate questions within the existing certification and labelling process for LLs or run a parallel evaluation scheme. Instead, a gender competency workshop has been successfully piloted (Woodcock, 2025) using scenario-based learning GRSIE methods and Gender Action Planning. This will be rolled out as part of the WG Action Plan for 2026.

2.4 Specific impact areas

2.4.1 Impact against vertical pillars

A full description of all AOE has been provided in D3.2. In this deliverable we are more concerned with their engagement with stakeholders and the impact they have had. With regard to this, a full account of all AOE is provided in Annex 2 with a critical analysis and synthesis of this provided in Chapter 4.

The tables below outline the main outcomes/impact of the AOE which were associated with EU priority areas relating to health and resilience, the green transition and digital transformation.

Members of the consortium had a track record in transport, human factors, and sustainable mobility enabling three of the AOE to work in these areas with different QH agents. Direct impact on the industrial sector for AOE5 and AOE7 was difficult owing to external factors (e.g. personnel and transport operational changes, confidentiality). AOE5's work fits into national interest and existing funding on accessible transport, so there is a direct route to impact. Additionally, students and ECRs

are being targeted in the hopes of building an epistemic transport community which recognises the need to remove gender bias in data collection. AOE14 has translated their knowledge of intersectionality and mobility into a serious board game to create awareness of a number of gender related issues in the design of sustainable mobility. The game has been used at a number of external events and has been shown to be playable and informative for a number of stakeholders (e.g., children, citizens and local authorities).

Table 6. Overview of AOE's associated with the green transition

AOE	Goal	Main outcome/Impact	QH Engagement
AOE5: Addressing Gender Inclusion in Transport Research	Making transport research more inclusive	Set of recommendations, peer reviewed paper, presentation to the House of Lords (UK), lectures to engineers and set of best practices related to 'fixing the knowledge' and the 'fixing the culture'.	Public authorities, researchers, students, transport industry
AOE7: The use of gender disaggregated data to guide urban planning	Use of gender disaggregated data in transport planning	Workshops with transport companies. The creation and use of gender-disaggregated, data-based personas to communicate gendered evidence in mobility research. Quantitative results were presented as relatable, understandable stories that could be used by management to address commuting issues.	Local authorities, universities, transport companies
AOE14: Increasing understanding of intersectionality and transport in smart cities through gamification	Improve citizens' understanding of transport in smart cities	'Serious game' to increase the understanding of intersectionality and mobility in smart cities. Summer school to increase awareness of gender and intersectional in innovation and entrepreneurship.	Local authorities, universities, citizens, museums, transport planners

AOE3 started by interrogating and auditing its own practices as an organisation which supports health tech innovation, discovering, surprisingly, that there was a pattern of gender bias. Using GRSIE tools and methods they have changed a number of their own processes and set up a regional network in response to a discovered need to better support women health tech entrepreneurs, with the ambition of applying for national funding. AOE12 held a series of workshops with entrepreneurs, authorities, non-profit sector, and academia that encouraged participants to consider the pros and cons of different resilience policies and their potential impact on population groups under a situation of crisis. The iterative sessions provided a platform for feedback on the communication and design of new government policies and were complemented with training sessions and materials that increased key actors' awareness of existing policies and challenges for entrepreneurs in general, and women in particular.

Table 7. Overview of AOE's associated with health and resilience

AOE	Goal	Main outcome/Impact	QH Engagement
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AOE3: Increasing GRSIE in new medical devices, healthcare tech and tech-dependent intervention	To raise awareness of gender health inequalities, change practice and increase gender responsive health related innovations and entrepreneurship.	D4D organisational change. Redesign of Fellowship Programme to balance previously inclusion and challenge implicit biases. Creation of a dedicated Women's Health Theme to D4D's project portfolio has increased the number of female-led projects seeking support.	D4D team, investors, health innovators
AOE12: Reducing gender inequalities to entrepreneurs during pandemics and crises	To create tools/approaches to eliminate gender inequalities in business in times of crisis (e.g. economic or pandemic) and help women entrepreneurs to face the risks.	Workshops, training sessions and training materials. Policy recommendations.	Public authorities, academia, non-profit sector, businesses.

Four AOE's worked on areas related to the digital transition. AOE6 and AOE9 developed new tools and methods to gather and analyse data. AOE6 looked at the use of sentiment analysis on social media posts relating to gender equality. AOE9 dealt with the perennial problem of encouraging citizens (with a wider range of intersectional characteristics) to participate in on-line surveys.

AOE's 10 and 13 addressed the fourth fix relating to creating fairer and more equitable workplaces in the AI/IT sector, either through a capacity building program or the use/development of GRSIE tools and methods to reduce gender bias. AOE10 structured a full capacity-building programme in two carefully designed iterations. The first part focused on awareness-raising, introducing participants to gender-responsive AI concepts and the broader implications of bias in data, algorithms, and workplace practices. The second part moved into hands-on, practical training, using modular case studies and interactive exercises, such as gender impact assessments, to help participants apply these methods directly to AI tools and entrepreneurial contexts. AOE13 implemented **GILL** methods such as "hear the right voices" and "inclusive communication", alongside practical tools like round robin and fair meetings in a tech company. This led to the creation of women's networks within the company and later in the wider local IT community, providing spaces for support and visibility while also highlighting everyday practices that perpetuate inequality. The second iteration focused on co-creating a new method, "evoke change talk", which is now spreading across teams and departments of the tech company where it is piloted, supported by management approval and employee initiative.

Table 8. Overview of AOE's associated with the digital transition

AOE	Goal	Main outcome/Impact	QH Engagement
AOE6: Measuring citizen's perceptions of gender equality measures	To apply NLP to analyse the perception of citizens as expressed on social networks to different gender equality measures.	Interactive dashboard of citizens' perceptions of gender equality. Methodological innovation: combination of explainable AI with participatory Living Lab practices, replicable in other social contexts.	Citizens, universities,

AOE9: Co-creation of polling platform to support crowdsourcing for GRSIE	Creating a multilingual, crowdsourced polling tool.	Dynamic Survey Management System providing a multilingual, crowdsourced polling platform to dynamically adapt surveys to responder profiles and incentivize wider participation through digital rewards	Citizens, LL, policy makers, industry
AOE10: Reducing gender inequalities in AI /IT workplace and entrepreneurship	To reduce gender inequality in AI workplace.	Capacity building program to enhance the knowledge, skills, and digital literacy of women and other stakeholders active in AI/digital entrepreneurship.	Researchers, students, regional policy makers, NGOs, women entrepreneurs, educators.
AOE13: Retaining women in tech companies by changing workplace culture	Change tech companies team practices, design methods and tools to retain women in the innovation cycle and to develop gender-responsive innovations.	Work culture changes in tech companies, incorporation of GRSIE methods, establishment of a local, company-independent women's network for women in IT/tech. Co-creation of a new method for teams: Evoke Change Talk.	Tech companies, university

The remaining AOE's' activities, as shown in Table 9, were not restricted to one vertical priority. AOE1 has developed an AI supported process through which a design idea/problem from a citizen can be transformed by AI into an actionable design brief, which can form the basis for a provocative design visualisation – which can be used to stimulate further discussion of the original problem or the design itself. The template has been tested for both health and transport related ideas. AOE4, also supports citizen led RI&E through an extension of CU's successful citizen science training course to incorporate gender sensitive research and GRSIE tools and methods. Although initially classified as a green transition/circular, resources were not available to support this, leading to a focus on migrant women's entrepreneurship and research related to social determinants of public health research (such as barriers in access to green spaces and medical services).

Staying with entrepreneurship, AOE2 identified a need to support female academics at the early stages of the process, especially those from minority backgrounds, and those who were seeking to set up businesses in area not related to their current discipline. To support these women, a local network was formed with regular salon style meetings, held away from the university, with inspirational local role models and advice. AOE8 worked on strengthening the capacity of start-ups and innovation hubs in Italy to incorporate gender perspectives into their business models. Through the pilot use of **GILL** outputs within local innovation ecosystems, FGB collaborated with around 30 start-ups to apply gender-analysis frameworks and participatory methods to support the integration of gender into their design, management, and strategic planning.

Both AOE 11 and 15 dealt with organisational changes; AOE11 in a LA, and AOE15 in their own organisation, the Experimentarium. In the latter case the original idea was simply to make science exhibits more inclusive. The holistic approach taken to this resulted in organisational changes and empowerment of all members of the workforce to make the science museum more welcoming and

inclusive⁷ A set of guidelines was also developed for the exhibits. All aspects of the work are transferable across the sector.

Table 9. Overview of AOE's not associated with a vertical theme

AOE	Goal	Main outcome/Impact	QH Engagement
AOE1: Open innovation Platform	To improve citizen led design and innovation	Design brief generator working prototype	Students, citizens, designers
AOE4: Increasing capacity of excluded groups to inform policy	To improve and empower citizen led research	Citizen social science course; business start-ups; social determinants of public health research presented to LA. Further courses requested	Citizens, LA, Public health officers
AOE2: Supporting Women in Academia in Their Spinout/Business Journey	To understand and fill the gaps in support for female academics	Identification of a gap in support and understanding of minority women's entrepreneurship; leading to participatory workshops, support network, and salon web	TTO, women, citizens, female academics
AOE8: Increasing capacity of start-ups to address gender related issues	To introduce the concept of gender innovation into their incubation programmes and training on how to apply it in practice to overcome the bottleneck between being interested/knowing how to do it.	Organisational change, introducing gender innovation model in startup pathways, comprehensive assessment of their own materials and participants in their innovation centres. This involved analysing and creating participation data, ownership structures, and gender representation.	Starts up, SMEs
AOE11: Deploying GILL methodology in a local authority	To highlight and then reduce gender inequalities in LAs	Changes in internal regulations and organisational charts to eliminate gender-based discrimination in hiring, promotions, and task assignments. Practical awareness and skills in applying gender equality principles, support of Gender Innovation events training for start-ups.	Local authority
AOE15: Applying GRSIE to the design of museum exhibits for more inclusive engagement and	Increase gender mainstreaming in design of science centre/museum exhibitions.	The application GRSIE methods on the science centre's daily work. The development of an institutional committee dedicated to support diversity and inclusion in all their projects. New and existing exhibits	Organisation, citizens,

⁷ Woodcock et al presented the work on organisational changes in D4D and the Experimentalism at ICGR 2025.

<p>highlighting of gender inequalities</p>		<p>developed with inclusive content, language, and design. Accessibility has been addressed in practice and been given a more prominent space on the website and communication. Stronger focus on whose stories are told, what types of scientific contributions are celebrated, and how visitors are invited to engage.</p>	
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2.4.2 2.4.2 Impact against horizontal spheres of innovation

The development of tools and methods to address the horizontal theme-related issues was central to the work of GILL and its potential impact. The development of tools and methods which addressed 4 spheres of innovation drew on the work of Marsden, Raudonat and Pröbster (2025). The framework conceptualises gender bias in RI&E as a systemic and circular process as shown in Figure 8 in which

- Structural inequalities shape participation in RI&E, influencing team practices and the design tools and methods employed.
- These processes result in non-inclusive innovation outcome, which in turn reinforce existing societal norms and inequalities.
- The model highlights **multiple entry points for intervention**, rather than a single linear cause., recognising the wicked problem of gender inequality in RI&E

Figure 8. Loops of discrimination in RI&E

These horizontal issues may influence each phase of the innovation cycle as well as the overall operation of the LL. A gender evaluation scheme for certification (as specified in KER7) could be used to highlight and reduce biases in LLs and provide information for the development of GEPs. Although there was no appetite for an additional certification process for LLs, a successful gender certification workshop was held at OLLD2025 (Woodcock, 2025) built around scenario-based learning (in which LLs had to ‘solve’ typical gender related problems (e.g. gender bias in leadership, roles and user centred design) in the operation of LLs, using GRSIE tools and methods. This was followed by an introduction to inclusive Gender Action Planning to address an urgent issue in their LL. Approximately 15 LLs took part, with requests for further details on how to run the workshop with other groups such as transport companies.

Over 45 searchable GRSIE tools and methods were collated, thematically grouped, and presented in the **GILL** hub accompanied by extensive notes on their usage and value. Their value and impact lie in:

- empowering individual team members to make a change and challenge /talk about practices
- their effectiveness as practical, stand-alone tools to address from the ground, issues of inclusion and gender equality,
- their usefulness in helping to operationalise GEPs

The AOE's not only validated the usefulness of the of tools and methods over 2 iterative lifecycles as explained in D3.2 but also used them to create changes within their organisations and centres (as shown in Table 10) and further described in Section 4.2 and Annex 2. This meant that **GILL** had an immediate impact at micro- and meso-levels of the RI&E ecosystem, through raising awareness, providing targeted support, changing mindsets, individual, work group and organisational cultures.

Table 10. Mapping of the work of the AOE's onto the horizontal themes

AOE	Horizontal theme
AOE1: Open Innovation Platform for Gender Responsive Collaborative Innovation	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods H3: Innovation and products
AOE2: Brick by Brick: Supporting Women in Academia in Their Spinout/Business Journey	H1: Individual and team practices H4: Societal process
AO3: Increasing GRSIE in new medical devices, healthcare tech and tech-dependent intervention	All
AOE4: Increasing capacity of excluded groups to act as GRSIE in their local community	All
AOE5: Addressing Gender Inclusion in Transport Research	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods H3: Innovation and products
AOE6: Measuring citizen's perceptions of gender equality measures	H3: Innovation and products H4: Societal process
AOE7: The use of gender disaggregated data to guide urban planning	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods
AOE8: Increasing capacity of start-ups to address gender related issues	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods
AOE9: Co-creation of polling platform to support crowdsourcing for GRSIE	H2: Tools and methods H3: innovation and products

AOE10: Reducing gender inequalities in AI /IT workplace and entrepreneurship	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods H3: Innovation and products H4: Societal process
AOE11: Deploying GILL methodology in a local authority	All
AOE12: Reducing gender inequalities to entrepreneurs during pandemics and crises	H2: Tools and methods H4: Societal process
AOE13: Retaining women in tech companies by changing workplace culture	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods
AOE14: Increasing understanding of intersectionality and transport in smart cities through gamification	H2: Tools and methods H3: Innovation and products
AOE15: Applying GRSIE to the design of science centre/museum exhibits for more inclusive engagement and highlighting of gender inequalities	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods H3: Innovation and products

2.4.3 Destination impacts

Table 11. Examples of contributions to Impact 1

Impact 1: An enhanced, more open, and inclusive research and innovation system			
Type: Scientific, economic, societal	Techno-	Pathway: 1b, 2a, 2b	KERs: 2, 3, 4, 5, 6
Objectives: A, B, C, D		Target groups: Education & Research, Business, Public sector	
Destination impacts		Overview and/or examples of <i>GILL</i>'s contributions	
[1] Reform and Enhance the EU R&I system,		<p>GILL's roadmap, the cultural fix and tools and methods offer practical and, in some cases, immediate ways in which gender equality and inclusive working practices can be developed in R&I.</p> <p>A series of far-reaching recommendations has been provided in a range of different outputs, in D4.5 and this deliverable which are targeted especially at the EU R&I system,</p>	
[5] Deepen the ERA,			
[12] Inclusive gender equality is promoted in the European R&I system,			
[8] Synergies between research & innovation and higher education policies and programmes,		<p>AOE3, AOE10 and AOE14 and 15 collaboration have introduced GILL recommendations and methods into master's courses, summer schools and specialised training on Human-Centred AI, and a fellowship programme for qualified Healthcare Scientists working within the NHS in England and Wales, while AOE2 introduced entrepreneurial mentoring for women in academia. AOE8 established compulsory training on gender innovation as part of start-up capacity building in their innovation centres. AOE11 and AOE12 have extended this reach into local authorities, IT clusters and wider entrepreneurial ecosystems, training LA, startups, and entrepreneurs on new policies and practices. Through workshops, fellowships and collaborative networks, the project has delivered targeted transformations that modernise higher education and strengthen synergies with innovation ecosystems, ensuring that inclusion and equality are embedded as drivers of institutional and technological change.</p>	
[9] Modernised higher education sector, benefitting from targeted transformations in higher education, research, and innovation.			

<p>[13] A more open and inclusive R&I system,</p>	<p>Development of GILL hub and content modules as resources for innovators and entrepreneurs, recommendations to make the work in EU projects more inclusive, open availability of GILL methods, tools and guidelines to apply them in different contexts (research, industry, LA, charities, etc).</p> <p>Collaboration with TTO and synergies between projects to extend the impact of GILL, changing the culture of how gender should be disseminated and communicated that will lead to strengthening innovation and inclusiveness</p> <p>A more inclusive and gender sensitive R&I ecosystem for LLS.</p> <p>Increasing gender sensitivity among the 'quadruple helix' actors working in the field of supporting women's entrepreneurship.</p>
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Table 12. Example of contributions to Impact 2

Impact 2: A stronger alignment of strategic R&I with society needs, expectations, and values.		
Type: Scientific, Techno-economic	Pathway: all	KERs: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
Objectives: A	Target groups: All	
Destination impacts	Overview and/or examples of GILL's contributions	
[15] Increased engagement of citizens with research and innovation	<p>Several AOE's have addressed these issues at local level, developing new tools, processes or educational courses to increase engagement and trust. For example, AOE1 has developed a template to bridge the gaps between a member of public expressing a problem -> generation a design brief -> visualisation of a 'provocative concept design to elicit further engagement; AOE4 has developed a social science citizen training course to empower citizens to conduct research on real world problems and present this to LAs; AOE9 has developed platform to support incentivised surveys to encourage citizens to participate in research; AOE15 has implemented organisational changes to change thinking about the design of more inclusive science exhibitions; AOE14 has used gamification to increase engagement of citizens and LAs with sustainable mobility</p>	
[4] Greater quality of the scientific production and stronger translation of R&I results into the economy,		
[18] Increased trust in science and R&I outcomes, and greater two-way communication between science and society,		

Table 13. Example of contributions to Impact 3

Impact 3 Knowledge and collaboration		
Type: Scientific, Techno-economic	Pathway: 1a, 2b	KERs: 1, 2, 4, 6
Objectives Addressed: A, SO3 (connect and collaborate)	Target groups: All	
Destination impacts	Overview and/or examples of GILL's contributions	
[3] Improved access to excellence	<p>Resources available through the GILL platform, including opportunities to meet with mentors and key researchers. Additionally, GILL outputs have been presented in a wide number of formats, and places to increase knowledge sharing: open access publications, international conferences, website, videos, games, recommendations, guidelines, etc.</p>	

[4] Greater quality of scientific production and stronger translation of R&I results into the economy	AOEs have been working with local QH agents such as industries, SMEs and Local Authorities to translate GILL 's R&I results, tools and methods into practical outputs that can bring economic benefit
[7] Improved knowledge for policy making about the networking patterns of research support staff and research management,	AOE2's work on female academic spin-outs revealed a lack of sex-disaggregated and discipline-specific data on enquiries to technology transfer offices (TTOs), the nature of business ideas, and progression rates. This data gap persists even in institutions that report entrepreneurship success metrics, limiting transparency and evidence-based policy development.
[8] Synergies between research & innovation and higher education policies and programmes	As a R&I project, GILL has been able to identify areas of weakness in HEI policies relating to gender inequality, which continue to suppress women's voices and wider contributions. We have developed recommendations and tools and methods which are HEI 'friendly' as well as a proven bottom-up organisational change process which could be supported by gender competency workshops and the development of inclusive GAPS ⁸ at different levels of granularity.
[10] Increased number of interconnected knowledge ecosystems, strong in knowledge creation, circulation, and use	GILL has connected to 29 ecosystems thereby strengthening and consolidating work in this area and opening up opportunities for new collaboration and knowledge sharing,

2.4.4 GILL's contribution to global goals

The tools and methods developed in **GILL**, and its highlighting of the need to address the fourth 'cultural fix' provide opportunities to address the inequalities outlined in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs) 2025 report. **GILL** could have an impact in areas of gender equality (SDG5) in terms of methods linked to empowerment, networking and mentorship, quality education (SDG4) for women at tertiary level through Capacity Building, and the work on vertical themes supports support the use of GRSIE in disciplines linked to several SDGs (e.g., SDG 3, 9, 13).

However, it is presumptuous and unethical to assert that resources developed in an EU context are transferrable to LMICs.

During the project we have drawn attention to issues related to western models of the entrepreneurship and the additional barriers faced by women and entrepreneurs with different ethnicities due to stereotypes of what a successful entrepreneur should look like and what constitutes a 'successful and investment-worthy business. The dominant image of the entrepreneur is built on masculinist ideals—risk-taking, competitiveness, autonomy, and rationality (Christensen et al., 2026). These traits are celebrated as universal, while qualities often associated with women, such as collaboration, passion, and emotion, are undervalued. Yet these very qualities are essential for innovation (see Balkmar and Mellstom (2026) on tech masculinities; Woodcock and Hault (2025) on older female entrepreneurs). This imbalance creates a fictive ideal that women are expected to emulate, even though it doesn't reflect the reality of most entrepreneurs.

Tanti (2026) has argued that looking beyond gender, race and colonial legacies play a critical role. Indigenous and Black women face unique barriers, from discriminatory investor practices to

⁸ Th term 'inclusive GAPS' is used in preference to GADAPs, and acronym for 'gender and diversity action plans'

definitions of entrepreneurship that exclude self-employment and micro-enterprises. These exclusions perpetuate systemic inequities and erase cultural approaches to business.

Entrepreneurship culture also reflects characteristics of white supremacy—objectivity, perfectionism, urgency, and competitiveness. These norms maintain power structures and marginalise alternative ways of doing business. Similarly, popular narratives like the “girlboss” myth promote an image of elite, white, heteronormative femininity as the entrepreneurial ideal, ignoring racial privilege and structural barriers.

Decolonising entrepreneurship means embracing frameworks like Two-Eyed Seeing (Bartlett et al., 2012), which integrate Western and Indigenous knowledge systems. For many Indigenous women, success is measured not by profit or growth but by community well-being, cultural resurgence, and reciprocity. Programs must respect these values and avoid imposing Western norms.

Cultural specificity matters. One-size-fits-all models fail because they ignore local histories and socio-economic realities. For example, Black women’s reluctance to dilute ownership or take on debt reflects intergenerational experiences of scarcity and discrimination. Supporting diverse entrepreneurs requires understanding these contexts.

Policy recommendations include expanding definitions of entrepreneurship to include micro-enterprises, creative work, and social ventures; adopting justice-oriented practices like racial equity investing and catalytic capital; and challenging discriminatory investor models. But funding alone is not enough—real change requires dismantling structural inequities and listening to nondominant voices.

Ultimately, women’s entrepreneurship is not just an economic activity—it is a sociopolitical construct shaped by power and privilege. Achieving transformation means moving beyond empowerment rhetoric toward emancipation, centring gender justice, and reframing entrepreneurship through feminist, antiracist, and decolonizing lenses.

Hacsek, Woodcock and Sears (2025) uncovered the ambitions and barriers faced by female academics and staff from minority groups in a UK university. Their challenges related to imposter syndrome, discrimination familial, cultural pressures around the role of women, and even their rights to the ownership of their business. Notably, the women we spoke to did not wish to develop businesses out of their university work but start businesses which would fulfil their needs and potential. They were standing at a crossroads, felt unsupported by university systems, and questioned their choices e.g., risking a seemingly successful and lucrative career to follow their needs. This was surprising because ‘the chains that tie these women’ did not evaporate when they migrated, but many found the inner strength to overcome and share their challenges. Creating safe spaces and networks, with understanding mentors/local role models who have relevant backgrounds, is essential in supporting the first steps towards entrepreneurial activities.

GILL outputs and activities need to be tailored to the needs of women in LMICs, and a concerted effort must be made post-project to derive additional benefits from the project in both EU and LMICs. One of the mechanisms by which this could be achieved is through ENOLL, with over 170 members across 40+ countries – 20% of whom are based outside the EU, including, India, Kenya, Tunisia. As ‘the world’s largest network of living labs’⁹, it is regularly invited to international conferences, congresses and conventions. At each of these a clear message could be included regarding gender equality; the WG in Gender and Innovation could co-design/tailor a gender competence workshops based on the existing plan (Woodcock, 2025) in LLs in LMICs as part of its working plan, so that these LLs led by

⁹ enoll.org

example, and became a safe space for women entrepreneurs; invitations should be sent out for LLs in LMICs to join the **GILL** network and efforts should be made to diversify the pool of mentors (see also Chapter 6).

2.4.5 Impact against the six key dimensions from SheFigures 2024

The following table shows the parts of the project which can contribute to advancing the dimensions of gender inequality raised in the latest She figures report.

Table 14. Summary of contributions of the project to different aspects of gender inequality

Dimensions of gender inequalities	GILL outputs and activities					
	AOE	GRSIE tools and methods	Mentorship, training and CPD	GILL hub	Networking	Policy and publications
<i>pipeline segregation</i>		x	x	x		
<i>research sectors</i>	x	x		x	x	x
<i>career progression</i>		x	x	x	x	x
<i>decision-making</i>		x		x		
<i>research participation</i>	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>incorporation of a gender dimension in research and innovation output</i>	x	x		x		x

The evidence for these claims is included in Chapter 4.

3 Methods

A pragmatic, mixed methods approach was used to gather evidence for impact during the lifetime of the project, at critical stages (e.g., for the interim report and completion of deliverables and milestones) and for both partners and AOE. This was conducted in close co-operation with WP3 and other WP4 tasks.

- Qualitative data was gathered from workshops (on-line and face to face), interviews with AOE, and research journals, bespoke questionnaires.
- Quantitative data was collected from bespoke questionnaires (e.g. on the usage and impact of **GILL** tools and methods, the extent to which the AOE operated effectively as LL and engaged with stakeholders (as reported in D3.2), and the impact of dissemination and communication activities (as reported in D4.3)). A pre-existing gender competency tool was used to measure the impact of working on the project on individual members.

This deliverable principally draws on data derived from the following methods. A brief explanation of the method used is included along with the results. Where appropriate data/ templates are added in as Annexes. The studies were undertaken by Coventry University. Overall ethical approval was obtained to cover the project. Internal 'evaluation' type studies, conducted with partners as part of their everyday activities did not require further ethical approval.

Table 15. Overview of methods used to collect data from partners

Impact type	Methods	With whom	When	Purpose
Macro project objectives	Bespoke questionnaires & interviews	AOEs	After each iterative cycle	To understand impact of AOE in their local ecosystem
Individual levels knowledge and practice in GRSIE	Gender competency checklist	Partners	Towards the start and end of the project	To understand gains in knowledge and potential for knowledge transfer within team members
	Reflective journals	Partners	Continual	To understand gender in relation to team dynamics and management
Impact 1: An enhanced, more open & inclusive R&I system: Impact 2 Stronger alignment of strategic R&I with society needs, expectations and values: Impact 3 Knowledge and collaboration	Workshops	Partners	At 18 and 36 months	To understand efforts undertaken or planned to achieve different impact types

3.1.1 Reflections on embedding impact analysis across the lifetime of the project

The attempt to embed impact, evaluation and reflection throughout the project has not been without its challenges. A pragmatic mixed methods approach was adopted in order to collect the right information at the right time and encourage participation of partners who may be less familiar with qualitative methods. The need to actively engage in this activity has been reinforced by repeat emails, in on-line meetings, 1-1 sessions and in project workshops.

Nevertheless, this has been regarded as a somewhat peripheral activity especially:

- given the number of contributions by partners and more traditional view of evaluation and impact, but **GILL** has been designed with this integration in mind, and the need to iteratively develop outputs based on evaluation
- previous experiences of evaluation
- the need for consideration and co-design of KPIs which can be used to measure the impact of activities against wider project objectives,

4 Evidence

4.1 Impact assessment across the project

A face-to-face workshop entitled ‘making gender equality sticky’ was held in the final project meeting. This built on previous on-line meetings, webinar on impact, and 2 previous project workshops in Thessaloniki and Prague. The aim of the workshop was to consolidate knowledge and activities at a project level, to complement the reporting of impact at AOE level (described in the Section 4.2). To prepare for the meeting all partners were sent an explanation of the workshop, and draft workbooks. Those unable to attend the meeting were given the opportunity to participate in an online workshop or complete worksheets (shown in Annex 4) individually (they all chose the latter).

The intention was to gather information on the steps the project had taken to create impact from its activities and outputs. Participants were divided into 6 groups – with each table led by a member of the Coventry team. Where possible each team worked on either Impact 1: An enhanced, more open & inclusive R&I system: Impact 2 Stronger alignment of strategic R&I with society needs, expectations and values: Impact 3 Knowledge and collaboration, and considered either what they had done during the project to achieve impact, or what their future actions would be.

The workshop was based around two key ideas in impact. Firstly, Spaapen and Van Drooge (2011) notion of a productive interactions or events as exchanges between researchers and stakeholders in which

- Knowledge is produced and valued that is both scientifically robust and socially relevant.
- Mediated through various ‘tracks’, for instance, a research publication, an exhibition, a design, people or financial support.
- An interaction is productive when it leads to efforts by stakeholders to somehow use or apply research results or practical information or experiences.
- Social impacts of knowledge are behavioural changes that happen because of this knowledge’
- They can take many forms; Direct (personal); indirect (mediated through artefacts) or financial (mediated through exchange relations)

Using this helped team members reflect on key activities, what they hoped to achieve, what their stakeholders were like (e.g. knowledgeable, receptive) the activities they had or could undertake before or after the event to ensure it had maximum impact, system characteristics (in terms of capacity for change) and factors which could have influenced the impact of the activity (e.g. timing, status, compatibility with personal and business goals).

Secondly, participants were asked to select which of 12+1 archetypal pathways (Muhonen et al., 2020) to social impact they used or would consider most appropriate for the impact they wanted to achieve. The archetypal pathways were developed to capture the diversity of mechanisms through which social science and humanities research can lead to societal impact. They are the classical pipeline; 1) interactive dissemination, 2) collaboration; 3) public engagement, 4) expertise, 5) mobility pathway, 6) Anticipating anniversaries, 7) Seize the day, 8) social innovation, 9) commercialisation, 10) research engagement, 11) knowledge creeps into society, and 12) building ‘new epistemic’ communities.

Together these provide a useful way of capturing the missing information in Figures 2 and 3, in which pathways are mentioned, but details are missing.

4.1.1 Results from the impact analysis

The results are based on 50 responses from project members. As not all members contributed, but the results are indicative of the work conducted by partners to achieve impact. Those contributing to the workshop found the approach novel and beneficial.

Archetypal pathways most used and perceived to be most impactful across the project

Table 16. Overview of the use of archetypal pathways in GILL

1. An enhanced, more open, and inclusive research and innovation system	
DURING GILL	POST GILL INTENTIONS
Collaboration pathway (5) Expertise Pathway (2) Also mentioned: classical pipeline, interactive dissemination, public engagement, 'seize the day', social innovation, 'research engagement as key to impact' pathways	Interactive dissemination (2) Also mentioned: Collaboration, mobility and social innovation pathway
Pathway considered to have the most potential for impact: Collaboration Pathway and possibly building new epistemic communities	
2. A stronger alignment of strategic R&I with society needs, expectations, and values	
DURING GILL	POST GILL INTENTIONS
Public engagement pathway	Social innovation pathway (2) Also mentioned: classical pipeline, interactive dissemination, 'anticipating anniversaries and new epistemic communities' pathways
Pathway considered to have the most potential for impact: Social innovation pathway	
3. Stronger knowledge sharing and collaboration	
DURING GILL	POST GILL INTENTIONS
Public engagement pathway (4), Social innovation pathway (3) Collaboration pathway (2) Interactive dissemination (2) Also mentioned: expertise, 'research engagement as key to impact' and the building 'new epistemic communities' pathways.	Classical pipeline (2) Collaboration pathway (2) Knowledge creeps into society (2) Also mentioned: Social innovation and new epistemic communities' pathways
Pathway considered to have the most potential for impact: Public engagement pathway	

4.2 AOE's Impact

The AOE's at the centre of the project have delivered tangible impact across the macro-objectives defined in **GILL**. This section presents a consolidated summary of AOE's outcomes and impact across the different themes of the project, and the pathways to impact that AOE's have followed. Annex 2 contains a full impact table of each of the AOE's, including detailed impact narratives with their original challenges and goals, as well as the key objectives they address, the beneficiaries from their activities, their next steps to consolidate their impact after the end of the **GILL** project, the barriers and enablers to impact they have encountered and the concrete actions they took to overcome them. Figure 9 shows an overview of the AOE's and their location. The work of each AOE is summarised briefly in the following paragraphs.

Figure 9. AOE Map

4.2.1 Description of AOE's

AOE1 – Open Innovation Platform for Gender Responsive Collaboration

The Design Brief Generator (DBG) is a semi-automated, form-based narrative tool that enables users with limited experience of writing design briefs to quickly articulate inclusive, well-structured design challenges. By offering selectable options rather than technical specifications, the DBG supports sense-making, lowers barriers to participation, and allows a coherent story to emerge from complex needs. Developed and tested across health and transport themes, the early prototype DBG has already generated design briefs and provocative visualisations shared on the TinnGO Open Innovation Platform (OIP), efficiently building on existing investment to enable open discussion, development, and the launch of design challenges in a single space. During the project, technical constraints and

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differing interpretations of the interaction method have restricted further development. **Next steps** include improving the user interface and the DBG, extending testing to a wider user base, and developing the DBG–OIP workflow as a sustainable, open-ended mechanism for democratically generating and advancing inclusive design solutions.

AOE2 – Supporting pre-start female academic entrepreneurs

AOE2 addressed gendered barriers faced by pre-start female academic entrepreneurs whose entrepreneurial aspirations fall outside conventional spinout and commercialisation pathways. The AOE identified the needs of women academics in the West Midlands interested in entrepreneurship and translated these into a local network and *Salon Series*: which focused on confidence-building, mentoring, skills development, and access to relatable local role models. Eight sessions were held, engaging over 50 participants and creating a trusted, confidential space in which women could explore entrepreneurship, address discrimination and imposter syndrome, and develop practical capabilities through peer exchange and mentoring. The AOE demonstrated the need and value of a local network which could strengthen entrepreneurial identity and agency and make otherwise invisible pathways into entrepreneurship more accessible. **Next steps** include linking the network to local support services, deepening the focus on concrete business development activities, integrating it with the GILL ecosystem, and further addressing systemic constraints such as time poverty and institutional precarity that disproportionately affect women academics' entrepreneurial trajectories.

AOE3 – Transforming gender equity in the UK health technology innovation ecosystem

AOE3 tackled persistent gender inequalities in the UK health technology innovation ecosystem. A retrospective analysis of five years of collaboration requests provided clear evidence base and need for improved diversity tracking. As a result D4D embedded gender-responsive practices into its core processes, piloting and institutionalising tools such as Fair Meetings, Airtime Monitoring, and Gender Impact Assessment to address bias in its decision-making, collaboration, and project evaluation. In parallel, the Women's Health Innovation Network was established to create visibility, connection, and legitimacy for female-led innovation across research, entrepreneurship, and investment. **Next steps** include integrating gender and diversity indicators into project management systems for real-time monitoring, expanding the Women's Health Innovation Network nationally through partnerships with HealthTech centres and industry, and sharing GILL-informed tools, case studies, and evaluation methods across UK health innovation networks to sustain and scale cultural change.

AOE4 – Amplifying marginalised women's voices through citizen-led innovation and research

AOE4 addressed gender inequality at city level RI&E beginning with migrant women and expanding into wider local communities, e.g., in the first iterative cycle migrant women entrepreneurs were equipped with entrepreneurial skills, access to maker resources, and visibility within the Coventry business ecosystem, enabling greater economic participation and social integration, leading to the launch of new micro businesses. The second cycle scaled this participatory logic through a gender sensitive Citizen Social Science course, training local people to identify, articulate, and translate their lived challenges into research questions and policy-relevant knowledge. The key impact lies in the development of a transferable methodology, i.e., the new course informed by GRSIE methods, that enables councils and public authorities to hear and act on community-defined priorities, rather than consulting with predefined agendas and builds up local capacity. This approach has influenced public health and council discussions, supported participants' professional progression, and demonstrated

the value of citizen-led knowledge for inclusive decision-making. **Next steps** include expanding the methodology to other councils and age groups, continuing delivery of the citizen social scientist course, and sustaining the approach through partnerships and alternative resources in response to funding withdrawal, ensuring that marginalised women’s voices remain structurally embedded in innovation and policy processes.

AOE5 – Embedding gender inclusion in transport research and policy

AOE5 tackled structural gender bias in transport research. Using GILL methods, the AOE engaged transport researchers to surface systemic barriers embedded in research design, recruitment, and leadership practices, leading to concrete changes within Coventry University’s National Transport Design Centre (NTDC), including extended timelines and improved strategies for engaging under-represented groups. The impact of this work extends beyond local practice: findings and recommendations have been published in a high-impact journal, presented at the House of Lords, and embedded in postgraduate teaching, directly shaping future generations of transport researchers. By reframing gender imbalance as a structural research issue rather than an individual recruitment problem, the AOE has influenced both policy and academic culture. **Next steps** include extending the methodology to intersectional dimensions of inequality, developing open-access toolkits and training for universities and Living Labs, strengthening mentoring and leadership pathways for women and gender-diverse researchers, and continuing engagement with European policy forums to embed gender equality metrics in future transport and mobility funding programmes.

AOE6 – Measuring citizens’ perceptions of gender equality measures through AI and participation

AOE6 addressed a critical gap in gender equality policy and innovation: the lack of scalable, timely, and cost-effective methods to assess how citizens perceive gender equality measures. By combining AI techniques with participatory Living Lab approaches, the AOE developed an innovative methodology using natural language processing and sentiment analysis to analyse public discourse on social media platforms. The resulting interactive dashboard enables real-time exploration of citizens’ perceptions, emotional responses, and discursive patterns, supporting evidence-based decision-making for policymakers, researchers, and organisations. This approach significantly reduces costs compared to traditional surveys, increases representativeness, and democratises access to citizen opinion, while remaining grounded in ethical and trustworthy AI principles. The methodology has been published and presented across academic and professional forums, demonstrating its transferability beyond gender to other social policy domains. **Next steps** include addressing long-term stakeholder engagement, strengthening governance around ethical and privacy concerns, and scaling the methodology across additional policy areas and European contexts to support more responsive and inclusive innovation systems.

AOE7 – Using gender-disaggregated mobility data to inform inclusive policy and innovation

AOE7 addressed the persistent gender bias in mobility planning by demonstrating the value of gender-disaggregated data for research, policy, and entrepreneurial decision-making in the transport sector. Through quantitative analysis of survey data, the AOE uncovered systematic gender differences in travel purpose, time use, transport mode, and perceptions of safety, revealing how unequal mobility patterns reflect broader social and economic inequalities. To make this evidence actionable and communicable, the findings were translated into data-based personas—narrative profiles that transformed statistical results into accessible stories capable of resonating with researchers,

companies, and policymakers. This approach introduced an innovative method for communicating gendered evidence beyond tables and charts, supporting greater awareness of how gender-sensitive data can inform more inclusive mobility services, policies, and business models. **Next steps** include replicating the methodology across additional companies and non-corporate contexts, expanding intersectional analysis, and further developing personas as a transferable tool for awareness-raising and gender-responsive transport policy design.

AOE8 – Building startup and innovation hub capacity for gender innovation

AOE8 tackled the low uptake of gender perspectives in startup and innovation ecosystems by embedding gender innovation directly into incubation pathways and organisational practice. Following an initial pilot that revealed limited awareness and engagement with gender related issues, the AOE shifted towards internal capacity-building within innovation hubs, analysing participation, ownership, and gender representation data and exposing persistent structural inequalities. These findings catalysed organisational change, prompting the development of gender-inclusive communication practices, practitioner guidelines, and targeted training—reframing gender innovation in terms of business performance, staff wellbeing, and talent retention. The impact includes cultural and organisational shifts, integration of gender perspectives into startup design processes, the creation of reusable training resources, and the establishment of a growing network of startups committed to gender innovation. **Next steps** focus on sustaining and expanding this network, moving from introductory training to advanced, hands-on support for startups, and further embedding the combined gender–business expert model across regional, national, and European innovation programmes.

AOE9 – Co-creating an inclusive polling platform for gender-responsive decision-making

AOE9 addressed structural barriers to inclusive evidence-gathering in research, policy, and innovation by developing a Dynamic Survey Management System (DSMS), a multilingual, GDPR-compliant polling platform designed to crowdsource gender-sensitive feedback from diverse and under-represented groups. Using GILL tools and gendered innovation principles, the system dynamically adapts surveys to responder profiles, employs AI-assisted translation, and incentivises participation to increase participation of hard-to-reach groups in surveys. **Next steps** focus on consolidating and scaling the platform through sustained funding, expanded partnerships, and business development, strengthening institutional uptake by public bodies, and continuing to refine governance, privacy, and engagement mechanisms to ensure long-term, trustworthy exploitation of gender-sensitive data infrastructures.

AOE10 – Reducing gender inequalities in AI/IT workplaces and digital entrepreneurship lifecycle

AOE10's activities spanned skills development, product design, and workplace participation, at a time when many practitioners remain unaware of gender-responsive AI methods despite emerging EU regulatory requirements. Through the capacity-building programme on Human-Centred AI and Data Science, the AOE equipped women and other stakeholders in AI/digital entrepreneurship with practical tools to identify and mitigate gender bias, conduct gender impact assessments, and embed intersectional considerations into AI-driven products and services. The programme delivered impact across professional development, by strengthening participants' career-relevant skills aligned with the EU AI Act; innovation processes, by supporting the integration of gender dimensions into digital products and services; and educational practice, by embedding GILL methods into AI and digital skills

training as spaces for inclusive reflection. **Next steps** include scaling the training through EIT Digital-funded entrepreneurship programmes (e.g. LOTUS), reusing and extending AOE10 materials across green and digital innovation contexts, and continuing to mainstream gender-responsive AI practices within European digital entrepreneurship ecosystems.

AOE11 – Deploying GILL methodology for organisational change in a local authority

AOE11 demonstrated how GILL methodologies can drive systemic organisational change within a local authority by operationalising gender mainstreaming commitments in everyday governance. Working with Alba Iulia City Hall, the AOE translated high-level strategies—such as the Equality Action Plan and Integrated Urban Development Strategy—into concrete practices, leading to updated internal regulations, revised organisational charts, and clearer procedures addressing gender discrimination, flexible working, and career progression. Civil servants gained practical skills to apply gender equality principles in their daily work, while women employees benefited from safer working environments, improved work–life balance, and enhanced transparency in advancement pathways. The municipality strengthened its institutional capacity, aligned more closely with European gender equality objectives, and expanded public engagement through policy dialogue and regional exchange. **Next steps** focus on formalising regulatory changes, continuing targeted training, conducting annual internal monitoring surveys, and embedding gender equality evaluation into routine governance to ensure the sustainability and transferability of impact beyond the project lifecycle.

AOE12 – Addressing gender inequalities among entrepreneurs during crises

AOE12 addressed the disproportionate impact of crises—such as pandemics and economic shocks—on women entrepreneurs by applying GRSIE methods to evaluate policy responses and co-design more gender-responsive approaches. Using participatory workshops grounded in gender-segregated data, the AOE enabled policymakers, practitioners, and researchers to critically examine how crisis measures are designed, communicated, and implemented, revealing how ostensibly neutral policies can perpetuate gender inequalities. The impact includes a measurable shift in participants’ thinking towards more gender-aware policy analysis, improved feedback loops between policymakers and stakeholders, increased professional awareness of gender-segregated data, and strengthened cross-sectoral relationships. **Next steps** include sustained monitoring of gendered impacts during crises, long-term sensitisation of decision-makers, embedding gender perspectives into policy roll-out processes, and following up on data utilisation to support durable behavioural and institutional change beyond short-term experimentation.

AOE13 – Retaining women in tech by transforming workplace culture

AOE13 addressed the persistent attrition of women from the tech sector by addressing workplace culture rather than focusing solely on recruitment. Through a Living Lab collaboration with industry, the AOE identified a gender gap in psychological safety and worked with employees, managers, and executives to co-design and embed gender-responsive practices. Impacts include the establishment of women’s networks within and beyond the company, the diffusion of GILL methods such as fair meetings and inclusive communication across departments, and the co-creation of a novel “evoke change talk” method that integrates gender reflection into routine team meetings. This approach enabled men to actively articulate commitments to gender equality, supporting allyship and cultural change without adding burdensome new processes. **Next steps** include continued diffusion of the method across teams and companies, strengthening stakeholder networks, and leveraging moments

of organisational readiness to sustain momentum towards inclusive innovation cultures that retain women across the full innovation cycle.

AOE14 – Advancing intersectional understanding of transport in smart cities through gamification

AOE14 addressed the disconnect between smart city discourse and citizens lived experiences by using gamification to communicate intersectional transport inequalities in accessible and engaging ways. Through the co-design of an educational board game based on transport and gender research, the AOE enabled citizens to reflect on mobility, inclusion, and policy trade-offs, achieving measurable short-term shifts in mindset and willingness to change practices. Long-term impact has been realised through the creation of a start-up that integrates the games into educational packages for municipalities, schools, universities, and NGOs, embedding gender-sensitive transport knowledge within entrepreneurial activity. **Next steps** include securing start-up capital, adapting the games for additional national and linguistic contexts, updating content to reflect diverse policy environments, and exploring digital extensions while preserving accessibility and inclusivity.

AOE15 – Applying GRSIE to the design of inclusive museum exhibitions

AOE15 addressed gender and inclusion gaps in science engagement by applying GRSIE principles to organisational culture change within a science centre, rather than focusing on isolated exhibit adaptations. Through professional development, reflective tools (e.g., SPARK, team manifestos, diaries), and co-creation workshops, the AOE built organisational awareness and agency, embedding inclusion as a shared responsibility across departments. This led to tangible changes in governance, including the establishment of an inclusion committee, new workflows integrating gender and diversity reflections, and systematic changes in exhibition design, storytelling, accessibility, and communication. Exhibits increasingly reflect diverse scientific contributions and invite broader public engagement, while staff benefit from enhanced professional development and institutional support. **Next steps** focus on operationalising a project-wide inclusion rubric across funding, design, delivery, and evaluation phases, ensuring that gender mainstreaming and sustainability are embedded as enduring organisational practices.

AOEs have generated a blend of tangible tools, organisational changes, GRSIE community-building, and knowledge dissemination activities, scalable and replicable, all embedding gender responsiveness in innovation, transport, health, AI, entrepreneurship, and cultural spaces. The outputs put forward can be grouped into different categories. On the practical side, they include dashboards, polling platforms, games, and toolkits that provide tangible resources and interactive tools. Structurally, they involve organisational reforms, the establishment of inclusion committees, and the creation of networks designed to embed gender responsiveness into institutions and communities. Educational outputs take the form of training programmes, workshops, summer schools, and lectures that build capacity and spread awareness. Finally, knowledge outputs encompass papers, policy recommendations, presentations, and websites that disseminate insights and evidence to wider audiences. Most AOE have produced outcomes across all these categories, focusing their impact on policy and organisational change, capacity building and training, building networks and communities of gender responsiveness in innovation ecosystems, the creation of new tools, platforms, and methodologies that can be used by others, and knowledge production and dissemination.

The ways in which AOE have influenced institutions and communities by embedding new practices and shifting their perspectives towards gender and inclusion has followed different pathways. Table 16

summarises the different pathways to impact that each AOE has followed and the macro-objectives that have been addressed.

Table 17. AOE, Objectives and Pathways to Impact

AOE	OC	Pathway to Impact
AOE1: Open Innovation Platform for Gender Responsive Collaborative Innovation	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations.	2a: Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA – Individuals.
AOE2: Brick by Brick: Supporting Women in Academia in Their Spinout/Business Journey	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies. OB/02 To enhance professional development. OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations.	1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe.
AO3: Increasing GRSIE in new medical devices, healthcare tech and tech-dependent intervention	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations.	Pathway 1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe. 2a. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA – individuals.
AOE4: Increasing capacity of excluded groups to act as GRSIE in their local community	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations. OD/04. To allow gendered educational practices from primary schools to Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) embodying and enabling recognition of the ethical and business cases for gender equality.	1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe. 2a. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA – individuals. 2b. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA – society.
AOE5: Addressing Gender Inclusion in Transport Research	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations.	Pathway 1a. Advancement of knowledge on gender-responsive innovation in Europe.
AOE6: Measuring citizen's perceptions of gender equality measures	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies. OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations.	Pathway 1a: Advancement of knowledge on gender-responsive innovation in Europe.
AOE7: The use of gender disaggregated data to guide urban planning	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies.	All
AOE8: Increasing capacity of start-ups to address gender related issues	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies.	All

AOE9: Co-creation of polling platform to support crowdsourcing for GRSIE	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations.	All
AOE10: Reducing gender inequalities in AI /IT workplace and entrepreneurship	OB/02 To enhance professional development. OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations.	1b. Advancement of practices on gender - responsive innovation in Europe. 2a. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA – individuals. 2b. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA – society.
AOE11: Deploying GILL methodology in a local authority	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies. OB/02 To enhance professional development. OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations.	All
AOE12: Reducing gender inequalities to entrepreneurs during pandemics and crises	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies.	1a: Advancement of knowledge on gender-responsive innovation in Europe. 2b. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA – society.
AOE13: Retaining women in tech companies by changing workplace culture	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies. OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations.	Pathway 1a. Advancement of knowledge on gender-responsive innovation in Europe. Pathway 1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe. Pathway 2a. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA – individuals.
AOE14: Increasing understanding of intersectionality and transport in smart cities through gamification	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations. OD/04 To allow gendered educational practices.	Pathway 1a. Advancement of knowledge on gender-responsive innovation in Europe. Pathway 1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe.
AOE15: Applying GRSIE to the design of museum exhibits for more inclusive engagement and highlighting of gender inequalities	OB/02 To enhance professional development, OD/04 To allow gendered educational practices	All

Regarding the alignment of AOE's impact with the expected outcomes of the project, AOE's impact has contributed to the different pathways in multiple ways.

Several AOE's advanced methodological innovation and knowledge creation in Europe. AOE6 combined AI methods with participatory approaches to measure citizen perceptions of gender equality on social media, representing a replicable methodological innovation. AOE14 developed a gamified tool to teach intersectionality in transport systems, which has already led to the creation of a funded start-up. AOE12 fostered critical reflection on entrepreneurship during crises, encouraging participants to interrogate how policies perpetuate inequalities and how to avoid them, and producing a set of policy recommendations applicable in different contexts. AOE 5 developed a set of recommendations to make transport research inclusive that have been incorporated to master's programme.

Regarding the advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe, AOE2 a network of women in academia interested in starting a business with monthly sessions, called salons on confidence-building, soft skills, and role-model connections. AOE4 applied **GILL** methods to the development of their citizen social scientist programme, enabling local councils to engage with marginalised local voices such as migrant women, often excluded from business or innovation support policies, ensuring policy makers learn about community concerns. AOE13 facilitated partnerships with technology companies, resulting in co-created gender-responsive strategies to change workplace cultures, which are already being implemented. And AOE3 triggered institutional change in health technology practices, embedding gender-responsive tools into the development of medical devices and healthcare technologies.

In terms of the strengthening of innovation and inclusiveness in the ERA, some AOE's worked at individual level, AOE1 contributed to the democratisation of design processes through a semi-automated Design Brief Generator, enabling citizens to create gender-responsive design briefs. AOE10 strengthened the skills of women and other stakeholders in AI and digital entrepreneurship, equipping them with tools to address bias and conduct gender impact assessments. Other AOE's focused on societal-level change. AOE4 identified gaps in business support for excluded communities and developed a new methodology for local councils to engage marginalised groups, building their skills to identify, research, and communicate their own issues to authorities, ensuring more societal voices are integrated into innovation processes. AOE11 achieved structural change by updating Alba Iulia's municipality regulations to eliminate gender-based discrimination, introducing flexible work options, and strengthening governance and creating networks and local events for local entrepreneurs working or interested in gender innovation. AOE15 embedded diversity considerations into science centre exhibitions, changing their organisational culture and ensuring accessibility and representation in exhibits. AOE7 worked with transport companies to develop inclusive strategies to include translated complex mobility survey data into accessible, gender-disaggregated personas, enabling urban planning stakeholders to act upon gendered evidence. AOE8 cultivated cultural change within start-up ecosystems, linking gender awareness to business outcomes and staff wellbeing, creating resources for gender-focused training, guidelines and recommendations for entrepreneurs and incubators, and setting up networks of entrepreneurs interested in gender innovation.

Many AOE's' work has taken place across all pathways, including AOE7, which worked with transport companies to translate complex mobility survey data into accessible, gender-disaggregated personas, enabling urban planning stakeholders to better understand and act upon gendered evidence. In the private sector.

Taken together, these outcomes demonstrate how AOE's not only achieved their immediate objectives but also created pathways to sustained impact. They advanced knowledge, transformed practices, empowered individuals, and strengthened societal inclusiveness. Across all pathways, the AOE's

contributed to the project's macro-objectives, employing diverse approaches ranging from individual and team practices to new tools and methods, and addressing vertical themes of digital and green transitions, health, resilience, and societal innovation.

4.2.2 Summary of key impact across AOE

Across the AOE, GILL strengthened the capacity of researchers, entrepreneurs, civil servants, designers, technologists, and innovation practitioners to recognise and address gender inequalities in their work. Participants acquired practical skills in gender analysis, inclusive design, data interpretation, reflexive practice, and co-creation, moving beyond abstract awareness to applied competence. This capacity building has had lasting effects, with tools, training materials, and methods continuing to be used beyond the project timeframe.

Transformation of organisational cultures and practices

Many AOE achieved impact by shifting organisational cultures rather than targeting individuals alone. Changes included revised governance structures, new internal procedures, gender-inclusive communication practices, safer working environments, and the embedding of gender perspectives into routine workflows. These transformations demonstrate that sustainable gender equality in RIE requires institutional change, leadership engagement, and alignment with organisational priorities such as productivity, wellbeing, and innovation quality.

Improved innovation processes and outcomes

By integrating gender and intersectional perspectives into innovation pathways—from problem framing and data collection to product design and evaluation—the AOE improved the relevance, inclusiveness, and robustness of innovation outputs. Gender-disaggregated data, personas, inclusive AI practices, and participatory methods enabled innovators to identify unmet needs, reduce bias, and design solutions that better reflect diverse users and markets.

Development of transferable tools, methods, and resources

A core impact of GILL lies in the creation and testing of practical, reusable tools, including design brief generators, training packs, polling platforms, gamified learning tools, organisational reflection methods, and guidelines for gender innovation. These resources have been adapted across contexts and are being taken up by external organisations, projects, and networks, demonstrating strong potential for replication and scaling.

Strengthening of ecosystems, networks, and entrepreneurship

Several AOE contributed to the formation of new networks, partnerships, and entrepreneurial activities centred on gender innovation. These include networks of start-ups, collaborations between gender and business experts, spin-off initiatives, and new market-ready solutions. By linking gender equality to innovation performance and societal impact, GILL has helped position gender-responsive innovation as a shared responsibility across RIE ecosystems.

Policy relevance and societal impact

Finally, the AOE generated evidence and approaches that support more inclusive, data-driven policymaking, particularly in areas such as transport, urban development, crisis response, and digital

governance. By making gendered evidence more accessible and actionable, GILL has strengthened the connection between research, innovation, policy, and lived experience.

Contribution to Horizon Europe Expected Impacts

Through its 15 Areas of Experimentation (AOEs), GILL has generated measurable and credible contributions to Horizon Europe's expected impacts on **gender equality in research, innovation and entrepreneurship (RIE)**. The project demonstrates how gender equality objectives can be translated into operational practices that enhance the **quality, relevance, and societal value of R&I**, in line with Horizon Europe's cross-cutting gender equality requirements and the EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025.

Rather than treating gender as a compliance exercise, GILL shows how embedding gender and intersectional perspectives into innovation processes, organisational practices, data systems, and governance structures produces **more inclusive, effective, and sustainable innovation outcomes**. The AOEs collectively provide evidence-based pathways for mainstreaming gender equality across diverse R&I environments, including public authorities, universities, SMEs, start-ups, Living Labs, and digital innovation ecosystems

4.3 Impact on GILL partners and their organisations

As part of EO1: Advancement of knowledge and practice on gender-responsive innovation in Europe, by participating in GILL, each partner had the opportunity to benefit from new methods and concepts, extend their knowledge and practice of gender, and be empowered to implement changes in their own organisation.

This is an intrinsic part of knowledge acquisition, transfer, and diffusion. Partners in **GILL** are on a learning journey, they take forward knowledge, experiences and know-how into their own organisations, work with stakeholders and future projects.

The impact on **GILL** partners was measured in two ways.

- Through a self-completion gender competency checklist
- A reflective diary in they documented everyday experiences of gender inequality, why they interpreted behaviour as being discriminatory, and how they would address this.

Through reflecting in, on and through practice we can constantly evaluate our initial understanding and conceptualisation of GRSIE.

In using these 2 approaches we expected to see an increase in gender competency and a heightened awareness and sophistication in understanding gender inequalities.

4.4 Gender competency

Whilst the original intention had been to develop a gender competency checklist as part of the **GILL** project, a state-of-the-art review revealed the existence of many such checklists which were already fit for purpose. Initial discussion with the University of Toronto provided an assurance that their checklist would remain freely available for the lifetime of the project. The Framework developed by the (<https://www.gendereconomy.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/GACF.pdf>)¹⁰ was used to benchmark and then consider the growth in capacity of consortium members to address gender

¹⁰ <https://www.gendereconomy.org/gender-analysis-competency-framework/>

related issues in their organisations. The Framework is divided into three sections: 1) The 5 W's (What, Why, Where, When and Who of Gender Analysis): 2) How: Applying Gender Analysis and 3) Organizational and Cultural Support. It identifies 16 competencies with a variety of different skills at each level:

- Basic skills are appropriate for those who are interested in understanding gender analysis or expected to participate in part of the process; or for senior leaders who need to know how to commission and interpret gender analysis.
- Intermediate skills appropriate for those practicing gender analysis in day-to-day work; or for those expected to work with experts.
- Advanced skills are those appropriate for gender advisors or those working in the area of gender equity; or for those who need to be experts in gender analysis.

The self-assessment quiz¹¹, enables return visits, and when completed, immediately provides a tailored pdf file to guide the development of personal action plans for capacity development. Repeat visits can be used to show skill development.

Method

In order to establish an understanding of baseline gender competence within the consortium, by the end of M1, all partners were given instructions on how to access the site and return their results anonymously to the Coventry team. Over the next few months, reminder emails were sent out. Thirteen completed forms were returned, and analysis presented at the interim review meeting. The process was repeated in the last quarter of the project, resulting in eleven completed forms. In both cases this was a disappointing return rate. The results are shown in Annex 3. At least one representative from each partner organisation completed the form.

The original intention had been to use a matched pairs analysis, given the size of the dataset this was not possible. In both cases, the results were pooled, and the number of checkboxes counted for each skill level the participant believed they had reached. This was converted into percentage scores so that means could be compared for both time periods.

Results

Results can only be indicative, due to the low rate of return but are in line with expectations. Figure 10 shows that the level of competence amongst project partners at the start of the project was lower at all levels, and their competency higher in the basic skills. There was an increase in self-reported gender skills competence at all levels by the end of the project, with a slightly larger increase in the advanced skills.

¹¹ https://rotman.az1.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_5no6Lo4kmvcn0u9

Figure 10. Comparison of partners' overall gender competency scores at the start and end of GILL

Table 17 breaks this down further in terms of the scores for each competence subsection. The end of project scores showed an improvement on baseline (shown in red) in all but 2 cases (1.1 Understand the key concepts related to gender and 2.6 rapid prototyping, shown in blue). The cells in orange show where the largest gains occurred. A more detailed breakdown, per question is shown in Annex 3.

Table 18. Comparison of partners' competency scores by section

Section	Competence	Basic skills		Intermediate skills		Advanced skills		Total	Mean
		Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score		
Section 1: The 5 Ws	1.1 Understand key concepts related to gender	98.5	100	80.8	77.3	59	69.7	485.3	80.88333
	1.2 Understand how intersectionality impacts outcomes	94.2	97.7	69.2	87.8	50	50.3	449.2	74.86667
	1.3 Understands the benefits of gender analysis	88.5	90.9	80.8	81.8	57.7	72.7	472.4	78.73333
	1.4 Where and when: See opportunities for gender analysis	79.5	87.9	80.8	86.4	53.8	63.6	452	75.33333
	1.5 Determine who in the organization should be involved in gender analysis	71.8	87.8	69.2	75.8	28.2	60.6	393.4	65.56667
Section 2 :Applying Gender Analysis	2.1 Clarify problem statement	76.9	90.9	53.8	81.8	38.5	84.6	426.5	71.08333
	2.2 Collect qualitative data ethically	84.6	97	75	86.4	69.2	72.7	484.9	80.81667
	2.3 Collect gender-disaggregated quantitative data ethically	75.4	81.8	67.3	70.5	46.2	57.6	398.8	66.46667
	2.4 Generate integrative insights	76.9	96.4	65.4	86.4	46.2	60.6	431.9	71.98333
	2.5 Design for equity	76.9	97	53.8	81.8	33.3	45.5	388.3	64.71667
	2.6 Rapid prototyping	84.6	75.8	69.2	69.7	50	50	399.3	66.55
	2.7 Equitable resource allocation	69.2	86.4	50	81.8	26.9	40.9	355.2	59.2
	2.8 Assessing impact	69.2	93.9	50	63.6	38.5	50	365.2	60.86667
	2.9 Sustainable adaptation	65.4	100	53.8	95.5	42.3	81.8	438.8	73.13333
Section 3: Organizational & Cultural Support	3.1 Effective collaboration	71.8	96.9	57.7	84	38.5	59	407.9	67.98333
	3.2 Fostering organizational change	79.5	90.9	36.5	65.9	26.9	61.4	59.94	60.18333

This shows for scores which increased, highest gains related to

- 1.5 Determine who in the organization should be involved in gender analysis: Advanced skills relating to *'Can troubleshoot issues arising from cross-departmental collaborations'* and *'Ensures organizational capacity and structures are in place for collaborations'*
- 2.5 Design for equity: Advanced skills relating to *'Pushes for game-changing designs based on the data insights'*
- 2.9 Sustainable adaptation: Advanced skills relating to *'Disseminates gender analysis learnings (including gaps, success and opportunities)'*
- 3.2 Fostering organizational change;
 - Intermediate skills relating to *'Advises on accountability practices and communications plan related to gender analysis'*
 - Advanced skills relating to *'Breaks down barriers to the gender analysis process using knowledge, empathy, and evidence'*, *'Embeds gender analysis processes in all areas of work in the organization'* and *'Strengthens the implementation of gender analysis through ongoing evaluation and learning, and sharing of effective practices.'*
- For scores which decreased
 - 1.1 Understand the key concepts related to gender related to a drop in the score of *'Consciously works to challenge gender stereotypes'* which may be difficult for some junior colleagues to address.
 - 2.6 rapid prototyping showed slightly decreases in answers to most questions. This might be because partners were not engaged in what is commonly regarded as rapid prototyping
 - 2.5 Design for equity: Advanced skills relating to *'Identifies roadblocks to implementation of design and leads effort to remove them or design around them'*

Conclusions and discussions

The relatively low level of **advanced gender** competence as measured at baseline being below 50% in relation to:

- Section 1: The 5 Ws (1.5 Determine who in the organization should be involved in gender analysis)
- Section 2: Applying gender analysis (2.1 Clarify problem statement, 2.3 Collect gender-disaggregated quantitative data ethically, 2.4 Generate integrative insights, 2.5 Design for equity, 2.7 Equitable resource allocation, 2.8 Assessing impact, 2.9 Sustainable adaptation)
- Section 3: Organisational and cultural support (both 3.1 Effective collaboration and 3.2 Fostering organizational change might have meant that many partners were not sufficiently aware of gender issues or had the skills and agency within their networks to create impact. The increased levels of gender competence in the project as measured at the end of the project can be attributable to internal **GILL** workshops; gender capacity building webinars and events organised by ENoLL and the use of GRSIE tools in the AOE.

In adapting a feminist phenomenological approach to impact assessment, the **GILL** project has attempted to understand at a deeper level the impact working on an EU project can have on its members. The adoption of the gender competency framework enabled us to do this, in relation to assessing how partners gained transferable knowledge and skills through working on the project. We believe such an approach is extremely valuable.

Methodological limitations: The lack of buy in of partners meant that these results can merely be indicative of the impact of the project on partners. Response bias might have meant that those most engaged and benefiting from the project were those most likely to respond. However, the results do triangulate well with other impact measures, showing an overall increase in competence and development of transferable skills, knowledge and practice.

4.5 Reflective Diaries

Reflection has been an integral part of our work in **GILL**. Using reflective diaries and autoethnography as analytical tools in the project evaluation allows for an examination of the dynamics that unfold in a European project such as **GILL**, including gendered patterns but also personal experiences, contextual factors, and cultural narratives that shape project outcomes. Reflective diaries are individual and serve as a personal lens through which project partners can appraise their thoughts and feelings over time, revealing how gender and related issues can affect daily practices. These personal narratives provide a window into the impact of **GILL** on its partners, leading to meaningful insights about project effectiveness and change. The impact on partners and the project was significant, but difficult to measure. Early reflections documented underpinning assumptions that women lacked technical expertise, or perceptions of male partners dominating meeting spaces, which clearly changed over time. Diaries included actionable strategies for change from partners, such as getting involved in certain aspects of organisation, adopting more inclusive formats during meetings, or setting personal goals to intervene more confidently in discussions or react to certain situations. Partners also reflected on their own emotional responses to certain behaviour's coming from colleagues, interrogating the assumptions that triggered them and how to change that. Over time, diaries charted a shift toward more balanced participation, more equal distributions of airtime, and conscious efforts to avoid exclusionary practices.

Why Reflective Diaries

Reflective diaries provide a structured way for individuals involved in **GILL** to document their observations, challenges, and learning experiences. As demonstrated in the work of Sudirman et al. (2021), this practice contributes to transformative learning by facilitating self-discovery and critical thought processes. It allows individuals to engage in critical reflection of their actions and what happens around them, helping to synthesise new knowledge and understanding about their roles within a group, a meeting, a consortium, a project. It helps to uncover unconscious thought patterns, leading to an understanding of how each partner's background and positionality influences behaviour. Autoethnographic reflection is part of **GILL**'s process evaluation and, as such, it is included in the overall evaluation task.

This autoethnographic approach complements the reflective process by enabling partners to connect their personal experiences with the wider sociocultural contexts and become aware of how those processes materialise in the project, articulate that awareness, and share it, something that can be crucial for both personal development, as it spreads to other contexts in which partners work, and collective project assessments. Newcomb et al. (2022) highlight the potential of collaborative autoethnography to explore shared experiences among researchers, allowing for diverse perspectives to emerge that enrich the understanding of sociocultural phenomena in project settings. This aligns with Hernandez-Carranza et al.'s (2021) assertion that autoethnography enhances reflexivity and facilitates a critical engagement with power dynamics that inform practices. Malone et al. (2024) argue that utilising an intersectional lens in autoethnographic research encourages a nuanced exploration of

individual experiences within systemic structures, and, we argue, in understanding the interdisciplinary, multi-institutional, international, and multicultural dynamics of a Horizon Europe project. This approach can uncover underlying biases and systemic issues influencing project impact, making complexities visible that might otherwise go unexamined within projects.

Methodology

In terms of methodology and data collection, we implemented the use of individual reflective journals at the outset of the project, with each partner maintaining an individual record of key **GILL** events. Partners were asked to write one reflective entry every year of the project covering a major project meeting of their choosing (consortium meetings, standup meetings, WP meetings, etc.), whether they were participants or facilitators. To ensure immediacy and accuracy, we asked for entries to be written as soon as possible following the relevant meeting. While we requested basic contextual details to situate each reflection and provide attributes for analysis, we were not interested in the content or the outcomes of the meetings. Rather, we sought to capture insights into group dynamics, matters relating to gender, emotions, themes of concern, and how partners interpreted what was happening. The journal instructions specifically directed participants to attend to questions such as: Who controlled the dialogue in the meeting? Were men or other privileged individuals afforded more speaking time or deference? Was the central seat reserved for them? What role did technology play in shaping the meeting experience, and did it serve to privilege certain participants while disadvantaging others? In addition, partners were asked to reflect on their own positionality—how their personal background and professional experience influenced their perceptions of the events described—and to consider what steps they might take to address any issues identified. Each journals included a list with the following general topics of reflection:

- Was there a gender/ race/ class dimension to the discussions?
- How were conflicts resolved during the meeting?
- Which group's views and opinions were missing?
- Was there any gender bias in assignation of roles during the meeting e.g. who made the coffee, cleaned up after the meeting, took minutes, supported IT?
- Who was deferred to during the meeting, did this relate to age, gender, seniority?
- What basic assumptions were raised, or were evident concerning the relevance of gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity and other social categories?
- Did social or other factors influence the teamwork or culture?
- How were decisions made – who led this and had the power, who controlled the flow of the meeting?
- Was the language used appropriate with no room for homophobic jokes, racism and sexism or expressions against disabled people?
- What attempts were made to make the meeting/event welcoming and inclusive to all?

Journals were collected after consortium meetings and, alternatively, at the end of each AOE iteration cycle, as we asked AOE leaders to keep a similar reflective diary for the running of their AOE. The team at Coventry University collected and processed the reflective journals. First, cleaning the data to make sure it was anonymised. We used qualitative analysis techniques, coding the journals to identify the main themes arising from the reflections in the different years of the project, what issues were reflected on, what emotions were involved, silences, etc.

Table 19. *List of Codes and frequency of appearance in the reflective journals by year of the **GILL** project*

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List of Codes	Year=2023	Year = 2024	Year = 2025
Communication (+)	2	2	1
Gender Dynamics among partners (+)	6	16	4
Language used (+)	6	1	0
Organisation and facilitation of the meeting (+)	6	8	1
Emotional Responses	4	14	0
Reflections about future actions	4	5	1
Issues with communication among partners	3	6	1
Domination on meetings	5	11	0
Lack of diversity	3	6	2
Problematic gendered dynamics	5	16	2
Hierarchies and power relations	2	8	5
Issues with meeting organisation	5	25	6
Problematic role assignments	2	4	1
Learnings	4	5	2
Self-positionality	4	7	4
Solutions to implement	10	13	6

Partners' positionality in project meetings: power dynamics and identity

In their diaries, partners offered personal reflections into their experiences of positionality within the meetings of such a complex, international, collaborative project. These entries reveal how identity, professional status, and social dynamics shape participation, voice, and influence in group settings, shift along the years working in **GILL**.

A central theme emerging from the reflections is the complex interplay of power dynamics within the project and their materialisation during meetings. Partners primarily perceived in their diaries that professional seniority and expertise, rather than gender, influenced the decision-making processes of the project. Partners also reflected on how their own geographic and professional backgrounds shaped their experiences. In their view, originating from Northern, Eastern, or Southern European countries was as a factor that mattered within the wider group context. Language competency played a significant role too. Some non-native English speakers articulated in their reflections a reticence to speak up in big meetings, feeling intimidated by the perceived higher English competency of others, particularly among those who were new to working in a European project setting. This was a frequent, sometimes underlying, barrier to participation. Conversely, native speakers or partners with a high English competence reported feeling an expectation to lead participation in discussions, which sometimes conflicted with other identity considerations, especially for men in the project. They

reflected about how to carefully navigate their position, consciously avoiding dominating discussions while still attempting to engage insightfully and offering their expertise. Partners unanimously appreciated the project's use of inclusive and appropriate language, noting the absence of inappropriate jokes or comments in their experience.

Care responsibilities were perceived as influencing participation too. Hybrid and online meetings posed challenges, particularly when agendas were not respected, conflicting with caregiving duties. In contrast, face-to-face meetings abroad were seen as more manageable, as there was always time to make proper arrangements and allowed for temporary, dedicated focus on the project.

Those identifying as junior or early career researchers often reflected that they felt uncomfortable speaking in large group settings. However, they used the diaries to identify moments when they felt more confident and engaged, for example, in smaller breakout groups, finding the atmosphere more comfortable and less intimidating, regardless of their colleagues' seniority. Personality traits like shyness and lack of presentation experience were barriers but, interestingly, the prompts in our diaries guided women partners to question the gendered aspects at the origin of their reluctance. Discomfort speaking up without having enough information about an issue or reluctance to disagree with other partners in discussions were some of the elements identified as gendered expectations of themselves. Some of these partners used their diaries to set small challenges to complete in coming project meetings: volunteer as rapporteur of their break-out groups, stand up for themselves if put on the spot, intervening at least once in a future meeting.

Being in minority positions made some partners hesitant to contribute too, fearing that input might not be what the project needed, or what the group wanted to hear. Interestingly, some male partners drew parallels between their feeling of hesitation when being in a minority and how it is often reported to be a woman in male-dominated environments, leading to insightful reflections that pointed to intersectionality and the need for meeting structures that actively counteract exclusionary dynamics beyond **GILL**.

Organisational dynamics and facilitation

The structure and facilitation of meetings, particularly in the first year, elicited significant emotional reactions. Partners expressed frustration when formats were not consistent or when they did not understand the goals or expectations in meeting, for example, with anxiety about last-minute changes to their presentations. As the project progressed, partners reflected positively on the improved organisational aspect of meetings, clear agenda setting, facilitators moving conversations forward, etc.

Small group formats (breakout rooms, workshops) were consistently praised for fostering more inclusive participation and confidence to early career partners. This contrast between large and small group dynamics underscores the importance of thoughtful facilitation in creating equitable dialogue spaces.

Gendered dynamics in the project

Project partners reveal a complex and sometimes tense landscape of gendered dynamics within meetings, which evolved over the course of the project. Informal power structures and cultural assumptions continued to shape interactions, even in a project focused on gender with a majority of

female partners that meant a high level of gender awareness. However, the diversity of disciplines, cultures, institutions, and technical profiles added layers to these dynamics.

In the first year of the project, reflections focused on instances of male partners dominating meeting spaces. Assumptions that women lack technical knowledge, and that technical knowledge yields more power than other types of expertise were identified, underpinning some presentations at the start of the project, producing frustration on female partners with expertise on those areas. Such assumptions made them feel the effects of the “prove-it-again” bias. Over time, however, the focus shifted: later reflections emphasised hierarchies and pressing topics rather than gendered dominance in the distribution of time and praised good facilitation in meetings.

Early observations noted some unconscious role assignments, such as younger male partners acting as “technical support” for senior colleagues, particularly in virtual settings. Yet as the project progressed, partners increasingly acknowledged that **GILL** meetings were free from such dynamics, unlike other meetings they participate regularly as part of their jobs.

In the last year of the project, participants reflected on the difficulties to engage male partners in conversations beyond the technical, specifically about gender. Partners reflected on this positioning as limiting because of the potential to perpetuate the notion that equity was primarily a women’s concern, an idea that this project has worked hard to dispel. Reflective practice nonetheless proved invaluable to bring forward important processes and decisions happening during meetings, with male partners navigating gendered expectations in co-creative spaces and reflecting on their own attitudes and concerns about speaking too early in discussions or remaining too quiet, doubting the value of their perspectives sometimes. Taking part without taking over was a conscious thought informing the behaviours of many in **GILL** meetings.

Emotional Landscape

The emotional tone of the reflections ranged from comfort and confidence to frustration, hesitation, and fear, often revealing deeper contextual dynamics from the partners' perspective:

Table 20. Summary of Emotions by Partners in Reflective Diaries

Emotions in Diaries	Context
Comfort	When engaging in small groups or among familiar peers
Hesitation	Speaking in large groups, especially for junior or minority participants
Frustration	With unclear presentation formats and rushed meeting structures
Anger	At gendered assumptions of technical expertise, and unequal use of airtime
Concern	About inclusivity, following formats, and facilitation practices
Surprise	At personal ease in certain roles (e.g., group spokesperson), overcoming challenges
Annoyance	When others disregard agreed-upon presentation norms
Fear	That contributions may be dismissed or not understood
Discomfort	At tension among partners, especially between female partners
Satisfaction	At presentations delivered by multiple colleagues with different levels of seniority who keep their times, build each other’s points, present interesting information, engage with questions.

Impact of reflective diaries on project partners

Diaries reflections showed shifts over time in participants' awareness and activities: meetings during **GILL** started to be praised by partners for collaboration among colleagues, for great facilitation in moments of tension, junior partners found ways of overcoming their barriers in voicing their opinion in bigger meetings by identifying manageable strategies like volunteering to report small group discussions, presenting on behalf of their teams, or preparing questions beforehand.

Diaries captured reflections about behaviours during meetings that would normally left unsaid, including how male partners approached their behaviour, were really aware of the behaviour of other male partners too. The complexity of that awareness also progressed as the reflective practice was settled in the project, with more attention to positive dynamics that are not always common in other settings, such as praising of partners' work, moments of encouragement, of seamless collaboration, etc. Similarly, tension and conflict were also analysed through gendered lens. These reflections that arose within **GILL**, because of the nature of the project, were linked to partners' experiences in other settings with different dynamics, e.g., male partners being the majority.

Attention to more practical issues such as presentation styles was also reflected on from a gendered perspective, for example, ways of addressing cues like hand-raising and questions from the audience, chat discussions, etc. Partners wrote about which strategies they found more inclusive, and how they planned to incorporate those realisations to their own styles to shape discussions in future.

This reflective approach has been successful, as many partners engaged with it and wrote and submitted their diaries. It has proved invaluable for surfacing internal biases, emotional dynamics, and patterns. The results reinforce the importance of inclusive meeting practices and GRSIE methods to include all voices, regardless of seniority, gender, personality, or even language competence. And it has also reinforced the need to strengthen male engagement in gender innovation projects, developing structured opportunities for men to reflect on gendered expectations and equity, reducing resistance to engage.

5 Discussion of barriers, enablers and challenges going forward

5.1 Critical risks and perceived barriers to impact included in the DoA

11 critical risks were identified in the 'critical risks and risk management strategy' table in the DoA.

Table 21. Foreseen Critical Risks and their perceived impact

Risk nos	Description	WP	Reflection on the effects on the impact of the project and its assessment
1	Lack of available/accessible information on existing methods and their uptake [L:Low, S:Med]	WP1	Risk did not materialise.
2	Lack of response to surveys on the barriers and need analysis [L:Low, S:High]	WP2, WP1	A low response from some stakeholder groups to surveys and co-creation activities meant that the results and subsequent design of project elements was biased towards the needs of the academic community.
3	Lack of engaged participants in the co-creation activities [L:Low, S:High]	WP2	
4	Lack of engaged participants in the co-creation activities [L:Low, S:High]	WP3	Lack of engagement had a substantial effect on some AOE's, despite risk management strategy being implemented. This had significant consequences in terms of resources spent in recruitment efforts, redesign of work and outcomes/impact.
5	Not achieving sufficient reach in terms of the platform's AI and DLT capabilities. [L:Med, S:High]	WP2	Unable to comment.
6	Creating a platform dependent on the chosen Cloud provider. [L:Low, S:Med]	WP2	There were substantial hold ups and technical difficulties with the platform and its functionality which delayed releases and engagement.
7	Low community building & stakeholders' engagement [L:Low, S:High]	all	This item related to capacity building and the Risk did not materialise.
8	Lack of understanding of key concepts across consortium [L:Low, S:Med]	WP5, WP1	Risk did not materialise.
9	Difficulty in managing a wide consortium [L:Low,S:Med]	WP5	The degree of organisational churn of senior project members contributed to some deviations
10	A partner leaves the consortium [L:Low, S:Low]	all	Risk did not materialise but see above. Whilst CU did not leave the consortium, its LL was wound down – with the loss of 35 staff, resources and community networks which seriously effected its AOE's and health and wellbeing of CU partners
11	Constraints due to COVID-19 situation slow down the implementation of the work plan [L:Med, S:Med]	all	Risk did not materialise.

From the initial set of risks those which are perceived to have the most impact on the project were external ones, such as organisational churn and low levels of buy in by key stakeholder groups. These were not insurmountable but took their toll on project members.

Lack of buy in of key stakeholder/user groups is common across many projects. The standard mitigation measures were undertaken e.g. inducements, change of venue, time and type of meeting, reframing of activity.

There may well be a gender barrier here:

- gender issues are low priority – so line managers of participants may not have given permission to attend.
- activities which are labelled ‘gender’ are not perceived as inclusive.
- people do not want to engage in GRSIE – as in the case of 2 participants refusing to engage in gender responsive design activities.
- Those delivering **GILL** activities lacked the power and authority to deliver in ‘hostile or indifferent’ cultures.
- Women participants could make time to attend events

The DoA outlined the following external framework factors that might work against **GILL** objectives and pathways to impact and planned mitigation actions.

Lack of interest. A barrier that is related to the uptake of the project results is the lack of interest from local communities and other actors in the QH. To overcome this barrier, the project will tailor dissemination and communication material to local situations and concrete contexts which will clearly demonstrate the potential for GRSIE and attract wider engagement and interest in GRSIE and intersectional issues.

Adoption rate. Despite the requirement for public bodies, research organisations or HEI to have a GEP in place in order to benefit of EC funding, European organisations may be restrained by what they can implement at an institutional transformation to enforce gender equality within their methods and methodologies. **GILL** will develop an ad-hoc dissemination and communication campaign to overcome such barriers, highlighting the benefits of such approach not only in terms of equality but also in terms of social, techno-economic and scientific impact.

Funding of follow-up steps. A complication may arise through financing of the follow-up steps to ensure the long-term sustainability of the pan-European hub as detailed in D4.6

Economic and well-being. Economic fluctuations have occurred which do effect RI&E. The current threats are not related to a global pandemic but around safety and security. The rise of populism and the far right is already having significant effects on gender equality in RI&E and required new policies and strategies to support women’s thought leadership and entrepreneurship.

5.2 Reappraisal of barriers to impact, enablers and mitigation measures

Many of the barriers to impact AOE reported were systemic, encompassing lack of awareness and prioritising of gender equality and inclusion in general, cultural resistances, resource limitations, data deficiencies, and low engagement.

Table 22. Actual barriers and enablers to impact found by the AOE

AOE	Barriers to Impact Identified	Enablers to Impact Identified
AOE1: Open Innovation Platform for Gender Responsive Collaborative Innovation	Technical challenges for the creation of the DBG in collaboration with technical colleagues, interdisciplinary communication gaps with partners regarding the method. Difficulty getting users to adopt professional methods.	Shifting to a solo user interaction model. Strong local leadership support and expert citizen/entrepreneur engagement.
AOE2: Brick by Brick: Supporting Women in Academia in Their Spinout/Business Journey	Low engagement from participants in events, time management issues for participants. Lack of resources and institutional changes/restructuring.	Local role models willing to fully engage, mentor, and share resources despite constraints.
AO3: Increasing GRSIE in new medical devices, healthcare tech and tech-dependent intervention	Institutional inertia and resistance to embedding new methods. Data visibility and granularity issues requiring extensive cleaning.	GILL project level priority and dedicated time. Structured GILL tools (e.g., Fair Meetings). Favourable external policy context (women's health).
AOE4: Increasing capacity of excluded groups to act as GRSIE in their local community	Withdrawal of external funding (e.g., Ecopreneurs). Shutdown of FabLab. Lack of resources and institutional changes/restructuring.	Existing strong partnerships and other available programmes working with the targeted community.
AOE5: Addressing Gender Inclusion in Transport Research	Initial reluctance among senior researchers to recognise gender imbalance. Time/funding constraints for sustained data collection. Difficulties engaging industry without prior contacts.	Strong GILL consortium partnership and credibility. Policy alignment with Horizon Europe mandate. Active support from institutional leadership.
AOE6: Measuring citizen's perceptions of gender equality measures	API restrictions and rate limits on data extraction (Reddit). Heterogeneity and potential bias of social media data. Ethical and privacy concerns with sensitive discussions.	GILL Trustworthy AI framework. Participatory Living Lab approach. Strong technical toolkit (NLP pipelines, prototyping tools).
AOE7: The use of gender disaggregated data to guide urban planning	Challenging to find companies willing to engage and host activities. Difficulties engaging participants actively in workshops.	Crucial support and facilitation from company management. Access to large amounts of corporate mobility survey data.
AOE8: Increasing capacity of start-ups to address gender related issues	Communication gaps between gender expert teams and innovation experts. Initial resistance to gender data collection. Difficulty bringing diverse stakeholders together.	Engagement with projects with similar objectives at regional, national, and European level. Strong commitment from their leadership/directors.
AOE9: Co-creation of polling platform to	Sustaining long-term partnerships beyond project. Funding/commercialization challenges for prototype. Institutional uptake	Strong partnerships (GRNET/EDYTE). SBOING's leadership emphasis on gender-

support crowdsourcing for GRSIE	resistance (public bodies). Data privacy/GDPR complexity.	sensitive innovation. External mentoring grant funding support.
AOE10: Reducing gender inequalities in AI /IT workplace and entrepreneurship	Difficulty achieving consistent stakeholder engagement (especially male stakeholders). Balancing advanced vs. introductory training material.	Resources and methodologies provided by GILL (GRISE methods). The 4-phase iterative AOE approach. Team's experience from previous gender-related projects.
AOE11: Deploying GILL methodology in a local authority	Low levels of awareness and practical understanding of gender equality at the start. Fragmented existing policies not translating into change.	GILL's foundational methodology/framework. Access to a vital collaborative network through the GILL project.
AOE12: Reducing gender inequalities to entrepreneurs during pandemics and crises	Unavailability of adequate gender-segregated data. Low priority of the Gender Agenda for management. Low gender sensitivity and outright resistance.	GILL project infrastructure provided structure and financial resources.
AOE13: Retaining women in tech companies by changing workplace culture	Institutional resistance to gender-related issues. Lack of awareness/practical knowledge by those not affected by marginalisation, who do not believe that discrimination still exists and that their reality creates unfairness.	Partnerships with several stakeholders from several companies to gain a stakeholder network that includes the local community.
AOE14: Increasing understanding of intersectionality and transport in smart cities through gamification	Resource and technical limits for game development. Gender and diversity data being overlooked due to lack of awareness. Knowledge translation challenges for the game. Contextual constraints: differences across countries.	Strong partnerships with universities, municipalities, labs, think tanks, etc. Ludo design helped with accessibility. Available entrepreneurial pathways for the game.
AOE15: Applying GRSIE to the design of science centre/museum exhibits for more inclusive engagement and highlighting of gender inequalities	Sharing the burden of work involved in writing and developing plans on sustainability.	The "stop, start, continue" projects defined by all personnel. Establishment of an inclusion committee to connect the work across staff.

Most barriers identified fall under the following general categories:

1. Low awareness of existing inequalities and resistance

Many AOE's faced institutional inertias of gender equality and inclusion not being a priority, as well as initial reluctance to recognise gender imbalance as a systemic issue in their organisations.

Low levels of awareness and practical understanding of gender equality principles were a barrier at the start of many experimentations. This led in some instances to communication barriers as

messaging rooted in gender expertise was perceived as too abstract or even “moralistic” by colleagues from business and innovation sectors, creating a disconnect and lack of initial buy-in in some cases.

Additionally, sometimes existing policies and initiatives, which could be fragmented and overlooked within institutions became a barrier for new initiatives, as organisations considered themselves covered in terms of gender and inclusion.

2. Data and Technical Limitations

Challenges in collecting, managing, and using data happened, especially when dealing with advanced technologies or institutional systems. A critical barrier for some AOE was the unavailability or lack of adequate gender-disaggregated data (including economic data), for evidence-based interventions. Additionally, existing data collection systems are often not structured to capture gender or diversity indicators with enough richness. Teams who wanted to start collecting that data encountered resistance to implementing new systems for gender-related data collection, often because of lack of awareness.

Projects using digital methods ran into technical challenges (e.g., API restrictions and rate limits). And the development of new digital tools faced barriers due to restrictions based on regulatory compliances (polling system), or communication issues between partners in charge of IT and AOE designing tools. Finally, some public institutions lacked the internal mechanisms for institutional uptake of new digital tools and gender-inclusive data practices.

3. Engagement

Mobilising and maintaining the engagement of diverse stakeholders, from policymakers to citizen groups, required continuous effort. Lower than expected participation in events that created interest among networks was another issue, mainly due to participants’ time constraints and work-life balance, caring responsibilities, etc. In efforts to collect new data, AOE encountered difficulties in recruiting a diverse and representative crowd, requiring specific strategies to overcome "survey fatigue". Some partners found it difficult to engage male stakeholders, as often only women were sent to events because the theme of the sessions was gender, despite the project communicating and inviting men directly.

4. Resource and Sustainability Challenges

Some AOE suffered from restructuring in their institutions and significant reduction in support for key partners due to external circumstances. Barriers in accessing sustained funding and investment for transitioning prototypes to market-ready products have been central for some AOE, and in overcoming internal capacity and resource allocation issues for small organisations.

The short-term nature of the experiments made behavioural and attitudinal change during the lifespan of the pilots complicated, as it often requires a much longer-term process.

Adaptive Strategies to overcome barriers and maximise impact.

AOE have taken specific actions throughout the project to overcome the encountered barriers by adapting methodologies, restructuring organisational practices, focusing on improving communication, and adding flexibility.

Many AOE pivoted to focus on raising awareness and incorporating inclusive practices through the implementation GRSIE methods like Fair Meetings, Airtime Monitoring, Team Manifestos, Gender Assessments. AOE plans were shifted to create organisational change, even in the cases where it was not the main original objective. Improved communication with innovators, entrepreneurs, and industry was prioritised, reframing messaging regarding inclusion in economic and innovation terms,

emphasising gender-responsive practices' relevance to productivity, profitability, talent management, etc. Systematic reviews of internal policies and updating internal regulations and organisational charts were important to design interventions that create change.

1. Solving Data and Technical Limitations

To address data gaps, teams retrospectively analysed years of collaboration data and made plans to integrate dedicated gender and diversity tracking fields into their systems.

In AOE's using advanced analytics, the approach involved combining automated analysis with manual validation to mitigate biases and improve the thematic accuracy of data collected from social networks.

When technical challenges emerged, the focus was placed on adaptation to delivery functional outcomes. In other cases, when funding was withdrawn or support reduced, teams demonstrated resilience by pivoting and continuing objectives using different available resources, settings, and collaborations.

2. Improving Stakeholder Engagement and Accessibility

To accommodate participant time management issues, network sessions were held using different formats (hybrid, lunch break, after-work) and the creation of websites and online resources ensured content was available to those who could not attend live meetings.

3. Maximising Enablers: Leveraging Support, Tools, and Momentum

The success of the actions was frequently amplified by leveraging internal and external support. The provision of **GILL**'s structured tools and frameworks was reported as a major enabler for AOE's, turning abstract concepts of inclusion into practical, repeatable processes that were easier for colleagues new to gender analysis to adopt. They also provided tangible evidence.

The Living Lab approach which was consistently used in the project was perceived by AOE's as another enabler for them to incorporate diverse stakeholder feedback and validate new methods and products.

Strong commitment from leadership to create organisational change priorities inclusion despite barriers was critical for experimenting and reflecting on new methods. The alignment of **GILL**'s work with policies, such as with Horizon Europe's gender equality mandate, with other Horizon Projects, or external funding from other national and regional bodies around gender equality was helpful for AOE's.

The involvement and support of citizens, local role models, companies, was crucial. Local role models were willing to invest time to mentor and share resources with network participants, leadership of partner organisations was committed to equality and incorporation of GRSIE, and the enthusiasm of participating companies and entrepreneurs was essential. Furthermore, some teams secured strategic mentoring or funding through external grants to support the commercialisation and long-term sustainability of new products.

Factors for impact

As part of the impact workshop held with all **GILL** partners, one of the questions we asked was concerned with the factors they considered contributed to the impact achieved, either low or high, for each one of the activities and outcomes they created for as part of the project. Factors like compatibility with stakeholders' ambitions, the effort needed, the size of the challenge proposed, the articulation of the messages to stakeholders and other agents, the timing of the activity or intervention, the overall priority of gender innovation, the compatibility with stakeholders' and

participants' business goals, the perceived cost of the intervention, and the noise around the messages that could make the activity get lost.

Figure 11. Average scoring of relevance of factors for impact.

All these factors were rated by partners as important, although there are not great differences among them. The factors which had a higher effect on the impact they achieved are the compatibility with stakeholder's ambitions, the effort needed, and the size of the challenge. Often, partners discussed that the challenges they faced require years of impactful interventions to produce changes, and as such, they considered it a very important factor on their own impact. Interestingly, partners considered that the alignment with the ambitions of stakeholders had a bigger effect on their impact achieved than the cost of the intervention proposed, or the compatibility with business goals. However, the differences between factors are small.

Partners completed pre-activities and follow up actions to maximise the impact of their outcomes. For activities that have achieved high impact during the project, the preparatory tasks are usually focused on stakeholders, and they are strategic to ensure it has as much impact as possible. Some practical examples are dissemination campaigns, creating gender disaggregated-data collections, setting up working groups, etc. Similarly, follow-up actions were robust, including creation of new databases, providing continuous support, or setting equality goals stemming from the activity.

In the case of the activities that achieved a medium level impact, preparatory tasks were more exploratory, including planning of workshops, raising awareness before an intervention or event, studying KPIs, researching a specific theme, like AI biases. For the fewer interventions that had a low impact, the preparatory tasks were outreach based: emails, informative sessions, introductions, etc. Similarly, follow-ups were mostly emails and information sessions.

Regarding interventions that will produce impact after the lifespan of the project, higher impact interventions focus on systemic change: building networks, producing knowledge, and embedding

inclusion in innovation practices. Follow-up activities are concrete: publishing recommendations or results, producing guides, sustaining networks, targeting funding. Medium impact interventions focus on supporting infrastructure: visibility, dissemination, mentoring, and scaling existing models and follow-up activities to maximise impact are more exploratory or ongoing: monitoring data, offering continuous support, meetings.

Table 23. *Preparatory & Follow-Up Actions by Impact Level (Impact During Project)*

Impact Level	Preparatory Tasks	Follow-up- Actions
High Impact	Strategic stakeholder focus: dissemination campaigns, gender disaggregated- data collection, creation of working groups.	Robust: creation of databases, continuous support, setting equality goals
Medium Impact	Exploratory: planning workshops, raising awareness, studying KPIs, researching themes (e.g., AI bias).	Ongoing: monitoring data, offering support, meetings
Low Impact	Outreach: emails, information sessions, introductions.	Outreach: emails and information sessions

Table 24. *Preparatory & Follow Up Actions by Impact Level (Impact Beyond Project Lifespan)*

Impact Level	Focus	Follow-up- Actions
High Impact	Systemic change: building networks, producing knowledge, embedding inclusion in innovation practices	Concrete: publishing recommendations/results, producing guides, sustaining networks, creating working groups, targeting funding
Medium Impact	Supporting infrastructure: visibility, dissemination, mentoring, scaling existing models	Exploratory/ongoing: monitoring data, continuous support, meetings

6 Recommendations

This section includes recommendations relating to not only gender inequality and how to build on the impact of the project, but also other issues related to the Horizon Europe and framework projects related to the broad fields of impact and evaluation in terms of proposal submission and project management.

6.1 Recommendations concerning maximising the impact of GILL in the future

6.1.1 E01: Advances in Knowledge and Practice

As mentioned in Section 2.4.4, ensuring the work of **GILL** advances UN SDGs, the research has to be accessible and useful in different contexts. We have shown the need for a cultural fix to supplement the earlier 3 fixes and provided a set of GRSIE tools and methods that can be used singly to make small changes or in concert with the development of inclusive Gender Action Plans. However, such changes are hard to accomplish in RI&E even when there is a strong will to change. Knowledge transfer may be possible when compared with context-aware, empathic co-creation e.g. through working with LLs in LMICs to develop GRSIE tools and methods appropriate to current problems. LMIC LLs could then become gender fair Open Innovation Ecosystems and lead by example.

6.1.2 E02: Strengthening innovation and inclusiveness in ERA

1. Within the ERA certain groups of women in RI&E are still ignored, even though one third of business in the EU are started by women¹². The needs of, for example older entrepreneurs and women from migrant backgrounds has been ignored. This is problematic in so far as
 - their needs are not met (e.g. because of lack of knowledge or discriminatory practices, e.g., in relation to financial support, appearance, stereotypes around competence) and they are denied opportunities to fulfil their ambitions. Solutions could be a mix of ring-fenced support, quotas, better training and support of RIE support staff, and a more nuanced understanding of the effects of intersectionality on the ways in which support is provided.
 - Using traditional and stereotypical models of what constitutes successful RI&E may no longer be appropriate, and new models/ways of doing business are not given an opportunity to show their value. For example, social enterprise businesses can be denied support because they are judged against the same criteria as high-tech companies in funding applications. It is time to adjust the metrics. This feeds into gender inequality because women tend to need lower levels of support for less high tech, and more socially oriented businesses that are more intrinsically motivated.

A better understanding of modern entrepreneurship is needed across the EU in order to provide the right support mechanisms, or the right groups at the right time.

2. Helping women entrepreneurs to find networks, peer support and mentorship are key priorities. In **GILL**, AOE1 in particular, found that these are hard to establish and sustain, even though being able to talk and share problems with like-minded strangers was seen as beneficial. Of key importance were holding the meetings in a safe space (i.e. outside the university), face-to-face

¹² [Gender distribution of early-stage entrepreneurs in Europe by country 2021 | Statista](#) & Eurostat via Macrobond

and at convenient times (avoiding school runs). The format of the Coventry university network was modelled loosely on the intersectionality research salon pioneered by the [Intersectionality Training Institute](#) with a short presentation by a local speaker on her business journey or key skills (e.g. tackling imposter syndrome) time for chats and knowledge transfer. This is a replicable model, which could be supported by a university or LL. It is resource light but requires energy and commitment of the organisers.

3. Collation and improvement of the quality of data from TTO. Despite best efforts across the project, TTO (or their equivalents) seemed to be unwilling to share data on the support they offered to academics who wished to start their own businesses or valorise their research, this is despite success rates of patent applications and spin outs featuring prominently on some university websites. The recommendation here is a requirement for publicly funded universities to provide sex and discipline disaggregated data on queries from staff regarding commercialisation of research, and the way these progressed.

6.2 Recommendations to maintain the sustainability and usefulness of the GILL hub

The **GILL** hub encapsulates key outcomes of the **GILL** project. To be more than a legacy document a series of actions need to be performed after the project. These are summarised in the following figure and below

Figure 12. Actions needed to sustain the longevity of the **GILL** hub

Other actions include

1. Increase the number, diversity and relevance of mentors and case studies.
2. Provide better support for mentors and case study organisations. It was mentioned on a number of occasions that there is a limited pool from which mentors are drawn and they can become burnt out.

3. Wide promotion of methods and resources within ENOLL, e.g. through CB, requirement for gender competency or a Gender Action Plan for ENOLL and its LLS, mentorship, populating the GILL network with information from the ENOLL network map.
4. GILL partners deliver on their post project plans as articulated in the Impact workshop and Individual Exploitation Plans.
5. Work with EU policy officers to ensure that GILL resources are referred to in future proposals
6. Increase usability and visibility of the discussion forum
7. Lobby for a COST action or equivalent that would maximise the legacy and potential for future work in gender research in EU, using the platform as a one-stop shop for information,
8. The wider application of GRSIE tools areas outside of EU, e.g. to support UNSDG 5 needs further research. Our tools to support ground up activities to address, amongst other things cultural barriers in the workplace, could be useful in other contexts. However, even within EU, a comment was made that we have provided the tools but no guidance on how these can be used if there is an extreme gender imbalance, when men have all the power and are hostile to change. Co-creation work with NGOs and non-European LLS committed to gender equality and women's entrepreneurship might be a starting point here.

6.3 Recommendations related to maximising the potential of EU team diversity through gender aware management.

Achieving team diversity and gender equality in R&I is a key goal of EU policy. It is considered to be advantageous, but the impact can be hard to valorise (Pinheiro et al, 2024). Their detailed multivariate analysis of the impact of gender composition in EU research teams on patent and policy-related documents in science revealed a complicated picture with outcomes influenced by team size, number of authors, seniority, discipline etc. Results included that in scientific publications, the share of publications cited by policy increases as the participation of women increases in health; in sciences in general and in research related to SDG13 and AI that the uptake in patents decreases with greater numbers of women co-authors of publication.

Additionally, no clear relationship has been found between diversity and performance (2022) even though diverse teams (particularly those with women) have better problem solving and creative skills, resulting in more innovative and successful businesses (e.g. Dai et al (2018); Garba and Kraemer-Mbula (2018). In terms of R&I, research (e.g. Nielsen et al (2018); Yang et al (2022) has found that gender diversity in a team can facilitate scientific discovery. The management of (gender) diverse teams in ways which bring out the potential of all members through collaboration and respect can be difficult (e.g. Roh and Koo, 2019) with problems (Ngonyama-Ndou and Makola, 2025) relating to conflict, cohesion and strategic alignment, communication styles, unconscious bias, stereotyping, discrimination role allocation and flexible working.

In relation to Pinheiro et al 's recommendations, we believe that useful insights into gender issues arising through the course of **GILL** (as an example of a project with gender, geographic and disciplinary diversity) can offer key recommendations into the management of future EU projects to ensure that gender equality is achieved in the operationalisation of the project, not just in terms of quantifiable measures such as the ratio of female to male researchers and their seniority. The recommendations will also ensure that **GILL**'s legacy is transmitted through ERA.

1. **Initial audit of researcher's gender competence.** For convenience, **GILL** adopted the University of Toronto's gender competence tool, others may be more appropriate. This was

selected because it provided direct, bespoke feedback to those using it, on issues relevant to the project (see Annex 3). A team score was also used to identify areas of weakness across the consortium

2. **Barriers to gender and inclusion in everyday practices.** A gender competency workshop was designed to get people talking about barriers to gender equality through scenario-based learning and the development of gender action plans. It is recommended that such workshops are conducted across research projects after 6 months to address any barriers to gender equality that may be arising in the team
3. **Increasing the inclusiveness of team culture.** Following from 2) , **GILL** has developed practical tools and methods which can be employed within projects to ensure equality and fairness e.g in meetings, work allocation, collecting gender sensitive data.

6.4 Recommendations related to impact evaluation (in proposals)

Impact is commonly measured in terms of the lowest common denominator, i.e. the number of project outputs; number of people attending webinars; KPIs which measure quantifiable change in the short term. It has been widely recognised in the run up to FP10 that key elements in proposals are not sufficiently addressed, such as gender. KPIs and quantitative measures may be convenient, but they are not always the best tools to address progress towards the solution of ‘wicked’ problems with many confounding variables, or the sustainability of impact after the project. They may also privilege one type of testimony or ‘reporter’ over others leading to epistemic injustice.

The use of process and output-oriented impact measures neglect the impact a project has on its members. This should be of key concern to the ERA in its ambitions to increase knowledge and practice fairly within the community. Peer reviewed publications, whilst increasing academic profiles only indirectly measure internal growth and capacity. What has a partner learnt by being part of the project, that they can take with them, how will their experiences contribute (in this case) to a more gender equitable ERA.

R&I projects need to encourage and provide space for reflection in, on and through practice (Frayling, 1993) in their busy workplans with partners being encouraged to think more widely about their role in the project, what has worked well, the direct and indirect impacts on them and the wider research community to which they belong.

We have trialled a more reflective and nuanced approach within **GILL**, through our narrative impact case studies, reflective journals, and the adaptation of the gender competency self-assessment tool. The support of partners for this approach has been mixed, with very little enthusiasm to build impact analysis into project activities from the start, use templates provided or work to agreed guidelines. A combination of factors appears to contribute to this reluctance – such as gender, nationality, discipline, timing of activity – even when a scientific explanation is presented for the need for the work e.g. baseline line assessment to measure impact. Our solutions have included provision of templates, impact workshops, email reminders, naming of noncompliant partners, and one-to one meetings.

Of the non-compulsory methods we used, reflective journals were most successful, leading to their inclusion as a GRSIE method; templates worked in some cases but were seen as ‘busy work’ especially when they required duplication of information and constant need to update them. The reflective practice did not require a lot of extra resources to implement, and it showed clear impact on partners’ awareness of inequalities and team dynamics in the unfolding of the project.

6.4.1 In research application process

Key recommendations:

1. Design of research proposal form. Additional guidelines and information should be provided on sections relate to impact, gender, complimentary, ethics and makeup of the consortium, to demonstrate wider benefits of the project to the ERA and project beneficiaries
2. Recognition of Continual Professional Development (CPD) of researchers as a recognised outcome and its impact potential in R&I projects
3. Greater use of narrative CVS
4. Wider support and integration of qualitative and reflective studies in R&I to address epistemic injustice.
5. There is a general tendency for projects to be over ambitious n the claims they make, to need to quantify the unquantifiable and make claims that are hard to substantiate, against sometimes inappropriate KPIs in the face of variables and external factors they can't control. More help and guidance are needed in the submission process with a clearer message regarding the scale of impact and how it will be assessed
6. Further research needs to be undertaken on the operationalisation of impact pathways so that these can be better specified in proposals.

6.5 Recommendations to maximise impact of extremely diverse, and fragmented project

1. Don't lose site of the whole (Gestalt) with continual reinforcement of where each part of the project fits into the wider picture.
2. Set up a matrix of purposive communication pathways, each being of equal value, i.e., not reporting just for the sake of reporting -which enables researchers in different parts of the project to talk to each other.
3. Allow sufficient time for meaningful face to face meetings within the project to build up knowledge, trust and explore synergies and collaboration

7 Summary conclusions

Strengthening human capital and skills for inclusive R&I

GILL contributes to Horizon Europe's objective of strengthening human capital by equipping researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, civil servants, and citizens with practical skills and competences to address gender inequalities in R&I. Across the AOE, participants developed applied capacities in gender analysis, inclusive design, data literacy, reflexive practice, and co-creation. These skills enable stakeholders to integrate gender considerations throughout the R&I lifecycle, contributing to more robust research outcomes and widening participation in innovation and entrepreneurship, particularly among women and under-represented groups.

Transforming organisations and innovation ecosystems

The project delivers impact at organisational and systemic levels by supporting structural and cultural change within R&I-performing and R&I-supporting organisations. AOE led to the revision of internal procedures, governance models, communication practices, and innovation pathways, embedding gender equality into everyday decision-making rather than isolating it in standalone actions. This directly supports Horizon Europe's ambition to move from individual-level interventions to **institutional change for gender equality**.

Improving the quality and inclusiveness of research and innovation

By integrating gender-disaggregated and intersectional data into research design, problem framing, and evaluation, GILL enhances the scientific excellence and societal relevance of R&I activities. The AOE demonstrate that gender-responsive methodologies reduce bias, reveal previously overlooked needs, and lead to innovation solutions that better reflect diverse users and markets. This aligns with Horizon Europe's objective to improve R&I quality by systematically considering sex, gender, and diversity variables where relevant.

Delivering transferable tools and scalable solutions

GILL contributes to Horizon Europe's impact pathways by developing and validating transferable, open, and scalable tools and methods for gender-responsive innovation. These include digital platforms, training resources, participatory methods, organisational reflection tools, and guidelines for gender innovation in entrepreneurship and research. The demonstrated uptake of these resources beyond the project, and their adaptability across sectors and regions, underpins their potential for **replication and long-term exploitation**.

Supporting evidence-based policymaking and societal impact

Several AOE generated actionable evidence and participatory mechanisms that strengthen the link between R&I and policymaking, particularly in areas such as transport, mobility, public health, and digital governance. By improving how gendered evidence is generated, communicated, and used, GILL supports Horizon Europe's objective to enhance evidence-informed, inclusive policy development and increase citizen trust and engagement in innovation processes.

Contribution to EU Gender Equality and Innovation Policy Objectives

Overall, GILL contributes directly to:

- Horizon Europe’s cross-cutting gender equality needs, by providing concrete methodologies for implementation across R&I contexts;
- The EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025, by addressing structural barriers, participation gaps, and gender bias in innovation systems;
- Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area (WIDERA) objectives, through inclusive methods, capacity building, and institutional transformation;
- The EU’s ambition for responsible, inclusive, and sustainable innovation, linking gender equality to innovation performance, social cohesion, and economic opportunity.

By evidencing *how* gender equality can be operationalised within R&I, and *why* this leads to better outcomes, GILL provides a strong, practice-based contribution to Horizon Europe’s expected impacts at individual, organisational, and systemic levels.

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Annex 1: Summary of needs, results, E, D and C measures, target groups, outcome and impacts proposed in the DoA.

Annex 2 Results for Self-Assessment Competency

Analysis based on sample size of N=13 for start of project N=13, and N=11 for end of project.

Matched pairs analysis was not possible. All scores have been converted into %s for ease of comparison

Key: ↔ no change; ↑ improvement on baseline; ↓ decrease since base line; ↑↑ over double score

Section 1: The 5 Ws

1.1 Understand key concepts related to gender

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Understands key terms used in gender analysis	100	100	↔	Interrogates own privilege and how it may impact the gender analysis process	76.9	81.8	↑	Helps others understand gender concepts and how to apply them	61.5	81.8	↑
Recognizes differentiation between sex and gender	100	100	↔	Consciously works to challenge gender stereotypes	84.6	72.7	↓	Advances discussion of gender issues within the organization	61.5	63.6	↑
Understands the spectrum of gender identity and respects the diverse ways in which people identify themselves	100	100	↔					Uses their position as an expert to encourage thoughtful dialogue about gender equity, inclusion, and intersectionality	53.8	63.6	↑
Understands concepts of privilege and gender stereotypes	100	100	↔								

Understands how gender dynamics can create differing outcomes for different people	92.3	100	↑								
Overall mean score for skill levels	98.5	100	↑		80.8	77.3	↓		59	69.7	↑

1.2 Understand how intersectionality impacts outcomes

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Demonstrates awareness of the concept of intersectionality and the importance of using an intersectional lens	92.3	100	↑	Demonstrates nuanced understanding of the concept of intersecting identities	53.8	90.9	↑	Facilitates reflective discussion about intersectionality and layered oppression with an ability to manage emotional and challenging conversations about discrimination, privilege and biases	30.8	54.5	↑
Understands how individuals with varied identities would be impacted differently by products, services, processes or policies	100	100	↔	Seeks out viewpoints of people with intersecting identities to speak to their lived experience	69.2	81.81	↑	Promotes an inclusive environment that reflects the intersectionality of the team and of the beneficiaries or customers	69.2	63.6	↓
Understands own privilege in comparison to other intersecting identities	100	100	↔	Understands how social power can be and has been used by institutions to marginalize particular	84.6	90.9	↑	Leads through actions, validating the experiences of those with overlapping or intersecting identities	30.8	45.5	↑
he principles behind key frameworks such as the Human Rights, Rights of Indigenous	84.6	90.9	↑					Influences others to use empathy when exploring others' lived experiences	69.2	45.5	↓

Overall mean score for skill levels	94.2	97.7	↑		69.2	87.8	↑		50	50.3	↑
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1.3 Understands the benefits of gender analysis

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Understands the legal requirements for ensuring equitable impact for beneficiaries or customers	76.9	81.8	↑	Explains what benefits are most relevant for own organization when proposing or implementing a gender analysis	76.9	90.9	↑	Adapts articulation of benefits to address different audiences or different needs at different points in time	61.5	72.7	↑
Understands the social and economic benefits of ensuring equitable impact for beneficiaries	100	100	↔	Understands and can convey why the organization should apply an intersectional gender lens	84.6	72.7	↓	Effectively communicates and advocates for gender analysis within the organization	53.8	72.7	↑
Overall mean score for skill levels	88.5	90.9	↑		80.8	81.8	↑		57.7	72.7	↑

1.4 Where and when: See opportunities for gender analysis

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Understands how systemic issues of inequity impact	92.3	100	↑	Identifies ways that gendered assumptions may impact design and development of	76.9	81.8	↑	Identifies areas within products, services, processes and policies	53.8	63.6	↑

products, services, processes and policies				products, services, processes and policies				where gender analysis may have the highest impact			
Sees that some “gender neutral” domains may actually have gendered outcomes	76.9	100	↑	Recognizes gender stereotypes, biases and assumptions underlying the design of products, services, processes and policies	84.6	90.9	↑				
Scans for opportunities for gender analysis	69.2	63.6	↓								
Overall mean score for skill levels	79.5	87.9	↑		80.8	86.4	↑		53.8	63.6	↑

1.5 Determine who in the organization should be involved in gender analysis

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Identifies people across departments who have resources needed for gender analysis	69.2	81.1	↑	Enables effective cross-departmental and external data collection for gender analysis	53.8	90.9	↑	Ensures leadership buy-in to the gender analysis process	30.8	45.5	↑
Seeks support from leaders, engaging them throughout the gender analysis process	76.9	90.9	↑	Supports gender analysis “champions” in other departments, areas and organizations	61.5	54.5	↓	Can troubleshoot issues arising from cross-departmental collaborations	30.8	63.6	↑↑
Understands and can access external resources for gender analysis	69.2	90.9	↑	Understands effective collaboration practices for cross-departmental work	92.3	81.1	↓	Ensures organizational capacity and structures are in place for collaborations	23.1	72.7	↑↑
Overall mean score for skill levels	71.8	87.8	↑		69.2	75.8	↑		28.2	60.6	↑↑

Section 2 :Applying Gender Analysis

2.1 Clarify problem statement

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Explores unexamined biases or assumptions underlying initial problem statements	69.2	81.8	↑	Reframes the problem statement iteratively with insights from quantitative and qualitative data collection from the eyes of intended customers or beneficiaries	53.8	81.8	↑	Challenges self and project team to abandon existing assumptions and solutions	46.2	81.8	↑
Examines why current solutions, if they exist, have failed or are inadequate from the perspectives of	84.6	100	↑					Continuously pushes self and team to focus on customer- or beneficiary-centric insights	30.8	54.5	↑
Overall mean score for skill levels	76.9	90.9	↑		53.8	81.8	↑		38.5	84.6	↑↑

2.2 Collect qualitative data ethically

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Understands how qualitative, community-based research can contribute to problem finding and problem solving	92.3	100	↑	Ensures a diversity of customers or beneficiaries is represented, prioritizing an intersectional lens	76.9	81.8	↑	Manages the complete qualitative data collection process, from designing research questions, choosing the most effective collection methods to ensuring best practices in execution	69.2	72.7	↑

Understands the use of a variety of participatory data collection methods, including interviews, focus groups, and ethnographic methods	84.6	100	↑	Recognizes factors that may influence data collection dynamics and results, including but not limited to indigeneity, education, literacy level, gender, lifestyle, immigrant status, differences in ability, socioeconomic status, race, familial status and age	76.9	100	↑	Takes responsibility for the ethical considerations in participatory data collection methods	69.2	72.7	↑
Bases data collection on building empathy for the target audiences	69.2	81.8	↑	Mitigates psychological, reputational or other risks to research participants	61.5	81.8	↑				
Protects confidentiality of vulnerable participants	92.3	100	↑	Questions how own bias may impact the way in which data is collected	84.6	81.8	↓				
Appropriately compensates users, beneficiaries and other external stakeholders for participating in data collection/design process	76.9	100	↑								
Uses emerging insights to inform the evolution of the problem statement	92.3	100	↑								
Overall mean score for skill levels	84.6	97	↑		75	86.4	↑		69.2	72.7	↑

2.3 Collect gender-disaggregated quantitative data ethically

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Locates internal or external sources of gender-	76.9	90.9	↑	Identifies data gaps and understands how these	61.5	54.5	↓	Designs and executes data collection methods to fill gaps where intersectional	38.5	54.5	↑

disaggregated data on customer or beneficiary needs				will shape analytical outcomes				gender-disaggregated data does not yet exist			
Ensures gender-disaggregated data also accounts for other intersecting identities.	61.5	81.8	↑	Ensures a diversity of customers or beneficiaries is represented, prioritizing an intersectional lens	61.5	72.7	↑	Develops partnerships aimed at filling data gaps	38.5	63.6	↑
Ensures integrity and representativeness of data	76.9	72.7	↓	Recognizes factors that may influence data collection dynamics and results, including but not	69.2	81.8	↑	Takes responsibility for the ethical considerations in quantitative data collection, storage and use	61.5	54.5	↓
Uses ethical principles for collecting, storing and analyzing data to protect the privacy and safety of vulnerable populations	84.6	90.9	↑	Questions how own bias may impact the way in which data is collected	76.9	72.7	↓				
Uses emerging insights to inform the evolution of the problem statement	76.9	72.7	↓								
Overall mean score for skill levels	75.4	81.8	↑		67.3	70.5	↑		46.2	57.6	↑

2.4 Generate integrative insights

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Gives weight to both quantitative and qualitative data in synthesizing evidence into insights	100	90.9	↓	Engages in and encourages divergent thinking	61.5	100	↑	Develops conceptual frameworks to guide gender analysis	38.5	54.5	↑

Collaborates with stakeholders in sensemaking about the different data inputs	61.5	100	↑	Creates visual tools, such as persona and journey map, to communicate insights with stakeholder	69.2	72.7	↑	Evaluates emerging findings against previous data to ensure validity of insights	46.2	63.6	↑
Searches beyond obvious patterns to understand the underlying drivers, motivations and tensions	76.9	100	↑					Looks for conflicting or contrasting data and develops insights that explain them	53.8	63.6	↑
Allows the data to “speak” rather than imposing pre-dispositions on the data	76.9	100	↑								
Uses emerging insights to inform the evolution of the problem statement	69.2	90.9	↑								
Overall mean score for skill levels	76.9	96.4	↑		65.4	86.4	↑		46.2	60.6	↑

2.5 Design for equity

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Applies insights from qualitative and quantitative data to the product, service, process or policy design	84.6	100	↑	Identifies the implications and potential impact of inclusive design options (political, economic, legal, social)	53.8	81.8	↑	Uses a structured design process to encourage creativity and generate a diversity of ideas	46.2	63.6	↑
Integrates the design process iteratively with the data collection and integration process	76.9	100	↑	Assesses the feasibility and expected outcomes of the proposed gender-inclusive design	53.8	81.8	↑	Pushes for game-changing designs based on the data insights	15.4	54.5	↑↑

Engages customers, users, beneficiaries, and other stakeholders in co-creation	69.2	90.9	↑					Identifies roadblocks to implementation of design and leads effort to remove them or design around them	38.5	18.2	↓↓
Overall mean score for skill levels	76.9	97	↑		53.8	81.8	↑		33.3	45.5	↑

2.6 Rapid prototyping

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Uses simple and quick ways to model or visualize designed solutions	84.6	72.7	↓	Considers limitations of prototypes and testing methods and how they affect testing results	69.2	63.6	↓	Identifies or designs cheap and simple prototyping approaches	46.2	54.5	↑
Engages with target customers, users or beneficiaries to test prototypes and collects feedback	84.6	72.7	↓	Ensures intersectional diversity in customers, users or beneficiaries for testing	53.8	72.7	↑	Asks critical “devil’s advocate” questions to enhance design of product, service, process or policy	53.9	45.5	↓
Uses feedback to revise and improve the design	84.6	81.8	↓	Critically analyzes negative feedback to identify fundamental faults of the design that cause	84.6	72.7	↓				
Overall mean score for skill levels	84.6	75.8	↓		69.2	69.7	↑		50	50	↔

2.7 Equitable resource allocation

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
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Understands relevant organizational processes for budgeting, stakeholder alignment and resource allocation	76.9	90.9	↑	Collaborates across departments to ensure resource requirements are being incorporated into planning, activities and reporting	46.154	72.727	↑	Allocates sufficient resources (including finances, capacity building and infrastructure) to enable design implementation	23.1	45.5	↑
Identifies impact of design solutions (product, service, process or policy) on budgets and other resource allocation	61.5	81.8	↑	Identifies potential risks of inclusive design, and budgets for the ability to re-design and adapt	53.846	90.909	↑	Offers critical analysis of budget proposals across the organization to ensure resource allocation informed by gender analysis	30.8	36.4	↑
Overall mean score for skill levels	69.231	86.364	↑		50	81.8	↑		26.9	40.9	↑

2.8 Assessing impact

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Uses established or new metrics to assess the impact of the product, service, process or policy on customers or beneficiaries	53.8	81.1	↑	Develops intersectional gender metrics for impact assessment where appropriate metrics do not exist	38.7	54.5	↑	Builds impact assessment into the design process	38.5	63.6	↑
Uses both qualitative and quantitative metrics for impact	84.6	100	↑	Analyzes both the intended and unintended consequences or impacts of the product, service, process or policy	61.5	72.7	↑	Anticipates unintended consequences and inequities created by product, service, process or policy	38.5	36.3	↓
Engages directly with customers, users or beneficiaries to identify impacts	69.2	100	↑								

Overall mean score for skill levels	69.2	93.9	↑		50	63.6	↑		38.5	50	↑
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2.9 Sustainable adaptation

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Uses insights from impact assessment to iterate on product, service, process or policy design	61.5	100	↑	Engages with beneficiaries, users, customers, and other stakeholders to make course corrections as needed to enhance or improve the delivery or design of the product, service, process or policy	46.154	90.9	↑	Identifies new opportunities (e.g., beneficiaries, collaborators, extensions) to improve product, service, process or policy over time	46.154	81.8	↑
Returns to previous quantitative and qualitative data analysis to compare the validity of the hypotheses and redesign based on new insights	69.2	100	↑	Tracks “lessons learned” from the design and implementation experience to improve design processes in the future	61.538	100	↑	Disseminates gender analysis learnings (including gaps, success and opportunities)	38.462	81.8	↑↑
Overall mean score for skill levels	65.4	100	↑		53.8	95.5	↑		42.3	81.8	↑

Section 3: Organizational and Cultural Support

3.1 Effective collaboration

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Identifies and supports opportunities for collaboration between departments in the organization	76.9	100	↑	Encourages cross-functional/departmental teams to work on gender analysis and inclusive design processes	46.1	81.8	↑	Identifies and breaks down barriers to collaborative processes in the organization	38.462	54.5	↑
Shares all equity-related relevant information and seeks other's input	61.5	90.9		Supports others in acting to increase equity	76.9	81.8	↑	Organizes teams that reflect the diversity of stakeholders	30.769	54.5	↑
Acknowledges other frames of reference and others lived experiences, learning how to gain diverse	76.9	100	↑	Invites and builds upon the ideas of others in various parts of the organization	46.1	90.9	↑	Encourages individuals with different lived experience to contribute to design process	53.846	81.8	↑
				Facilitates knowledge and capacity building of staff engaging in the gender analysis process	61.5	81.8	↑	Arbitrates opposing points of view and stakeholder conflicts	30.769	45.5	↑
Overall mean score for skill levels	71.8	96.9	↑		57.7	84	↑		38.5	59	↑

3.2 Fostering organizational change

Basic skill	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Intermediate skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact	Advanced skills	Start of project mean score	End of project mean score	Direction of impact
Recognizes the value and importance of organizational and team commitment to gender analysis	92.3	100	↑	Applies an intersectional gender lens to organizational practices	46.154	72.7	↑	Leads by example and fosters an organizational culture that values and embeds a gender lens in all areas of work	38.5	63.6	↑
Challenges assumptions, stereotypes, and gender structures in existing practices	84.6	90.9	↑	Creates safe spaces where people feel comfortable expressing how they feel and having difficult conversations	53.8	90.9	↑	Breaks down barriers to the gender analysis process using knowledge, empathy, and evidence	30.8	72.7	↑↑
Advocates for gender analysis, provides leadership support and offers solutions when issues arise	61.5	81.8	↑	Builds technical capacity of team to facilitate and carry out a gender analysis process	23.1	45.5	↑	Embeds gender analysis processes in all areas of work in the organization	15.4	45.5	↑↑
				Advises on accountability practices and communications plan related to gender analysis	23.1	54.5	↑↑	Strengthens the implementation of gender analysis through ongoing evaluation and learning, and sharing of effective practices	23.1	63.6	↑↑
Overall mean score for skill levels	79.5	90.9	↑		36.5	65.9	↑		26.9	61.4	↑↑

Annex 3. AOE Impact Stories

AOE1: Open Innovation Platform for Gender Responsive Collaborative Innovation	
<p>Challenge: Working with citizen scientists and entrepreneurs looking to develop their ideas, a recurring theme emerged about the difficulty of taking ideas forward in a way that professional services would understand, be able to respond to and to give the idea its due respect.</p> <p>AOE: A design brief generator (DBG) has been created to provide opportunities to easily create design briefs out of identified needs, alongside a platform to developed and sharing GRSI ‘design provocations’ as a means of communicating and developing ideas across the project, with citizens and design students.</p> <p>Goals: To democratise design and the potential of gender responsive innovation to solve everyday problems.</p> <p>Impact:</p> <p>A Design Brief is a document that explains the story of an idea and typically lists the core requirements, such as user groups or material choice. There are often so many options that is difficult to know where to start. This is why we have constructed the DBG as a form, with selectable options. By clicking through these options, a wider story starts to emerge. This is the optimum way we have observed for users to prepare such a useful document. This has taken the form of a narrative communication tool, not technical specification which appears to make it easier to understand and to use.</p> <p>As experience/practice of writing a design brief may be limited, through the GILL hub we have developed a semi-automated design brief generator. This is form based and has been tested by multiple partners of the GILL project to ensure accessibility and sense checking. The form format has been split into two themes: Health and Transport.</p> <p>Creating a design brief with the DBG is quick and easy. We will post the design briefs on the TInnGO Open Innovation Platform (OIP); a creative forum to share knowledge and insight. We have previously developed this OIP and are able to continue to use its functions, rather than develop the same again, thus making efficient use of the existing time and investment. This is where we plan to share democratically developed design briefs and resulting design solutions. The OIP will show the Design Brief which can then be discussed, developed and become the source of a design challenge, all in the OIP.</p> <p>Participants have already contributed to the narrative forms and we have begun to add concept ideas to the OIP. It is an open-ended method that will continue to be used.</p>	
Key objectives	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations
Horizontal theme	Individual and Team, Innovation and Product
Vertical theme	Green transition???
Pathway	2a: Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA: Individuals
Stakeholder groups proposed	University staff, students and citizens (20 students and project members; 20 citizens)
Next Steps after GILL	The DBG is live and operating normally. The access to the TInnGO OIP could be smoothed out but as a proof of concept, it works well.

	<p>To continue to do so will need further signposting and encouragement of users to access, contribute to the discussion and expand the DBG usage.</p> <p>Even though the formal project is concluding soon, I do intend to progress the idea of the Design Brief Generator since this could form a vital tool to bridge the communication gap between innovative thinkers and the design/development/investment community</p>
Barriers to Impact	<p>We've encountered some technical challenges in collaborating with project partners to develop the interaction method for the AOE online, as well as in the lead-up to the overall OIP and the use of the DBG. While a workable solution has been achieved, it is sub-optimal in terms of user experience.</p> <p>Communicating and making technical partners understand the method we were trying to establish was challenging. In the end, the focus was on delivering a functional outcome, rather than exploring enhancements to achieve something that would be better than functional.</p>
Enablers to Impact	<p>Accepting that there was reluctance for users to adopt professional interaction methods meant that we could move on to one that was based on solo user interaction and thus address concerns about communication. This was similar to accepting that the younger design community did not engage at the beginning of phase 1. Coming to terms with this was helped by the local leadership at CU and the discussion meetings we have internally for the project to be shared and problems considered.</p> <p>By then moving our discussion out of the existing grouping of designers and people with a need for designed solution, into the expert citizen/entrepreneur the message about communication became clearer and we were then able to assemble an alternative, interactive method, that addressed professional communication in a different way and provided a bridge to overcome that barrier.</p>
Concrete Actions	<p>We have pushed for comms support in a manner that users would interact with and relate to, mostly using social media. This has been provided and was an effective introduction for external participants. This method also helped for the methodology to be grounded in something that was more than a hidden research project helping to give another angle to democratising the method, which has been a core value of AOE1 since the start of the project. Stronger comms messages would have been even more effective.</p>

AOE2: Brick by Brick: Supporting Women in Academia in Their Spinout/Business Journey¹²

Challenge: Although extensive opportunities are offered by universities to support academics commercialising their research or developing patents/starts ups, these are not widely taken up.

Goals: Support the needs of pre-start female academic entrepreneurs in a sustainable way.

AOE: During the first cycle, we conducted semi-structured interviews with university E&I and administrative staff, as well as with (predominantly male) academics who are running successful spinouts. We organised a workshop with an innovative, participatory methodology which we called Brick by Brick, and which was based on LEGO® Serious Play®. Bottom-up data collected at this workshop led us to a redefinition of the original problem. Women academics from West Midlands universities who attended our problem-centred Brick by Brick workshop expressed an interest in starting a business, but not necessarily spinouts. Their main motivation was not to commercialise their research, but to start and run businesses as an activity parallel/supplementarily to academic careers. Consequently, using GRSIE methods, we identified ‘user needs’ of our main target group, which was women at West Midlands universities who are interested in starting and running their own business. We created an official (branded) network with regular meetings to generate information and a website to collect and showcase all the resources and materials shared by local role models in the sessions based on the identified ‘user needs’.

Impact:

We created the Salon Series, designed to meet user needs, primarily addressing soft components: the domains of education, training and mentoring which encourage and educate prospective entrepreneurs. We could not therefore guarantee that every participant of AOE activities will automatically become a ‘successful business owner’ by the end of the last iterative cycle, nor that we have a visible impact on a quantitative elevation of business or spinout activities in the West Midlands. But, we achieved the following:

- Creation of a new network for women in academia interested in entrepreneurship with over 50 participants called the Salon Series.
- Delivery of eight Salon Series meetings between January and September, all including a presentation on a different “need” identified: building confidence and beating imposter syndrome; fighting discrimination; becoming a spinout CEO; becoming a small business owner after leaving academia; and other soft skills development sessions related to GDPR and writing a narrative CV.
- Local role models delivered every session, all women entrepreneurs running different types of businesses. Sessions provided the women in the network access to relaxed interaction with role models and between participants, Q&As, further contact and mentoring opportunities.
- Around 6-10 participants per session, with some of them recurring and most new. There was a constant interest in our sessions throughout the series, with participants being engaged and eager to meet each other and the local role model.
- The Salon Series website is a resource we created for the members of the network who could not join the sessions. The narratives of the past Salon Series have been published here, so they are accessible, as well as the resources provided and shared by the role models. We decided, however, not to record any of the sessions. We attached the following disclaimer to the invitation: “As a general rule, this meeting space should be safe, confidential, and fair: whatever we share will stay in this

	group, and everyone will have the chance to share however much they wish to share”.
Key objectives	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies OB/02 To enhance professional development OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations
Horizontal theme	Individual & team; societal
Vertical theme	All
Pathway	1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe
Stakeholder groups proposed	Tech transfer office, Female university staff (26 in first cycle, 25 attendants in second cycle, over 50 participants subscribed to network)
Next Steps	<p>We have linked our network to the Women’s Stuff Network at Coventry University as a step to continue after the end of the project. As next steps, we would like to do the following:</p> <p>Expanding the Salon Series to include sessions (longitudinal presentation/workshop series?) on specific aspects of business development, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial planning and management, • Legal aspects of starting and running a business, • Time management strategies tailored to women in academia and entrepreneurship. <p>Deepening the exploration of systemic barriers, especially around time management, by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigating its structural roots (e.g., patriarchal and capitalist systems), • Developing strategies that go beyond surface-level fixes. <p>Strengthening the online platform (Salon Series website) to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serve as a resource hub for business-related materials, • Facilitate asynchronous engagement for those unable to attend live sessions.
Barriers to Impact	<p>Mobilising the network was challenging. The whole Salon Series was impacted by time management issues, and it was also often mentioned as a problem by participants during both the Brick by Brick and the Salon Series sessions. It seems to be one of the most complex hindrances as part of the academic and/or business journey, and we should continue exploring it in the future, tackling its systemic (patriarchal, capitalist) aspects and develop a strategy to address it not only on the surface but to its core.</p> <p>Lack of resources, institutional changes and restructuring.</p>
Enablers to Impact	Local role models willing to fully engage with the network and invest their time, prepare amazing presentations, share their

	resources, and offer mentoring to some of the participants despite our lack of resources.
Concrete Actions	We considered the time management issues of participants and tried different formats for the network sessions, different time windows, and different engagement strategies. We held the first two Salon Series offline in a non-university-owned, neutral space (coffeeshop), which reflected the user need initially shared with us. Nevertheless, it turned out that whereas women were theoretically interested in the offline meetings, they had practical issues when it came to actually joining them. Therefore, we organised hybrid sessions in campus, sessions during lunch break, sessions after work, surveys to ask for time availability, and remote sessions. We also created the website to make the content of the sessions available to those who could not attend.

AO3: Increasing GRSIE in new medical devices, healthcare tech and tech-dependent intervention

Challenge: Within the UK's health technology innovation ecosystem, gender inequities persist across research participation, leadership, and investment. Female innovators face significant barriers to advancing their ideas, from limited access to funding and networks to unconscious bias in product design and evaluation.

The challenge, therefore, was twofold: to transform D4D's own internal culture and processes, and to build a more equitable external environment for women innovators and communities engaging with health technologies. **AOE:** D4D will incorporate tools and methods developed in **GILL** to improve its user centred approach. 10 'champion health practitioner innovators' will apply and test **GILL** resources during their yearlong health innovation projects.

Goals: To raise awareness of gender health inequalities, change practice and increase gender responsive health related innovations and entrepreneurship.

Impact: The impacts of this AOE have been both organisational and systemic, influencing D4D's internal culture and external collaborations.

Organisational and Cultural Change:

D4D's participation in GILL catalysed a fundamental shift in how equity and inclusion are understood and operationalised. Fair Meetings and Airtime Monitoring data revealed that discussions were often dominated by theme leads, limiting broader participation. By embedding these tools, D4D restructured its meeting practices, rotating facilitators, ensuring agenda balance, and tracking airtime. As a result, internal communication became more inclusive and participatory.

Reflective practice also prompted D4D to re-examine its assumption that a female-dominated team inherently ensured gender-aware outputs. The project demonstrated that awareness must be intentional, evidence-driven, and supported by structured tools.

Changes in Product Design and Innovation Processes:

By applying Gender Mag and Gender Impact Assessment, D4D transformed how inclusivity is considered across digital resources and innovation training. The Fellowship Programme's Moodle platform is being redesigned to balance representation and

<p>challenge implicit bias in content and imagery. Future updates will undergo the same gender review process.</p> <p>Externally, D4D's collaboration pipeline now includes gender-responsive reflection at the assessment stage, ensuring female-led innovations are better supported and understood. The addition of a dedicated Women's Health Theme to D4D's project portfolio has increased the number of female-led projects seeking support.</p>	
Key objectives	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations
Horizontal theme	all
Vertical theme	V1: health and resilience
Pathway	Pathway 1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe 2a. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA - individuals
Stakeholder groups	<p>DVD team, investors, health innovators (19 in second cycle). The benefits of this work have reached multiple stakeholder groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women Innovators and Entrepreneurs: Reflective interviews and network-building activities have provided a platform for female founders to share experiences, building on these reflections we are looking to establish a Women's Health Innovation Network (Kick off meeting scheduled for 13th November 2025). • Other NIHR HRCs and partner organisations, will have the opportunity to benefit from our work through shared learning, resources and case studies.
Next steps beyond GILL	<p>In the short term, D4D will continue to refine its collaboration and assessment processes to ensure gender-responsive decision-making is consistently applied to all new project proposals. The internal tools piloted during GILL, such as Fair Meetings, Airtime Monitoring, and Gender Impact Assessment, are now routinely performed as standard evaluation checks.</p> <p>The Women's Health Innovation Network, established during GILL, will serve as a long-term platform for maintaining momentum. D4D plans to expand this network nationally, linking with other HealthTech Research Centres, academic institutions, and industry partners to support female-led innovation and collaboration.</p> <p>Lastly, D4D will look to share its learning across the wider UK HealthTech networks, contributing case studies, training materials, and evaluation tools to help other organisations adopt GILL-informed practices. These steps will ensure that the impact initiated through this project continues to grow and influence innovation culture across the health technology landscape</p>
Barriers to Impact	Several interconnected challenges emerged during D4D's journey to achieving impact through the GILL project.

	<p>The first barrier was institutional inertia and competing priorities. As a nationally commissioned research centre with multiple programmes of work, embedding new equity-focused methods within existing processes initially met with hesitancy. While the value of inclusion was widely recognised in principle, translating this into new operational routines, such as airtime monitoring or gender assessments of materials required time and consistency. A second challenge related to data visibility and granularity. D4D’s collaboration tracking systems are not structured to capture gender or diversity indicators. Establishing a baseline analysis of 351 collaboration requests therefore required substantial retrospective data cleaning and interpretation. This highlighted the need for more robust data systems capable of capturing diversity metrics in real time to inform decision-making, something we are considering for the future.</p>
<p>Enablers to Impact</p>	<p>Despite these challenges, several key enablers helped D4D to make meaningful progress.</p> <p>Our work within the GILL project gave us a project level priority for this work, providing legitimacy and dedicated staff time for experimentation and reflection.</p> <p>Structured tools and frameworks provided by GILL offered accessible starting points for action. These tools turned abstract ideas about inclusion into practical, repeatable processes, which made it easier to engage colleagues who were new to gender analysis.</p> <p>Finally, external momentum around women’s health policy in the UK, created a favourable context for D4D’s work. This alignment between institutional priorities and policy direction reinforced the importance of continuing gender-responsive innovation beyond the GILL project.</p>
<p>Concrete Actions</p>	<p>D4D undertook a series of concrete actions to address these challenges and build on the enablers identified:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Developing a Gender-Informed Evidence Base <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To address data limitations, D4D retrospectively analysed five years of collaboration data and now plans to integrate gender and diversity tracking fields into its project management system. This will enable ongoing monitoring and inform targeted interventions. 2. Normalising Inclusive Practices Internally <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practical tools such as Fair Meetings and Airtime Monitoring were piloted in a subset of meetings, with findings shared transparently across the team. The clear, data-driven feedback from these exercises helped shift attitudes and embed inclusivity as a shared organisational value.

	<p>3. Strengthening External Partnerships and Visibility</p> <p>The recently established Women’s Health Innovation Network aims to maintain dialogue between female innovators, researchers, and investors. By showcasing positive examples and success stories, we hope the network will help challenge stereotypes and promote women-led entrepreneurship as visible, viable, and valuable.</p>
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AOE4 - Increasing capacity of excluded groups to act as GRSIE in their local community

Challenge: The core issue addressed by this AOE is the lack of access to practical business support and innovation ecosystems for migrant and marginalised local communities, particularly women. Traditional innovation and entrepreneurship pathways often exclude these groups., Another element of this problem emerged during the first cycle of the AOE and that is the existing gap in how local authorities engage with and respond to the lived experiences of these communities. There is no support to include them into the innovation ecosystems and no pathways of communication for their specific needs to be articulated and heard.

AOE: This AOE has focused on the less heard voices, starting first with a group of migrant women and widening into local communities.

During the first cycle, we run a programme to support female ecopreneurs. Through a series of workshops, we provided a group of migrant women interested in creating their own small ecobusinesses with the opportunity to learn new skills and develop their entrepreneurial journeys. By taking part in a showcase, they were able to advertise and promote the maker support services available through FabLab. This initiative empowered these women and helped them integrate into the Coventry business community by equipping them with the necessary tools and resources to start their own businesses.

During the second cycle, we run two iterations of the Citizen Social Science courses. The course trained local people to identify problems and challenges they encounter and care about, provided the tools to help them articulate those challenges into their own research questions and projects.

Impact: This AOE has developed a methodology for the council to hear voices that they don’t normally hear, for getting community voices to decision makers. It is not about having local people researching or providing their perspective into the challenges identified by the council, but a methodology to train local communities to be able to identify and articulate what their problems are, and a communication path to connect that research with the council. The methodology provides a way for authorities to get the real challenges of all communities, including those areas where there is less attention.

This AOE has achieved awareness and recognition that having local people communicating their actual challenges to the HDRC, the council, is a really valuable participation tool. Webinars and recordings evidence that they are taking it seriously. Other impacts: Policy Influence with citizen-led research informing public health discussions and local council priorities. Professional development: participants have gained employment, advanced in their careers, or launched micro-enterprises.

Key objectives	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations OD. To allow gendered educational practices from primary schools to Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) embodying and enabling recognition of the ethical and business cases for gender equality
Horizontal theme	all
Vertical theme	all
Pathway	1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe 2a. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA - individuals 2b. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA - society
Stakeholder groups	University: Gill team, fab lab and students (6) Society: Females from minority communities – summer school participants trying out the GILL tools 10. Gained entrepreneurial skills, started businesses. Citizen Scientists (20): Learnt research skills, developed research projects with support, presented research to councils and national health bodies, influencing policy conversations. Local Authorities: Received direct insight into community challenges and new methodology for community participation. Community Members: Experienced increased visibility and empowerment through participation and recognition.
Next Steps	- Expand the methodology to other councils and authorities - Continue running the citizen social scientist course and expand it to younger people.
Barriers to Impact	The funding for the Ecopreneurs was withdrawn when Coventry City of Culture became bankrupt. Other sources of funding were located to support female entrepreneurs. Support for FabLab was significantly reduced in 2023, leading to mass redundancies in December. It was irrevocably shut down in 2024.
Enablers to Impact	Partnerships and other available programmes working with the targeted community in this AOE.
Concrete Actions	Pivoting and continuing with the objectives of the experimentation in the different available settings and resources for marginalised communities.

AOE5 Addressing Gender Inclusion in Transport Research

Challenge: Fundamentally, transport research is not inclusive. There are longstanding and well-established biases in the way in which transport and services are designed, which systemically discriminate women, limiting opportunities for economic participation, socialisation and more. This fundamentally comes down to the impact of biased transport

<p>research. AOE: This AOE used GILL methods to interview and engage with transport researchers to uncover the barriers and issues within the research. As a result, changes have been implemented locally within the NTDC (CU) to ensure research considers extra time to recruit and engage with under-represented groups. GOAL: Determine new recommendations around how transport research should be conducted, in order to facilitate better transport access and therefore GRSIE. Impact: The results and recommendations of this AOE have been published in a high-impact journal. Case Studies on Transport Policy and have been presented in the House of Lords. The recommendations have also been implemented in a human factors Masters course, delivered twice a year.</p>	
Key objectives	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations
Horizontal theme	Individual and team, innovation and product, tools and methods
Vertical theme	Green transition
Pathway	n/s
Stakeholder groups	<p>University: NTDC team and transport researchers</p> <p>Citizen; who are participants, have lived experience of transport issues. All women who use the transport system. By addressing the root causes of bias in transport, over the long-term, we hope to see transport research that is more inclusive.</p> <p>Industry – transport</p> <p>Transport policy makers</p>
Next Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extend the GiLL methodology beyond gender to embed intersectional inclusion (e.g. disability, ethnicity, socio-economic background) across transport research programmes. • Develop an open-access toolkit and training package for universities and Living Labs, helping research teams assess and address gender imbalance in their own projects. • Continue influencing policy by contributing to the European Commission’s WIDERA and CCAM working groups, ensuring future mobility funding calls integrate gender-equality metrics. • Strengthen the network of female and gender-diverse researchers through mentoring, joint publications, and leadership development initiatives.
Barriers to Impact	<p>Initial reluctance among senior researchers to recognise gender imbalance as a systemic issue rather than a recruitment problem.</p> <p>Time and funding constraints for sustained engagement and data collection across multiple institutions.</p> <p>Significant difficulties in engaging with industry, without prior contacts</p>
Enablers to Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong partnership through the GiLL consortium, providing credibility and cross-national legitimacy.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy alignment with Horizon Europe’s gender equality mandate and WIDERA framework. • Active support from institutional leadership at Coventry University and the NTDC, enabling integration of recommendations into local research policy. • Use of the GILL GIA Tool to provide tangible evidence and an easy entry point for discussion.
Concrete Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducted targeted interviews and workshops with transport researchers to surface lived experiences of gender bias. • Co-developed and piloted inclusive recruitment and leadership guidelines for NTDC-funded projects. • Presented outcomes and recommendations at the House of Lords Commission on Bus Services, raising the profile of gender-inclusive research nationally. • Published peer-reviewed case studies in Case Studies on Transport Policy, ensuring long-term academic visibility.

AOE6 - Measuring citizen’s perceptions of gender equality measures

Challenge: Although numerous gender equality measures are promoted by international, European, and local organisations, it remains very difficult and costly to assess how citizens actually perceive the impact of these policies. Traditional surveys have significant limitations: they are expensive, slow, often unrepresentative, and fail to capture the dynamic and evolving nature of public opinion in digital environments. **AOE:** The AOE intervened in the problem by applying a comprehensive set of **GILL** methods and approaches, combining advanced AI tools with participatory engagement techniques. Natural Language Processing and Sentiment Analysis were used to survey a broad spectrum of people through the comments they make on social networks (e.g., Twitter, etc.) to measure analyse the perception of citizens (expressed in different social networks) regarding different gender innovation measures.

Impact:

- Creation of an interactive dashboard that allows citizens' perceptions of gender equality to be explored in real time and in a way that is understandable to diverse audiences.
- Methodological innovation: combination of explainable AI with participatory Living Lab practices, replicable in other social contexts.
- Cost reduction and increased scalability compared to traditional surveys, democratising access to citizen opinion.
- Support for evidence-based decision-making, both for public policies and for associations and companies.
- Visibility of emotional and discursive patterns.
- Published and presented this method in conferences and settings.

Key objectives	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies, OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations
Horizontal theme	innovation and products , Societal process
Vertical theme	digital transition
Pathway	Pathway 1a: Advancement of knowledge on gender-responsive innovation in Europe
Stakeholder groups	<p>Policy makers and public authorities: access to up-to-date, data-driven evidence to adjust and design more effective equality policies.</p> <p>Companies and associations: actionable feedback on how their equality initiatives are perceived, helping them identify gaps and opportunities.</p> <p>Researchers: validation of new methods for digital social analysis, advancing the field of responsible and explainable AI.</p> <p>Citizens: indirect benefits, as their voices expressed on social media are recognised as relevant inputs in shaping equality policies and strategies (49 in second cycle).</p>
Next Steps	Focus on ensuring the long-term sustainability of the dashboard and on strengthening its dissemination through academic publications, policy briefs, and collaboration with European and local stakeholders.
Barriers to Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • API restrictions and rate limits when extracting data from Reddit, which slowed down the collection process. • Heterogeneity and potential bias of social media data, which may not fully represent citizens' perceptions. • Computational complexity when combining multiple NLP methods (sentiment, topic modelling, embeddings) on large datasets. • Difficulty in designing dashboards that were both scientifically accurate and accessible to non-technical audiences. • Ethical and privacy concerns when analysing sensitive gender-related discussions. • Maintaining stakeholder engagement after the end of the project.
Enablers to Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The GILL Trustworthy AI framework, which provided an ethical and methodological foundation for the work. • Participatory Living Lab approach, including co-design workshops, critique meetings, and round tables with diverse stakeholders. • Strong technical toolkit (Python, PRAW/Reddit API, NLP pipelines, prototyping tools, dashboards). • Institutional and partner support that validated the methodology and results.

Concrete actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimised preprocessing routines and modularised NLP pipelines to reduce computation time and memory usage. • Combined automated NLP analysis with manual validation to mitigate bias and improve thematic accuracy. • Iteratively tested dashboard prototypes with usability feedback to improve clarity, navigation, and accessibility. • reinforce privacy, transparency, and ethical handling of sensitive data. • Organised co-design workshops and Mentimeter surveys to prioritise improvements based on user needs. • Standardised critique meetings and reflective diaries to capture decisions and lessons learned systematically. • Conducted surveys after delivering the final product in order to validate usability and integrate the latest improvements requested by participants
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AOE7 - The use of gender disaggregated data to guide urban planning

Challenge: Mobility planning often assumes that all users share similar travel needs and patterns. However, data consistently show that women and men move differently — in distance, purpose, timing, and transport mode — reflecting broader social and economic inequalities. Despite this, gender-disaggregated data are rarely used to inform transport policies or planning processes.

AOE: AOE 7 applied the method of gender-disaggregated data analysis to uncover systematic differences in travel behaviours between women and men. Using survey data, the team explored how gender shapes mobility in terms of trip purpose, time use, and transport mode.

To make the findings more tangible and communicable, the results were translated into data-based personas — narrative profiles illustrating real-world inequalities in access, flexibility, and safety perceptions. These personas helped turn quantitative evidence into stories that resonate with the participants.

Goals: To raise awareness of opportunities to enhance entrepreneurship and policy actions through the exploitation of gendered datasets and the use of intersectional analysis.

Impact: The creation and use of gender-disaggregated, data-based personas contributed to a new way of communicating gendered evidence within the field of mobility research. Instead of presenting only tables and graphs, the team translated quantitative results into accessible stories that could be easily grasped.

Key objectives	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies
Horizontal theme	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods
Vertical theme	Green transition
Pathway	all
Stakeholder groups	University, Government :Public admin office, Companies (78)

Next Steps	In the future, it could be valuable to replicate this experience in other companies or in non-corporate contexts, to test how gender-disaggregated data can foster reflection and change across different settings. Expanding the approach beyond the initial case would allow the team to explore its potential as a transferable tool for awareness-raising and policy design.
Barriers to Impact	It was challenging to find companies willing to host the activities and to believe in the project's objectives. In addition, it proved difficult to engage participants in the workshops in a truly active and motivated way.
Enablers for Impact	The support from company management was crucial in facilitating the activities. Moreover, access to a large amount of data from corporate mobility surveys provided a strong empirical basis for the analysis, allowing the team to produce evidence-based insights and to communicate findings in a credible and impactful way.
Concrete Actions	To address the limited engagement observed during the activities — especially in the second iteration — the team experimented with different methods and formats to introduce more variety and maintain participants' interest. This adaptation helped make the sessions more dynamic and responsive to participants' expectations, while keeping the focus on the gendered dimensions of mobility.

AOE8- Increasing capacity of start-ups to address gender related issues

Challenge: Start-ups and companies working in fields with a high level of innovation and/or using innovative technologies may not be aware of the benefits of adopting a gender perspective, despite the push effect of several factors (regulatory norms; specific funds; public opinion and mainstreaming media).

AOE: The first cycle of the AOE served as a pilot, which showed some limitations to the original approach that needed to be overcome. The main difficulties to introduce gender innovation model in startup pathways rested on the lack of awareness in the area, which led to lack of interest on pursuing this. The team then conducted a comprehensive assessment of their own materials and participants in 2 of their most impactful hubs. This involved analysing participation data, ownership structures, and gender representation—specifically looking at how many women were involved in the startup ecosystem. The findings revealed that, while their hubs reflected average sector-wide participation rates, gender equality was low.

The team presented the findings internally to colleagues and stakeholders, organising interviews with internal and external experts, sparking conversations and organizing meetings on how to intervene.

- Identified male-centric communication practices and provided targeted advice on how to adopt gender-inclusive language and messaging.
- Interviewed practitioners working within the hub and used their insights to develop practical guidelines for embedding gender perspectives into innovation processes.
- Delivered training sessions, including one with 25 participants (mostly men), which was recorded and packaged as a reusable resource for future cohorts.

<p>Building on this momentum, the team replicated the initiative in other innovation hub, collaborating with other local projects and hosted a one-day dedicated to gender innovation.</p> <p>Goals: To introduce the concept of gender innovation into their incubation programmes and show how to apply it in practice to overcome the bottleneck between being interested/knowing how to do it.</p> <p>Impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisational changes: Increased awareness and requests for gender-focused training within innovation hubs, more collaborations between teams as part of the organisation, gender mainstreaming. Cultural changes within their organisation: Shift in internal discourse, with gender now linked to business outcomes and staff wellbeing, not as a separate section. - Innovation processes: Inclusion of gender perspectives in startup design and development practices. Creation of set of guidelines on how to introduce gender innovation in startup pathways, not only for startups also for incubators. - Setting up of a network of startups interested in gender innovation - Educational practices: Development of training packs and guidelines for practitioners - GILL's expertise is now being used as a foundational knowledge base for other local initiatives. The team has also contributed to a magazine showcasing women-led projects, further amplifying the visibility of gender innovation in the sector 	
Key objectives	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies
Horizontal theme	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods
Vertical theme	No information provided
Pathway	No information provided
Stakeholder groups	FGB staff members, startups, firms, consultancies (125 between internal and external interviewees and participants)
Next Steps	This work is ongoing, the network will continue working and supported. The plan is to change gender training to start-ups beyond introductory courses into more detailed, advanced support.
Barriers to Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One of the most significant barriers was communication among different teams. Messages rooted in gender expertise, while meaningful to those within the field, were often perceived as abstract or moralistic by colleagues from business and innovation. This creates a disconnect and lack of awareness. - Resistance to implementing systems for gender-related data collection. Although these systems proved to be powerful tools for identifying inequalities and guiding interventions, initial pushback was strong. Many stakeholders were hesitant to

	<p>formalize gender metrics, fearing complexity or disruption. It took persistent effort and clear demonstration of value to gain buy-in.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bringing diverse stakeholders into the same room to discuss gender and innovation was itself a challenge. The topic was new and unfamiliar to many, and required careful facilitation to foster open, constructive dialogue.
Enablers to Impact	<p>Other projects with similar objectives Their strong commitment from their leadership, strong input from the director (woman).</p>
Concrete Actions	<p>The team had to reframe their messaging in language that resonated with business and innovation stakeholders, emphasizing relevance to productivity, staff wellbeing, and talent management. Efforts included a new focus on organisational and cultural change within the organisation, which originally were not necessarily considered part of the AOE. That enable the work supporting the startup programme. This method of working, joining gender experts with business experts in the support of startups, has continued beyond GILL interventions for the work that is also carried with other projects, regional, national, and European.</p>

AOE9 - Co-creation of polling platform to support crowdsourcing for GRSIE

Challenge: Public and private organisations often struggle to collect reliable, diverse, and gender-sensitive feedback to inform policies and innovation strategies. Traditional survey tools are costly, time-consuming, and frequently biased toward overrepresented groups, while under-represented voices—such as women, migrants, or marginalized citizens—remain unheard. This limits the inclusiveness, efficiency, and evidence-base of decision-making, particularly in the Transport sector. **AOE:** Using the GILL Toolbox and gendered innovation principles, the AOE developed the Dynamic Survey Management System (DSMS): a multilingual, crowdsourced polling platform that dynamically adapts surveys to responder profiles and incentivizes participation through digital rewards. The system was also designed with GDPR compliance, open data principles, and AI-assisted translation to ensure accessibility and inclusivity.

Impact: The AOE has:

- **Introduced a new model of inclusive, data-driven decision-making**, allowing organisations to reach balanced and diverse audiences in real time.
- **Enhanced organisational and methodological capacity** within SBOING and partner institutions, embedding gender and diversity considerations into digital product design and evaluation processes.
- **Improved efficiency and quality of data collection**, reducing survey fatigue and bias through dynamic incentives and validation mechanisms.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalyzed partnerships and professional development, as demonstrated through the mentoring collaboration with GRNET (EDYTE) for business development, commercialization, and sustainability. • Supported policy influence, by enabling data-driven insights for public agencies to align transport and mobility policies with real societal needs.
Key objectives	OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations
Horizontal theme	H2: Tools and methods H3: innovation and products
Vertical theme	digital transition
Pathway	all
Stakeholder groups	<p>Survey designers, LL, citizens (75)</p> <p>Policy makers now have access to an advanced, gender-responsive survey tool for inclusive policy formulation.</p> <p>Researchers and innovators gain high-quality, open, anonymized datasets for analysis and validation of social innovations.</p> <p>Citizen groups - including women and under-represented communities - benefit from increased visibility and influence in shaping policies that affect their mobility and daily lives.</p> <p>SBOING as an SME has strengthened its commercial and research position in Europe, projecting a 25% growth within three years.</p>
Next Steps	The Polling System (Dynamic Survey Management System – DSMS) has reached a promising early stage of impact, with strong technical validation and strategic partnerships in place. The next steps focus on consolidation, scaling, and sustained exploitation.
Barriers to Impact	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sustaining Long-Term Partnerships and Engagement Maintaining active participation from diverse stakeholders - particularly policy makers and citizen groups - required continuous effort, resources, and communication. Ensuring consistent engagement beyond project timelines remains challenging. 2. Funding and Commercialization Support Transitioning from a research prototype to a market-ready product demanded resources for testing, validation, and business development. Accessing sustained funding and investment beyond the GILL framework was initially a barrier, now partially addressed through the GRNET mentoring grant. 3. Policy Alignment and Institutional Uptake Public institutions often lack mechanisms to adopt new digital tools quickly or to embed gender-inclusive data practices in their workflows.

	<p>4. Data Privacy and Regulatory Compliance Operating within GDPR constraints required meticulous design and legal oversight. Balancing data openness with user privacy and trust added technical and administrative complexity.</p> <p>5. Community Engagement and Representation Recruiting a diverse, representative crowd of respondents - especially from under-represented or vulnerable groups - was time-intensive. Overcoming “survey fatigue” and ensuring balanced participation demanded innovative incentivization and outreach strategies.</p> <p>6. Internal Capacity and Resource Allocation As an SME, SBOING had to balance internal R&D resources between project commitments, commercialization efforts, and continuous innovation, which occasionally slowed development and scaling processes</p>
Enablers to Impact	<p>1. Strong Partnerships and Mentoring Support Collaboration with GRNET (EDYTE) through the EU- and Greece-funded mentoring programme (2025) provided crucial guidance on business development, market analysis, and commercialization. Additionally, engagement with the International Hellenic University and ENoLL strengthened validation, crowd engagement, and alignment with European Living Lab standards.</p> <p>4. SBOING’s leadership placed strong emphasis on gender-sensitive innovation, open data, and digital ethics.</p> <p>5. Funding and Institutional Backing EU project funding through GILL, complemented by the €50,000 GRNET mentoring grant, provided both financial and strategic support during the critical phase of transitioning from prototype to scalable solution.</p> <p>5. Community and Stakeholder Engagement The use of participatory workshops and incentivized polling mechanisms helped attract a diverse pool of users, researchers, and transport professionals.</p> <p>6. SBOING’s existing expertise in open data management, GDPR, and digital ethics enabled the development of a compliant and trustworthy platform.</p>
Concrete Actions	<p>1. Strategic Mentoring & Funding SBOING secured a GRNET (EDYTE) contract under Digital Europe 2021–2027, providing expert support in beta testing,</p>

	<p>business planning, market entry, and investment readiness through 2025.</p> <p>2. Expanded Partnerships Collaborations with the International Hellenic University and ENoLL enabled academic validation, user recruitment, and European outreach, boosting visibility and scaling.</p> <p>3. Incentivization & Recognition A Digital Virtual Currency (DVC) and Badge Management System (DBM) improved survey engagement, data quality, and participation, especially among underrepresented groups.</p> <p>4. Dissemination & Awareness A multi-channel plan—webinars, outreach, and social media—showcased system benefits, using case studies and demos to engage stakeholders and policymakers.</p> <p>5. Sustainability & Business Plan Under GILL’s WP4, SBOING began shaping a commercialization and exploitation strategy aligned with EU innovation and open data ecosystems.</p>
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AOE10 - Reducing gender inequalities in AI /IT workplace and entrepreneurship

Challenge: Many gender challenges and gaps exist in the AI lifecycle, for instance from the data that are used to train AI models, up to the deployment of AI-driven tools and services. This is also exacerbated in light of individuals in the AI/digital entrepreneurship field often being unaware of gender-responsive methods and tools. Finally, gender gaps and inequalities in the AI field extend to the employment sphere as well, whereby there is unequal female representation and career progression in AI/digital entrepreneurship workplaces. **AOE:** AOE10 has implemented a capacity-building (training) program on Human-Centred AI and Data Science, with a focus on gender-responsive AI. The capacity-building program was organised in two parts (iterations), with each of them capitalising on GILL methods and approaches.

Impact: AOE10 impact extends in three areas.

- 1) Professional development. The capacity building program, especially its practical part, has enhanced the knowledge, skills, and digital literacy of women and other stakeholders active in AI/digital entrepreneurship. Those individuals have strengthened their knowledge and skills on gender-responsive AI methods, e.g. solutions to address gender bias in AI, gender impact assessment methods to proactively address the gendered (incl. intersectional) implications of AI tools and products in the broader R&I application field. Capitalising on these, they can further support their career advancement in their AI/IT workplace, as they are equipped with knowledge that is necessary to implement AI under a human-centred lens -now required, in line with EU mandates (e.g. EU AI Act).
- 2) Gender dimension integration into product design, technologies, and innovations. The capacity-building program has both raised awareness and provided practical resources and solutions on how to integrate the gender dimension and intersectionality principles into AI-driven tools, services, and products. It has reached both the local ecosystem (e.g. entrepreneurs in Greece) and the broader EU ecosystem on AI/digital-related innovation

<p>(e.g. through synergies with other EU projects during the AOE execution, e.g. TRINEFLEX EU project). In doing so, it overall suggests the value of GRISE in the digital sphere.</p> <p>3) <u>Gender-related educational practices</u>. AOE10 advanced gender-related educational practices by embedding GILL methods (e.g., co-design, training with a gender lens, gender impact assessment) into digital and AI education sessions and practices. Importantly, by integrating a gender lens into the training activities, the AOE turned education practices on digital skills into a space for inclusive reflection. Such initiatives overall demonstrate how gender-sensitive pedagogy can drive more inclusive innovation ecosystems.</p>	
Key objectives	OB/02 To enhance professional development OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations
Horizontal theme	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods H3: innovation and products H4: Societal process
Vertical theme	digital transition
Pathway	1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe 2a. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA - individuals 2b. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA - society
Stakeholder groups	University – ICT researchers and students inc social scientists Government – regional policy makers Society – civil society reps and NGOs working in female entrepreneurship Women entrepreneurs in the digital/AI innovation field (industry sector and academic sectors, e.g. university spin-offs), Educators, since they can gain inspiration from the AOE training activities and potentially replicate them. (70 in first cycle, 82 in second cycle)
Next Steps	GILL AUTH team will contribute to delivering training within the context of an EIT DIGITAL-funded project. The LOTUS project focuses on green and digital innovation and entrepreneurship. The corresponding training will focus on gender issues in green and digital entrepreneurship. In this context, AOE10 training material will be used, and broader material on GRISE methods will also be showcased.
Barriers to Impact	Firstly, achieving consistent stakeholder engagement occasionally proved challenging, especially on behalf of male stakeholders. Also, individuals engaged in digital entrepreneurship within academia (e.g. spin-off founders) were generally easier to involve, compared to those from the industry sector. From our point of view, this may reflect the fact that gender-related discussions are more widespread

	<p>in academic environments, thus making the respective stakeholders more sensitised and receptive to the AOE10 topic.</p> <p>Secondly, while developing the content of our training sessions, it was occasionally challenging to find a balance between advanced, practical material and introductory content. Still, we deemed it was necessary to ensure that the material remained relevant, understandable, and accessible for participants with diverse levels of expertise in gender-responsive innovation and AI. Concrete actions were pursued in that regard (see question on actions to overcome barriers and leverage enablers).</p>
Enablers to Impact	<p>The resources and methodologies provided by GILL, specifically the rich collection of GRISE methods, offered a strong foundation for designing and implementing the AOE. The 4-phase iterative approach for conducting the AOE similarly proved useful. It enabled reflection on past and upcoming phases, and a careful monitoring of all activities conducted.</p> <p>Additionally, the AUTH team was able to capitalise on experience gained from previous gender-related projects, which facilitated a more informed integration of gender perspectives into digital and AI training.</p>
Concrete Actions	<p>Personal and professional networks were actively mobilised to promote the AOE activities and ensure broad outreach. Notably, synergies with other EU projects (i.e. RESET, TRINEFLEX) while conducting the training sessions further strengthened the AOE's visibility and reach, and contributed to reaching diverse stakeholders (e.g. R&D and industry representatives working on AI/digital innovation and twin transition topics).</p> <p>Then, an additional challenge refers to striking a balance between including advanced, practical material and introductory content in the training sessions. To ensure this balance, the first part (iteration) of the training program focused on raising awareness, and the second part focused on hands-on and practical components.</p> <p>Moreover, even the second part adopted a modular and example-based approach (especially to accommodate the needs of new attendees), combining introductory concepts with practical case studies and interactive exercises, e.g. on gender impact assessment. This allowed participants to engage with the material at their own level of familiarity.</p> <p>Beyond addressing the above challenges through concrete mitigation measures, AOE10 also leveraged some project-level enablers. In particular, the resources accompanying each GRISE method provided useful ideas, material, and information on past initiatives for structuring the AOE in an efficient way (e.g. resources on GIA methods).</p>

AOE11 - Deploying **GILL** methodology in a local authority

Challenge: AIM has championed Gender mainstreaming by signing the European Charter for Equality of Women and Men in Local Life, created an Equality Action Plan, an essential tool to activate gender budgeting and integrated the gender concept and corresponding intersectional approaches in the updated Integrated Urban Development Strategy. Methods and tools are needed to enact these plans.

AOE: Through a collaborative effort, ATIT and AIM have strategically leveraged **GILL** methodologies to intervene in these challenges by focusing on organizational-level change.

Goals: To deliver organisational change and create new paradigms related to mobility, digital transformation, climate change to deliver authentic change process at the local level.

Impact: The AOE has led to tangible organisational and cultural change within Alba Iulia City Hall. Internal regulations and organisational charts were updated to eliminate gender-based discrimination in hiring, promotions, and task assignments. Civil servants gained practical awareness and skills in applying gender equality principles, while women employees benefited from flexible work arrangements, safer environments, and clearer career progression pathways. The municipality itself strengthened governance, modernised its organizational culture, and aligned more closely with European gender equality objectives. Public engagement events expanded awareness beyond the institution, inspiring regional dialogue and exchange of good practices. Finally, ATIT and AIM researchers gained valuable insights into real-world implementation, reinforcing the effectiveness of GILL methodologies in driving measurable, systemic change.

Key objectives	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies OB/02 To enhance professional development OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations
Horizontal theme	all
Vertical theme	V2: green transition V3: digital transition
Pathway	Mostly on pathways 1a and 1b, although through implementing knowledge and practices that are done in a participatory manner, the pathways 2a and 2b are directly addressed as well.
Stakeholder groups	Officials in LAs, citizens, startups and SMEs (355 participants overall in the events of the first cycle, and 261 participants in workshops and events of second cycle)
Next Steps	Our next steps will focus on formalizing the changes initiated, continuing capacity building, and rigorously evaluating our interventions to ensure sustained impact: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •We will ensure the modification and communication of internal regulations to explicitly prohibit gender discrimination, clarify disciplinary sanctions, and update work organization rules to reflect flexible working options. This includes revising job descriptions to remove provisions contrary to flexible work schedules •We will continue organizing and delivering targeted training and workshops on gender equality, non-discrimination, and prevention

	<p>of workplace harassment for civil servants, building on the initial three sessions conducted in March 2025. This includes creating practical tutorials for prevention and intervention in cases of discrimination.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We plan to conduct annual internal surveys to assess staff satisfaction regarding working conditions and adherence to gender equality principles. The insights gathered will directly inform further improvements and policy refinements within the City Hall.
Barriers to Impact	<p>Low levels of awareness and practical understanding of gender equality at the start of the experimentation.</p> <p>Fragmented existing policies and initiatives that were not translating into actual change.</p>
Enablers to Impact	<p>GILL's foundational methodology, providing a robust conceptual framework that significantly shaped interventions.</p> <p>Access to a vital collaborative network through GILL project.</p>
Concrete actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Policy and Practice Analysis: We systematically reviewed Alba Iulia City Hall's internal policies, strategies, and documents to identify opportunities for stronger gender equality integration. This involved sending questionnaires to employees to gauge the current state of gender equality and assess the impact of previous policy reviews. ◦ Collaborative Solution Design: We facilitated focus groups with ATIT and AIM experts, incorporating insights from the private sector to co-design improvements for the City Hall's gender equality policies. This process culminated in a new document outlining three actionable measures for implementation, each with a detailed plan. ◦ Capacity Building and Training: We initiated a public procurement for a trainer and, subsequently, conducted three targeted training sessions (March 18-21, 2025) for civil servants. These trainings aimed to directly increase their awareness and practical application of gender equality principles in their daily work, aligning with GILL's objective of professional development. ◦ Structural Support Mechanisms: We advanced plans for establishing a dedicated information and support point for preventing, detecting, and reporting harassment and gender-based violence, building on existing internal procedures and forming an institutional harassment commission. ◦ Policy Recommendations: Concrete proposals were developed for flexible working arrangements, including telework and part-time options, and innovative initiatives like a "Parents' Transition Month" and paid paternity leave. Additionally, we addressed gender equity in recruitment, career progression, leadership, and decision-making through procedural analysis, specialized training, and organizational chart updates. ◦ Public Engagement: We organized two public events (April 3 and April 17, 2025) in Alba Iulia and Cluj-Napoca to present our public policy recommendations and gather feedback through

	questionnaires, aiming to raise awareness about combating gender discrimination at the policy level.
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AOE12 - Reducing gender inequalities to entrepreneurs during pandemics and crises	
<p>Challenge: The fundamental issue is the lack of gender equality within the entrepreneurial environment, especially when considering past and potential crises.</p> <p>AOE: Using data collected during the pandemic to assess the approaches of the policymakers who created the measures were tested and use participatory techniques to discuss possible innovative approaches that would be applicable in a pandemic and in other areas where entrepreneurs face risks. Goals: To create tools/approaches that will eliminate gender inequalities in business in times of crisis (such as economic crises, pandemic, etc.) and help women entrepreneurs to face the risks.</p> <p>Impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A positive shift in participants' thinking was recorded. The recurring workshops encouraged participants to consider the pros and cons of the policies discussed and their potential impact on different population groups. Discussions evolved from a simple agreement on the necessity of policies, such as attendance allowances for the self-employed, to a more critical perspective that took into account how the formal implementation of the policies might perpetuate gender inequalities. - Policy Influence/Feedback: The workshops provided a platform for feedback on the communication and design of new government policies. - Professional Development/Information Sharing: The workshops, training sessions and training materials increased key actors' awareness of recent crucial changes and policies for entrepreneurs. Participants stated that they had gained new information from the materials on gender-segregated data and declared their intention to use this data in their work. - Organisational/Relational Changes: Personal meetings facilitated the development and maintenance of contacts between individuals from different sectors who would not otherwise meet. This led to a better mutual understanding of perspectives. 	
Key objectives	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies
Horizontal theme	H2: Tools and methods , H4: Societal process
Vertical theme	health and resilience
Pathway	1a: Advancement of knowledge on gender-responsive innovation in Europe 2b. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA - society

Stakeholder groups	<p>Actors from the Quadruple Helix (State Administration, Academia, Business, Non-profit Sector): They gained increased gender sensitivity, new information on government policies and data sources, a platform to provide feedback on policies, and new contacts and improved mutual understanding across sectors (261 participants in all workshops and events organised).</p> <p>Women Entrepreneurs (Indirectly): The AOE aimed to improve their position by encouraging key actors to consider gender when creating future measures and policies, which should result in more effective, gender-sensitive support.</p> <p>Researchers/Organizing Team: The team gained valuable methodological insights into ensuring the participation of diverse stakeholders and facilitating equitable discussions. The team gained new contacts not only in academia.</p>
Next Steps	<p>Continuous Monitoring and Data Expansion: It is necessary to continue monitoring the needs of all Quadruple Helix actors with regard to gender-segregated data, and to encourage key stakeholders to collect relevant data.</p> <p>Targeted and Long-Term Sensitisation: Focus attention on gender sensitisation for individuals in decision-making positions. These activities should be long-term, as one-off awareness-raising events may not change the attitudes of certain individuals.</p> <p>Integrating Gender Perspective into Policy Roll-Out: Similar workshops should be led when new policies are introduced to allow a greater variety of perspectives to enter the debate.</p> <p>Following Up on Data Utilisation Intentions: As participants have expressed an intention to work with the data, the project should follow up to assess whether they have successfully integrated gender-segregated data into their work. This will help to address the stated barrier of the gender agenda that is otherwise given low priority.</p>
Barriers to Impact	<p>Unavailability of Adequate Gender-Segregated Data: A critical barrier was the lack of adequate data, including economic data on entrepreneurs and attitudinal data. Many participants highlighted the absence of comparable statistics to those in other countries. Without this data, key actors were unable to advocate for policies supporting women entrepreneurs.</p> <p>Low Priority of the Gender Agenda: Addressing gender issues was not a priority for management in many of the participating organisations. Professionals had heavy workloads and lacked the time and resources for gender analyses.</p> <p>Low Gender Sensitivity and Resistance: Barriers to using sex-disaggregated data also stemmed from a low level of gender sensitivity. Some participants viewed certain topics as 'gender-neutral', despite data showing differences between genders.</p>

	<p>Furthermore, some participants were a priori resistant to gender-related topics, perceiving gender segregation as undermining the goal of equal opportunities for all.</p> <p>Short-Term Nature of the Experiment: The experiment had a relatively short duration. Real behavioural and attitudinal change (e.g. long-term utilisation of gender-sensitive methods) is a long-term process that cannot be fully realised or consolidated within such a brief timeframe. Changes are expected to manifest over a much longer period.</p>
Enablers to Impact	<p>GILL project infrastructure: The GILL project provided the overarching structure and financial resources necessary to conduct the experiment, which involved multiple activities. Without this framework, it would not have been possible to organise repeated, high-effort participatory workshops and develop extensive educational materials. The knowledge support provided by GILL, which focused on methods and a gender-sensitive approach, was also essential. The GILL project's extensive network of partners enabled us to increase the impact of our work, for example by disseminating information about the publication of our outputs.</p> <p>Our work in this area is long-term. Given that ISAS has long been involved in researching business inequalities and supporting women in business, we already have a fairly stable network of collaborating partners. This has enabled us to build on our existing contacts and further expand this work within the project. At the same time, our expertise in gender-sensitive methods and theory provides a solid foundation for innovative work with new approaches.</p>
Concrete Actions:	<p>The main way we overcame barriers was by constantly learning from past activities and insights. We had to apply our current knowledge and methods in innovative ways, adapting them to the specific conditions and problems that arose during our experiment. Another important factor in promoting impact was maintaining informal contact with our participants. This allows us to participate in joint activities over the long term and monitor the project's impact.</p>

AOE13 - Retaining women in tech companies by changing workplace culture

Challenge: Although tech companies hire more women to reduce some forms of gender inequalities, they do not change their workplace culture or make their products more gender friendly. **Goals:** To convince tech companies and demonstrate how they can make gender inequality a priority to change their team practices, design methods and tools to retain women in the innovation cycle and to develop gender-responsive innovations.

Impact: To reach this goal AOE 13 collaborated with the industry. Specifically, this means working closely with a real-world company where the Living Lab phases were carried out in two iterations, each of which was completed in full. A survey on psychological safety confirmed the aforementioned problem for this company, as it revealed a gender gap in psychological safety. This was also confirmed by qualitative interviews with female employees.

The collaboration involved working with various stakeholders within the company (employees, executives, management, works council, volunteers committed to the issue of promoting women, and cross-divisional diversity officers). The selection and involvement of employees in decision-making processes, for example, regarding which methods should be implemented, represents the GILL method “hear the right voices,” and precise and selective communication represents the “inclusive communication” method.

In addition to introducing numerous smaller GILL methods such as round robin and fair meetings, the first iteration specifically involved establishing a women's network for the software development department and later a women's network for the entire company.

This was furthered through collaboration with the local community by establishing a local, company-independent women's network for women in IT/tech.

Various methods such as observations and reflective diaries showed after the first iteration that this wide range of services offered by the women's network was important, but at the same time often failed to address the everyday practices that make women's working lives unfair.

Carefully selected methods (e.g., SPARK to engage in reflection with diversity managers across departments) led to the GILL methods becoming known in a wide variety of circles, whether it be various department heads who now use the methods, diversity managers who disseminate the practices, or individual teams in which team leaders or individual employees have recognized the need and, after making contact, have inquired about them at internal conferences, for example, and have thus been introduced to GILL methods or discussed them for their specific situation.

However, the focus of the second iteration was the co-creation of a new method for teams. This meant integrating all existing challenges: too little time for managers to introduce new methods. Curiosity among managers, while many employees showed little empathy for the situation of women. And, in principle, too little time: the new method (evoke change talk) integrates input with a focus on motivational interviewing into existing team meetings (such as a department's monthly meeting) at regular intervals. This is in line with the desire of female employees that their colleagues learn what it means to be a woman in the tech sector and should lead to more "change talk" overall, i.e. moments when men themselves articulate reasons for, and commitments to, advancing gender equality, which is also in line with the (male) allies method. Word about the method is currently spreading, and it is currently being implemented by a team of developers, a development department, and a management group. The employee responsible for this in the company has been given the go-ahead by her boss to work on it during her working hours and is now also being invited by other teams to discuss the topic.

At the beginning, there was mainly this one company, but by working on a stakeholder network, contacts were expanded, which also led to cooperation with other companies.

Key objectives	OA/01 To enable the organisational and cultural changes in agencies. OC/03 To increase the integration of gender and diversity into PD, technologies and innovations
Horizontal theme	H1: Individual and team practices H2: Tools and methods
Vertical theme	Digital transition
Pathway	Pathway 1a. Advancement of knowledge on gender-responsive innovation in Europe Pathway 1b. Advancement of practices on gender-responsive innovation in Europe Pathway 2a. Strengthening of the innovation and inclusiveness dimension of the ERA – individuals
Stakeholder groups	Tech companies, women. Overall, the group of “female employees” within our real-world laboratory company has benefited from the GILL methods, but so have all employees, as the issue of fairness in teams does not only affect women and is now on everyone's lips, unlike three years ago when the GILL project was launched. It is represented at all internal conferences, and the women's network has given two people time to work on the topic during their working hours. Beyond the company, numerous interventions such as participatory workshops within the local women's network have also reached a large audience. The privilege walk method was often used because the interactive physical experience repeatedly elicits feedback that it has enabled certain differences in the realities of life to be understood for the first time. (186 participants in workshops and events in first cycle, 359 in the second).
Barriers to Impact	Leadership support: The biggest challenge is people who are not affected by marginalization and do not understand it, who do not believe that discrimination still exists and that their reality creates unfairness.
Enablers to Impact	Partnerships with several stakeholders from several companies to gain a stakeholder network that includes the local community.
Concrete Actions	Our approach to fair work culture focuses on practices from different perspectives: For example, presenting the results from the understanding phase (lower scores for women in psychological safety) to top management, attending internal conferences, diversity weeks, barcamps, and women's network events, and specifically addressing cross-divisional managers responsible for diversity management or human resources, as well as individual executives. In addition, always make the most of opportunities when willingness is shown: Following a (senior) manager's interest in a privilege walk at the internal developer conference, it was immediately agreed that time would be set aside for our topic in their management meeting (without knowing at the time what we

	would be doing specifically). This was then well planned and, in co-creation with the people involved, the evoke change talk method was developed and launched in this team. And this approach is always appropriate: use the slightest interest as a basis for direct agreements so as not to let the moment and the interest pass you by.
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AOE14 - Increasing understanding of intersectionality and transport in smart cities through gamification	
<p>Challenge: Smart cities struggle to communicate their thinking to citizens. Smartness becomes equate with the use of technology, not issues around inclusion, effective and efficient services that cut across population groups. AOE: Engaged multiple stakeholders to codesign and produce an interactive, education game using results from the TInnGO project to enable citizens to intervene and submit ideas to transport planning and policy in a given context. Goals: Increase the understanding of intersectionality and transport in smart cities through gamification. We understand gamification in a very broad sense within the notion of nudging games and game-based learning.</p> <p>Impact: Immediate impact has been measured in asking if this game has changed the mindset of the gamer and the wish to change practices. An aim which has been met - see summary of results Long term impact: the two games have been made part of a newly launched start up – business, headed by one of the post docs in the GILL project. The business plan includes the game as part of an educational package, which will be offered for municipalities, state institutions, universities, high schools and NGO.</p>	
Key objectives	OD/04 To allow gendered educational practices? OC: Product design, technologies, Innovation?
Horizontal theme	Tools & Methods Innovation & Products
Vertical theme	Green transition
Pathway	Ia, ib, Ic
Stakeholder groups	Citizens, museums, teachers., transport planning (144 participants)
Next Steps	Find start-up capital needed for both salary and capital for producing an appropriate number of games. Future plans also include new game editions across national borders and languages. If this is going to be realized there is a need for ongoing updates of question and knowledge related to the particular (national/international) contexts. Online and technical solutions may also be considered.
Barriers to Impact	Limited budget, not enough for professional design or online game development. Hard to translate complex diversity/transport data into engaging questions for the public and educational.

	<p>Context differences across countries made content less universally relevant. Transport and diversity issues vary greatly by region, requiring constant updates to game content.</p> <p>Some partner institutions used outdated gaming consoles, privileging certain demographics (young men).</p> <p>Need for ongoing updates and start-up capital.</p> <p>Some partners did not address gender/diversity directly, limiting alignment with project aims.</p>
Enablers to Impact	<p>Strong partnerships (universities, labs, municipalities, think tanks). The Ludo design of the game helped with global accessibility.</p> <p>Iterative testing and surveys were very useful to guide refinements and make the game more engaging and relevant.</p> <p>Research on game-based learning showed motivational benefits.</p> <p>Interest in gamification: dissemination via publications, videos, conferences.</p> <p>Entrepreneurial pathway: Integration into DiverCities start-up, creating a business plan for municipalities, schools, NGOs.</p>

[\[4\]](#) Revised draft title of AOE:

Annex 4: Example of an Impact worksheet

Please put a tick in one of the following 6 boxes to indicate the impact most relevant to the actions/output you are going to describe. This could have been conducted during the project or one you would like to implement after the project to achieve impact.

Impact 1 An enhanced, more open, and inclusive research and innovation system

During project After project

Impact 2 A stronger alignment of strategic R&I with society needs, expectations, and values.

During project After project

Impact 3 Stronger knowledge sharing and collaboration

During project After project

Then answer the following questions, as fully as possible. This can relate to **any** output/outcome /action you have undertaken to have impact, at any stage of the project. It does not necessarily have to relate to an AOE.

Many thanks
Andree and Oihane

Description and proposed impact

1. What is the specific impact you hope to achieve in relation to Impact 1,2 or 3 Increasing gender sensitivity among the 'quadruple helix' actors working in the field of supporting women's entrepreneurship.

2. What outcome/part of the project are you using to achieve this? E.g. paper, mentorship, GRSIE tools?
_____participative workshops, using GRSIE tools_____

3. What would the impact look like 'on the ground'? Participants will pay more attention to the impact of their measures/actions on gender equality.

4. Who are the stakeholders? Academics citizens industry local authorities entrepreneurs
policy makers other, please state _____

5.How would you describe the size of the impact you wanted: micro meso macro local regional
 national EU wide sector specific other, please state _____

6. What best describes the interaction ? indirect/mediated through the output financial
direct/personal other, please state _____

7. What would success look like? Consider the gender impacts of the measures/activities that actors are taking at the stage when they are being developed.

8. What did you do in advance to make this a productive interaction? There were participatory discussions in which current measures were discussed in depth. We gave participants the opportunity to reflect on things they normally took for granted, which led to a clash of different discourses.

9. What follow up actions did you take to achieve you aim? After the first iteration, we collected feedback. Before the second participatory workshop, we sought the views of those who were not planning to participate, so that their opinions could be incorporated into the discussion.

10. Which pathway archetype best describes this? 5. mobility pathway___ and why did you use this? Between the first and second phases, our internal expert team evaluated the impact of the initial iteration. We critically assessed the shortcomings present and adjusted the second iteration accordingly, ensuring it would have a greater impact.

11. To what extent did you achieve the desired impact?

Not at all Beyond expectations

12. How would you characterise your stakeholders?

Knowledgeable	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Uninformed
Interested	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Disinterested
Receptive	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hostile
Able to effect change	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Unable to effect change

Please explain

As expected, the impact was moderate. There were no major systemic changes; rather, the participants reflected on issues that had not been considered in the first phase. They recognised the value of certain measures, but in the second phase they were more aware of their potential unequal impact.

Above expectations was the creation of connections between actors with diametrically opposed views.

13. How would you characterise the level of capacity for change in the system?

Low High

Please give reason

The problem we encountered was that the people who attended our events were interested in the topic, but they did not have the influence on effect system change. This meant that the impact was more local than comprehensive systemic change.

14. How influential do you think the following were/would be in achieving the impact you sought?

	<i>Low</i>				<i>High</i>
Timing of message	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Perceived cost to stakeholder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall priority	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Level of noise in system (message lost)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Articulation of message	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Compatibility with business goals	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Compatibility with stakeholder ambitions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Effort needed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Size of challenge	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

15. What would you have done differently/any other comments

We believe that we have done everything within our power to fulfil the objectives of this project. However, a greater impact could be achieved through longer-term efforts.